

**Conference Proceedings of International Conference on
Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)
(JULY 29-31, 2025)**

Jointly Organized By

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

(Estd. 25 Aug 1969 - (Affiliated To D.D.U. Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur(U.P.) | B++ with C.G.P.A. 2.84)

&

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow UP

(Run by: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860, Reg. No. LUC/03140/2019-2020, INDIA)

(Registered by : Govt. of India , NITI Aayog, Reg. No. UP/2019/0248444)

दिग्विजयनाथ स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय, गोरखपुर
शिक्षकगण

Edited by

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Parikshit Singh

Dr. R. K. Shukla

**Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary
Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)**

Editors

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary
MKSES Educational Society,
Lucknow, UP, India

Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh
Professor
Dept. of Botany
Digvijay Nath P.G College
Gorakhpur, UP, India

Prof. R.K. Shukla
Professor
Department of Physics
University of Lucknow, Lucknow, U.P., India

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur was established on 25th August, 1969 by the managing committee constituted under Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur. It is situated in civil lines, the heart of Gorakhpur city in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Days are not far when the college shall be able to realize the vision and the grand mission of the great soul 'Brahmleen Mahanth Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj', whose name decorates the identity of the College. His Holiness 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj, former Head Priest of world fame Shree Guru Goraksh nath Temple, Gorakhpur was the founder of the college. He was a pioneer of educational renaissance in Eastern U.P. It was none other than himself who established Maha Rana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur in 1932 to spread the light of knowledge and awareness among the people of Eastern U.P. whom he found to be living in utter poverty, ignorance and backwardness of all kinds. He came to Gorakhnath temple, Gorakhpur at the age of five from the Royal Rana Family of Mewar, Rajasthan in 1900 and grew and learnt the lesson of selfless sacrifice and dedication to the service of humanity under the spiritual care of his accomplished great Guru Yogiraj Gambhir Nathji Maharaj. In 1949-50 Maharana Pratap Degree College was established by "Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad Gorakhpur", which was later sacrificed to contribute to the establishment of Gorakhpur University. Maharana Pratap Degree College along with its entire infrastructure including teaching and non-teaching staff was dedicated to count for the resources to meet up the requirements for establishment of the University of Gorakhpur, in 1958. Post-merger of the Maharana Pratap Degree College into Gorakhpur University, there was a vacuum in the educational facilities of the area. To fill in this vacuum, Digvijai Nath College was established on 25th August 1969. Now the administration of this college is run by the managing committee appointed by Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, under inspiring guidance and patronage of jis Holiness Mahant Aditya Nath ji Maharaj. His holiness Gorakshpeethadheeshwar 'Brahmleen Mahant Avedya Nathji Maharaj (the Ex-Head priest of Gorakhnath Temple) and his worthy successor who is the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh His Holiness reverent Yogi Aditya Nath ji maharaj, is the guiding light behind more than four dozen institutions, including D.N.P.G. College Gorakhpur, successfully run by the Maharana Pratap Shiksha

Parishad. The College holds the glory of functioning with four faculty disciplines covering various departments at undergraduate and post graduate levels. College provides education at graduate level in eleven subjects covering Arts, six in Science and Commerce. Post Graduate teaching is offered in Ancient History Archeology & Culture, Geography and Hindi & Modern Indian Language; apart from its renowned Bachelors in Education. In addition to these, part time classes in eight non-practical subjects are also offered and the Institution also serves as an education center of Uttar Pradesh Rajarshi Tandon Open University; and hosts their 26 courses at U.G and P.G. level. In light of letter dated 15 June 2006 from U.P. State Council for Higher Education we revised 'The Self Study Report' on modified format on the basis of guidelines of NAAC-Bangalore. Digvijai Nath P.G. college, Civil lines, Gorakhpur has been placed on the UGC-NAAC approved list in 2021 with B⁺⁺ grade with C.G.P.A 2.84. Gorakhnath sahyik kendra is established by UP Hindi Sansthan Lucknow in 2019. The institution, guided by the vision of Brahmleen Digvijay Nath Ji Maharaj, is a believer in multi-dimensional development of students. His vision of 'healthy mind residing in a healthy body' is relied and practiced by the Institution. Beyond books and classes students are groomed by extra-curricular and co-curricular activities. Students have participated in Inter-University and Inter-State games & sports as well as in the prestigious republic day parade in the National capital. Students of the college participate and compete with the students of other colleges of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, in different competitions organized during Founder's Week every year from 4th to 10th December. Institution also hosts an annual sports festival. To meet the Post-Accreditation requirements, the College also has the Internal Quality Assurance Cell. IQAC maneuvers to assure the internal quality of Academic and Administrative activities through its different committees at college.

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow, U.P., India
(Run by: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

The Science-Tech is one of the premier institutes of Lucknow dedicated to organize various academic activities like conferences, seminars, workshops and training programmes in collaboration with many national & international organizations and Institute have own Publication house and Journals' to be published Edited books, Course books and research papers. The institute is run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow. The society is working for the development of deprived socio-economic students by providing them quality education.

International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP are going to organize International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025) from July 29-31, 2025. This Conference will provide a platform to the researchers and academicians to enrich their methodological and analytical skills.

This has brought us to a juncture where innovation and interdisciplinary research are crucial for the survival of humanity. It has become a moral imperative these days to have exchange of ideas using available advanced technologies. Hence the global scientific community must become a key player on scientific and technological innovations, but also to impart true education to the academia and industry across the globe. In the era of social distancing, **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, U.P. & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, U.P.** India has chosen an e-platform for the scientific community to share their ideas and research by organizing a three International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025). Conference will include Keynote lectures, Invited lectures, Special Talk, Oral presentations and Poster presentations.

Chief Patron

Mahanth Yogi Aditya Nath Ji Maharaj, Manager/ Secretary, Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Patron

Prof. Udai Pratap Singh, President, Maharana Pratap Siksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, UP, Former Vice Chancler, V.B.S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur

❖ Chairperson

Prof.(Dr.).Om Prakash Singh, Principal, Digvijay Nath P.G, College Gorakhpur, UP

Co-Patron

Mrs. Shweta Singh, Chairman, Governing Body, MKSES Educational Society, Lucknow, UP, India

Prof. Dev. D. Sharma, Executive Director, Global Knowledge, Foundation (GKF), USA

Prof. (Dr) Anil Kumar Singh, Principal, MGPG College, Gorakhpur, UP, India

Prof. P Chhakraborty, Visiting Professor, Rutgers the State, University of New Jersey, USA

Senior Advisor

1. Prof. D.S. Hooda, Former, (Pro-Vice Chancellor) Kurukshetra University, Haryana, India
2. Prof. N.B. Singh, (Emeritus Professor Chemistry, SBSR & RTDC Sharda University, Greater Noida, UP)
3. Prof. Somesh Shukla, Professor Department of Commerce, University of Lucknow, Lucknow
4. Prof. R. K. Shukla (Professor, Department of Physics, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP)
5. Prof. C.K. Dixit, Dean & Head, DSMR University, Lucknow, India

Convener

- ❖ **Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh**, Professor Dept. of Botany, Digvijay Nath P.G College Gorakhpur, UP, India

DIGVIJAI NATH POST GRADUATE COLLEGE

GORAKHPUR-273001

(NAAC B⁺⁺ Accredited College)

☎ : 0551-2334549

☎ : 09792987700

e-mail : digvijayans@gmail.com

☎ : dnpggkp@gmail.com

website : www.dnpgcollege.edu.in

Affiliated to
D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to **International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025) from July 29-31, 2025**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to National and International students, Academicians, Researchers and Industrialists to interact and involve in research and innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of research, analytics and innovation.

I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Prof. Udai Pratap Singh
President

Maharana Pratap Siksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, UP
Former Vice Chancler
V.B.S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur

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Prof.(Dr.). Om Prakash Singh
Principal

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☎ : 09792987700

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D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur

Ref. No. : /2024-25

Date :22-07-2025

Message

I'm incredibly happy to send my greetings on this historic occasion to the core committee of the share that Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP are going to organize International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025) from July 29-31, 2025. In current scenario interdisciplinary research is foundation of every country and humanity has directly benefited from its results. Interdisciplinary research grounding and education are essential to future competitiveness, because knowledge creation and innovation frequently occur at the interface of disciplines. Inter disciplinary agendas widen the horizon of knowledge and aids to ensure better educational programs. This conference offered opportunity to connect all researchers, scientists and faculties together at one single platform to share their innovative ideas and skills which is helpful to carry out future research in well-organized way.

Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh
Professor
Coordinator IQAC

MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860)

Reg. Office : Hydrel Nahar Chauraha, Housing Society Sarojini Nagar, Lucknow - 226008, UP India

Head Office : 1ST Floor Building No.85 A (Nanak Arcade) Near Shani Mandir,

Parag Road, LDA Colony, Kanpur Road, Lucknow-226012, UP India

Contact No. : +91 9838298016, +91 8299547952 | E-mail : manrajkuwarsec@gmail.com

Mrs. Shweta Singh
Chairman
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP, India

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to share that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025) from July 29-31, 2025.**

The conference will offer a great opportunity to discuss important issues, researches and topics from varied fields and will allow exchange of knowledge, ideas.

This conference is also an opportunity to meet virtually many eminent faculty, scholars and public health specialists of national and international repute on a common platform.

I & my team ensure that the audience will experience the exchange of scientific knowledge and return with a satisfactory take home message.

[Shweta Singh]

Date: 25/07/2025

SCIENCE TECH INSTITUTE

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. Higher Education Department & Ordinance No. 8 of 2002)

Run by : **MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY**

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860, Reg. No. LUC/03140/2019-2020)

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Contact No. : +91 9838298016, +91 8299547952 | E-mail : sciencetech487@gmail.com

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP

Message

On behalf of the whole organizing team, share that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025) from July 29-31, 2025**. I am sure that this online gathering will provide a common platform for academicians of different branches (Medical Sciences, Humanities etc.), public health experts & researchers to put forth their research studies and works.

I take this opportunity to acknowledge all the concerned authorities or persons for their permission, continuous support and guidance in arranging this conference. I am sure that this conference will succeed in the walk on Commerce this path for improving the various soft skills of faculties and students in varied fields.

Date: 23/07/2025

[Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh]

International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)

Mode: Virtual

Organized by

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

(Estd.25 Aug 1969 - (Affiliated To D.D.U. Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur(U.P.) | B++ with C.G.P.A. 2.84)

In Collaboration with

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow,

Details of Programe Schedule DAY-1 (29th July, 2025)

For Technical Support Contact Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh (8299547952)

WhatsApp group Chat link: <https://chat.whatsapp.com/Kh47bGorvA57Megahv2zH3>

Inaugural Session Hosted by: Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83979498869?pwd=W1vk7aGYla2Ag7kpb43QtEDs7zpR6G.1 Meeting id- 839 7949 8869 Password- 433868	
11:20 AM	INAUGURATION AND WELCOME ADDRESS BY Conference Chair/Conveners/ Organizing Secretaries
11:45 AM-12:00 PM Key Note Speaker	Dr. Sanjay Kumar, Nodal Officer, MRU & Professor, Dept. of Pathology PGIMS, Rohtak
12:00-12.25 PM IT01	Dr. N.K. Sharma: - “ Renewable Energy Development in India”
12:25-12:50 PM IT02	Dr. Poornima Singh: - “The Role of AI in Future of Healthcare”
12:50-1:15 PM IT03	Dr. Garima Awasthi: - “From Academia to Industry: QA/QC Career Scope for Biotech and Life Science Aspirants”
1.15-1.35 PM IT04	Dr. Shambhavi Mishra “ Application of Flexible statistical modeling to study undernutrition among under-five children in India”
1.35-2.00 PM IT05	Dr. Ritika “ Insights on impact of different modification techniques on functional properties of dietary fiber”

2 PM to 5 PM Day 1 (29th July,2025)

Session Chair: Dr.Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Neha Singh

Dr. Praveen Kumar Mishra

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83979498869?pwd=W1vk7aGYla2Ag7kpb43QtEDs7zpR6G.1>

Meeting id- 839 7949 8869 Password- 33868

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral/Poster

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A1	Mrs.Rupali Deshmukh	Phytochemical profiling and Antioxidant activity of tridax procumbens
A2	Dr.Bhavana Sharma	Nanotechnology in Environmental Remediation: Current Advances and Future Prospects
A3	Ms.Pallavi Singh	Design of Various Derivatives with Naphthoquinone Moiety: Prediction of Bioactivities of Virtual Derivatives Using Developed QSAR Models
A4	Dr. Sondeep Kaur	Neuromarketing Cues in FMCG Packaging Design: A PRISMA-Compliant Systematic Review of Color, Shape, and Texture Effects on Consumer Attention and Impulse Purchasing
A5	Ms.SHRUTI BHONSLE	Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for Social Risk Assessment: Innovations in Social Work Practice
A6	Dr.Garvita Singh	Life Beyond Work: Understanding the Human Experience of Work Life Balance in India
A7	Prof.Maneesh Yadav HARSHIKA KAPOOR	The role of digital identity in ensuring inclusive governance systems
A8	Dr.Sangeeta verma	A critical review on Kalwat bhojan ,fasting, autophagy and itâ€™s effect on health
A9	Mrs.SOMA RANI KARAN	Agricultural Economics
A10	Dr.Rahinaz Usman Bedrabettu	MicroRNA-191a and Nephrin Protein: Key Modulators of Nephrotic Syndrome Severity
A11	Dr.Adil Ali Ansari (PT)	Effect of Blood Flow Restricted Resistance Training on Peak Lower Body Strength
A12	Dr.Arnold Nikhilesh	EFFICACY OF NEURODYNAMIC TREATMENT ON PAIN AND ROM (SLR) IN SUBJECTS WITH SCIATICA
A13	Dr.Dilpreet Kaur	Scope of nano formulations in combating ticks
A14	Dr.Gayathri N.	Role of NCC and NSS in Youth Leadership and Nation Building Computational Analysis of Energy Metabolism in Drosophila melanogaster under Hypoxia
A15	Dr.Ishwar Chandra Maurya	Photovoltaic Efficiency of TiO ₂ -Based DSSCs Using Natural Dyes from Cassia Flowers
A16	Dr.Pratima Maurya	The Power of Gratitude: Enhancing Happiness Through Positive Practice
A17	Dr.SUNITA DEVI	मध्यकालीन संत साहित्य और लोकजागरण
A18	Prof.Dr Ramesh Kumar Prajapati	Application of Artificial Intelligence in Disposal of Solid Waste through Membrane
A19	Dr.PRATIMA SINGH	optimizing CLOUD SERVICES WITH QUEUEING THEORY

A20	Dr.JASBIR SINGH	Effect of tablet shape on swelling rate through rapid disintegrating tablets
A21	Dr.Seema Rani Sarraf	Positive and negative metaemotion in CHD patients with and without hypertension
A22	Prof.Shallu Sachdeva Abhay Patel Tanvi Kaushik Badal Chawla Abhishek Yadav	Determination of stability constants of some bivalent and trivalent metal ions with a biologically active ligand
A23	Dr.Girija Akkinepally	A study on identification of gaps in public healthcare facilities for NQAS certification
A24	Dr.Shital S.Deshmukh	Functional Morphology of suckers and suction discs in leeches in Melghat region Maharashtra
A25	Dr. Akhilesh Sharma	Spider and its Role in Ecological Ecosystem and Agriculture field

6 PM to 12 PM Day 1 (29th July,2025)

Session Chair: Dr. Pratyasha Tripathi

Dr. Neelam Bansal

Dr. Hardeep Kour

Dr. Anuradha Mishra

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83979498869?pwd=W1vk7aGYla2Ag7kpb43QtEDs7zpR6G.1>

Meeting id- **839 7949 8869** Password- **33868**

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral/Poster

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	Name	Title
IT06	Dr. Pratyasha Tripathi	A Critical Evaluation of Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana in Bihar
IT07	Dr.Ashwini Katole	Male perspective and involvement in Family planning: Insight from a Qualitative exploration
A26	Dr. Arpita kackar	Health Beliefs and preventive behaviors in the context of life style diseases: a co-relational study
A27	Dr. Sonia Saini	Phytopharmacologically activities of syzygium aromaticum
A28	Dr.Abhinav Srivastava	Comparative evaluation of effectiveness of Tutorial and Fishbowl small group teaching methods among medical undergraduates
A29	Dr.Shilpa Premchand Badhe	An Integrative Approach to Anesthesia and Pain Management: Scientific Insights from Ayurvedic Medicine
A30	Dr.Parul Trivedi	Importance of biodiversity in ecosystems
A31	Dr.KAPIL RAGHUWANSHI	Estimation of Serum Vitamin D in Patients of Generalized Anxiety Disorder: A Cross Sectional Study in A Government Medical College of Madhya Pradesh, India
A32	Dr.Dr Gopal Singh Yadav	NIL
A33	Mrs.Mayuri	Adoption of Ind AS (Accounting Standard): An Appraisal of the Impact on Financial Performance of Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited (BHEL)
A34	Dr.Saloni Verma	Personalized Medicine in Oral Cancer
A35	Dr.Shivaji Pawar	COMPERATIVE LITERARY STUDY OF THREE TIKAS OF CHARAK SAMHITA NAMELY AYURVED DIPIKA, JALPAKALPATARU TIKA AND CHARKOPSKAR WSR TO

		DIRGHANJIVATIYA ADHYAYA (1to 25 shloks)
A36	Dr. Pankaj Masodker	ROLE OF AAMA IN AYURVEDIC DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT: A LITERARY REVIEW
A37	Dr.Antim j. vyas	ROLE OF SWARNPRASHAN AS IMMUNITY BOOSTER AND ITS EFFECT ON NEUROLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILD.
A38	Mrs.vinita jamdade	A study to assess the lived experiences of stroke survivors in the selected areas of Pune city
A39	Miss.Agrima Singh	Blockchain technology in financial management
A40	Mr.Malkhan Shree Ramesh	A CRITICAL STUDY ON THE FEASIBILITY OF AN AMBITION OF ONGC TO ACHIEVE NET ZERO EMISSION BY 2038
A41	Dr.Satish Kumar Ms.Nidhi Saini	Perception of Small and Marginal Farmers Towards the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: A Study of Kurukshetra District of Haryana
A42	Ms.Anushree Narekuli	Dental practitioners awareness and referral practices for Physiotherapy in Temporomandibular Disorder management in Maharashtra: A Study Protocol
A43	Mrs.Minati Das	Empowering Non-Clinical Women Through Breast Self-Examination Training: A One-Group Pretest-Posttest Evaluation
A44	Dr.Rajani Singh	Natural Deep Eutectic Solvents (NADES) : A green Alternative in modern chemistry
A45	Dr.RIYA MARKAM	Zingiber officinale Nanoparticles as a Potential Anti Inflammatory and Antibiotic Nanomedicine
A46	Dr.Bandana Dwivedi	Harnessing Green Chemistry: A Strategic Review of Environmental Benefits and Practical Constraints
A47	Dr.Nisha Kapoor	Delineating molecular mechanisms underlying central obesity
A48	Dr. Nancy	Recent developments of rodent control strategies in India
A49	Mrs.Priyanka	Research and Innovation with AI in English Literature
A50	Mrs.Priyanka Toppo	Evolution and Green Synthesis of Carbon Dots
A51	Dr.Imtiaz khan	Testicular histology alterations and impaired steroidogenesis in fluoride exposed rats
A52	Dr.Heena	Environmental applications of iron impregnated metal organic frameworks
A53	Dr.Yash P. Khajuria	Biochemical analysis of microbial communities associated with Morchella species
A54	Ms.Gharate Seema Vedu	Evaluation of Antimicrobial and Antifungal Potential of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Dairy-Based Probiotic Sources
A55	Mr.SOUMITRA BHATTACHARYA	The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Financial Performance of Firms, with emphasis on Industry 5.0
A56	Ms.Sukanksha Singh	The impact of Role Conflict on Turnover in IT sector organization
A58	Ms.Sakshi Chamoli	Fintech and India's Green Transition: A Study on Digital Finance for Sustainable Development in a Global Context
A59	Mrs.Namrata Chugh	Impact of IT-Enabled Services Expenditure on Decision Quality in Corporate Governance: An Empirical Analysis through Financial Performance Metrics
A60	Ms.Shristi Chamoli	A Study on the Impact of Virtual Reality Tourism in contrast with Real-Time Tourism experience on Customer Satisfaction: Indian perspective
A61	Ms. farheen azad	Fermentation-Driven Enhancement of Glycine max Metabolites: Therapeutic Implications for Postmenopausal Osteoporosis
A62	Ms.Sandhya Nagolu	Machine Learning Based Prediction of Patellar Malalignment Using Radiographic Anatomical Indices in Patellofemoral Pain Disorders: A Comparative Study
A63	Mrs.Chandni yadav	Educational problems of child labourers

A83	Mr.Ankit babu	Pre-existing Statistical Predictive Models for Early Detection of Cancer: A Comprehension review
A84	Miss.Anjali Sharma	Experiential learning in the course curriculum of two year B.Ed programme of University of Jammu: A Study
A85	Mr.PAWAN KUMAR RATHAUR	ब्लॉक सफीपुर जनपद उन्नाव में जनसंख्या वृद्धि का कृषि भूमि उपयोग पर प्रभाव: एक भौगोलिक अध्ययन
A86	Mrs.Mohini gupta	Role of Ethical Practices in Modern Business
A87	Ms.Kuntal Mandal	An exploratory study on the Quality of Life among elderly residing in selected old age home of West Bengal
A88	Ms.Roshni Kumari	A Review on Metal Oxide Nanoparticles as Antimicrobial Agents
A89	Mrs.Namita Singh	An analytical study on ASHA workers' role in maternal health services in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh
A90	Miss.Shreya Sharma	Thoughts That Trap: The Role of Metacognitive Beliefs in Emotional Distress and Substance Use Among Indian Youth
A91	Mr.Vivek Kumar	Title: To Determine Seroprevalence Rates Among Different ABO/Rh Group
A92	Miss.Gayatri Oak	Assessment of Carbon Sequestration to describe the conservation potential of a sacred groves from Guhagar Taluka, Maharashtra India
A93	Ms.Anu Nawhal	Organic manure Efficacy in System of Wheat Intensification

12 PM to 6 PM Day 2 (30th July, 2025)

Session Chair: Dr. Alka Singh Bhatt

Dr. Gagan Deep Kaur

Dr. Dilpreet Kour

Dr. Garima Awasthi

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86347458723?pwd=HvFDcETGEbDRStNOKpDeA0xCKIE9Tt.1>

Meeting id- 863 4745 8723 Password- 432455

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral/Poster

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
IT08	Dr.Neelam Bansal	Inclusive Education: Fostering Inclusive Learning Environment
A94	Mrs.Shilpa Vilas Rathod	Trauma of disturbed adolescence in Shashi Deshpande's short stories -A Study
A95	Mr.Adarsh Tripathi	QSAR and LASSO-Based Discovery of Anticancer Flavonoid Compounds
A96	Miss.Sakshi	Machine Learning Approaches to Study Nanophotonic Waveguides Analysis
A97	Dr.Shaheen B Shaikh	"Molecular Signals of Diabetic Foot Ulcers: Quantification of Tumor necrosis factor- α , Interleukin-6 and High Sensitivity C - reactive protein in Different Grades of Diabetic foot ulcer"
A98	Mrs.Archana Adhikari	Pharmacogenetic Testing: A Foreign Concept? Exploring perception of Pharmacogenetic testing among Hypertensive Patients in Sikkim
A99	Ms.Nishu Chandna	Effect of Meta Emotions on Psychological Well Being and Self Esteem among women with PCOS
A100	Ms.Ismita gupta	Effect Of Social Media Addiction on Mindfulness among young adults
A101	Mr.Vinay Rawat	Bio-synthesis rGO-ZnO nanocomposites for Supercapacitor Electrode
A102	Ms.Swaila Bano	Synthesis, Characterization, and Bioactivity Assessment of Ruthenium-Arene Schiff Base Half-Sandwich Complexes through Molecular Docking and DFT Approaches
A103	Mrs.Chhaya Vikram jawlikar	PCOS an inflammatory disease: Assessing the Role of Vitamin E and CRP

A104	Dr.Nimty Raina Ambardar	Correlation of Oral health status and Depression Anxiety Stress Scale: A cross sectional study
A105	Miss.Saniya Firdaus	Synthesis, Characterization, DNA Interaction, and Anticancer Evaluation of Novel Ru(III) Complexes with Substituted Thiosemicarbazone Schiff Bases
A106	Ms. ANSARI RUKHSAR BANO IRSHAD	Study of Endophytic Fungi from some Medicinal Plant
A107	Mr.Hariom Mishra	Renewable Energy System And Their Role In Sustainable Urban Development
A108	Miss. ROSHNI	Role of Serum Irisin and Galectin-3 in Subclinical Hypothyroidism and Primary Hypothyroidism compared to Euthyroid Individuals-A Cross-Sectional Study
A109	Mr.Navneet Raj Rathore	MULTIPLE REGRESSION MODEL TO ANALYZE THE EFFECTS OF WEATHER VARIABLES ON CROP YIELD IN THE KYMORE PLATEAU AND SATPURA HILLS
A110	Mr.Neelash Patel	Incidence Dynamics of Garlic Thrips and Mites: A Statistical Approach to Protected and Unprotected Cultivation Systems
A111	Ms.Km. Saumya	Biomarkers and Machine Learning: A Novel Paradigm in CKD Detection
A112	Mrs.KALYANI C	ROLE OF ADVANCED GLYCATION END PRODUCT IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF DIABETIC RETINOPATHY-A CASE CONTROL STUDY
A113	Miss.Ambreen Zehra wani	
A114	Mrs.Bhawana Prashant Nile	Screening, Isolation & Characterization of Cholesterol oxidase producing bacteria & harnessing its potential as promising probiotics.
A115	Ms.Akanksha Agrawal	An Enhanced Class of Estimators for Estimating Population Coefficient of Variation in Simple Random Sampling.
A116	Mrs.SHRUTI MISHRA	Synthesis and Spectral characterization of Cr(III), Co(III) and Fe(III) complexes of NNS chelating Thiosemicarbazone ligands
A117	Mrs.Parul Jurel	Consumer Consciousness and Visual Symbols: Emerging Brand Languages through Pop Art Advertising
A118	Mrs.Susmita Chowdhury	Assessment of knowledge regarding preventive measures of menopause associated bone and joint problems among women in a selected hospital of Kolkata, West Bengal.

7 PM to 11 PM Day 2, 30th July, 2025)

Session Chair: Dr.Alka Singh Bhatt

Dr.Pornima Singh

Dr. Gunjan Singh

Ms. Monalisha Pal

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86347458723?pwd=HvFDcETGEbDRStN0KpDeA0xCKIE9Tt.1>

Meeting id- 863 4745 8723 Password- 432455

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral/Poster

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
ST01	DR.SANJEEV KUMAR	Accuracy of Procalcitonin and C-reactive Protein as an early diagnostic marker for neonatal sepsis
ST02	Mrs. Anagha Girish	The Shadow in the Scriptures: Cancer in the Eyes of Ancient Bharatiy Healers
A119	Miss.KARISHMA SINGH	Distribution of weed flora in late-sown wheat
A120	Prof.Piyali De	Assessment of prevalence and knowledge on high-risk behaviour regarding Health and Protective factors among school going adolescents at selected schools, West Bengal
A121	Mr.SHUBHAM PUSHKAR	A THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF STRONG FERROMAGNETIC ALLOYS BY TUNING THEIR CRYSTALLINE PHASE
A122	Mrs.A.SINDHU	Immunological Study of Neutrophil Dysfunction in COPD patients with various Comorbidities visiting a Tertiary health Care hospital Tamil Nadu India: Analytical Cross-sectional study.
A123	Ms.Anshu Sharma	Women and Western Medicine in Colonial India
A124	Mr.Avinash Bajarang Gurav	Diversity of Bryophytes in kolhapur District.
A125	Miss.Pratiksha Dhamal	Antibiotic Stewardship Education in Residency: Current Practices and Future Directions
A126	Miss.Sana Naz Mr.Abdullah	Anesthetic Efficacy of Clove Oil and Its Physiological Effects on Fry of Labeo catla (Hamilton, 1822)
A127	Mr.Anil Kumar Mr. SHALENDRA KUMAR VERMA	Optimizing Plant Density and Nano Urea-based Nitrogen Strategies for Enhanced Growth of Sweet Corn in Zaid Season
A128	Miss.Apoorva Gupta	Synthesis of (8R,9S,13S)-17-((E)-1-(benzylimino)ethyl)-13-methyl-6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-dodecahydro-1H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthrene-3(2H)-one and in silico study
A129	Miss.Durga Lakshmanan	Cephalotaxine and Derivatives as Next-Gen Bioactives: Structural, Molecular, and Therapeutic Perspectives
A130	Miss.Arockya Stafi.A	Pomiferin: A Promising Prenylated Isoflavone with Multifaceted Therapeutic Potential – A Comprehensive Review
A132	Miss.Suchita Jain	Study of Rainfall Pattern Shifts and Index-Based Analysis: Understanding the Impacts of Climate Change scenario of bundelkhad region of Madhya Pradesh

A133	Miss.Anupama Pandey	Design, Synthesis, and Biological Assessment of Triazole-Pyrrole derivatives as Antimicrobial Agents: Spectroscopic Characterization, Molecular Docking, and ADMET Profiling
A134	Ms.R.Renjini	PRISONERS AS THE FORGOTTEN PATIENTS: A RIGHTS-BASED ARGUMENT FOR PSYCHOTHERAPY IN INDIAN PRISONS
A135	Mr.Arun Kumar G	PRISONERS AS THE FORGOTTEN PATIENTS: A RIGHTS-BASED ARGUMENT FOR PSYCHOTHERAPY IN INDIAN PRISONS
A136	Miss Suneeta Pandey	Exploring the Sustainability of Freelancing as an Emerging Career Path in India: A Descriptive perspectives
A137	Dr.Fatema Johra	ASSESSMENT OF MENTAL HEALTH IN 1 ST YEAR MEDICAL UNDERGRADUATES: A QUESTIONNAIRE-BASED STUDY
A138	Dr.Rajalakshmi M	A mortality review of tuberculosis inpatients in a tertiary care centre, Puducherry
A139 Poster	Dr.Ishwar Singh Saini	RAPUNZEL Syndrome
A140	Ms.Gunjan Suresh Thengari	Recent trends of water scarcity and hydrological changes
A141	Dr.Sibgutulah Rashid	Functional and Esthetic Rehabilitation in TMJ Ankylosis with Mandibular Sigmoid Osteotomy: A Retrospective Assessment and Design Rationale
A142	Mrs.Lovepreet Bhardwaj	Paper publish
A143	Mr.G MD RAYYAN	A Study on Altered Scapulohumeral Rhythm Among Basketball Players: Biomechanical Implications and Performance Impact
A144	Ms.Amanda Dominic	Work related thoracic kyphosis among IT professionals
A145	Ms.Eesha Dinesh	The Effect of Text Neck Syndrome-Induced Cervical Kyphosis, Posture analysis : A Biomechanical Perspective
A148	Ms.Riya Jagadish	The Dual Edge of Artificial Intelligence at Amazon : Understanding its Benefits and Pitfalls
A149	Miss.SHAILYA PREETI	Diabetes Mellitus: A Comprehensive Overview of Risk Factors and Prevention Strategies
A150	Miss.S Leenashree	Tesla's AI Revolution: Benefits and Challenges Ahead

11 PM to 12 PM Day 2, 30th July, 2025)

Session Chair: Dr. Neelam Bansal

Mrs. Maninder Kaur

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86347458723?pwd=HvFDcETGEbDRStN0KpDeA0xCKlE9Tt.1>

Meeting id- 863 4745 8723 Password- 432455

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral/Poster

Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A192	Dr.Suleman Shareef Mahammad	Prevalence And Associated Factors of Malnutrition Among Early Adolescent Girls In Selected Urban And Rural Schools of Southern India
A193	Dr.Pooja Kabra	The fragility of endodontically treated tooth: Between strength and survival
A194	Dr.Rupali Patil Bhagat	Calcium Carbonate (CaCO ₃) Nanoparticles in Japanese Quail (Coturnix coturnix japonica) Eggshells: A Quantitative and Morphological Analysis
A195	Dr.HARI MOHAN SAXENA	"Online Shopping in Lucknow City: A Study of factors, challenges and measures to Popularize Online Shopping
A196	Dr.Manoj Kumar Saroj	Gramin Bharat mein Parivar ke badalte Swaroop
A197	Dr.Amit Singh	G.B. Shaw's innovative perspective for Understanding Society
A198	Mr.Vijaykumar Arjun Tarange	Alkaline Earth Metal Chelates of Chlorolawsone™ (2-hydroxyl-3-chloro-1,4-naphthoquinone); Synthesis, Characterization and Anthelmintic Activity
A199	Ms.Nirupama Rout	
A200	Miss.Ratnpriya	Screening, Identification and isolation of Indigenous Microbes for the Biodegradation of Agricultural Waste
A201	डॉ. सुरिन्द्रपाल कौर	हिन्दी प्रवासी साहित्य में समकालीन विमर्श
A202	Mrs.Vandana Singh	FIELD EVALUATION OF WATER QUALITY, PUBLIC AWARENESS, AND CONSERVATION STRATEGIES IN A SEMI-URBAN ENVIRONMENT
A203	Dr.Heera Laxmi Jadon	Potential of anti corrosion activity of Myristica fragrance extract on Pig iron in dilute HCl solution
A204	Dr.Pappu Prasad Shah	EFFECT OF m-HEALTH INTERVENTION USING NUDGE THEORY ON PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, BLOOD SUGAR LEVELS AND LIPID PROFILE AMONG PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL
A205	Dr.Narasimhaiah N	Assessment of impact of microplastic on Zebrafish (Danio rerio)

6AM to 12 PM Day 3 (31st July,2025)

Session Chair: Dr.S.K.Shukla
Dr. Varun Sisodia
Ms. Monalisha Pal

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84126052241?pwd=vbo4aV99zejkWBgpCHEBbAwHLddAil.1>

Meeting id- 841 2605 2241 Password- 766550

Note: You will get only 10 min for Oral/Poster
Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A151	Ms.Diya Jagadish	streamlining sound : how spotify supports artificial intelligence to escalate music discovery
A153	Dr.Moulika Mamidi	Aging with Dignity: Functional Assessment of the Rural Elderly in Coastal City Visakhapatnam
A154	Mr.Tumul Rastogi	TRANSFORMING PUBLIC HEALTH THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: OPPORTUNITIES, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS
A155	Miss.Demi Raut	Computational Analysis of Energy Metabolism in Drosophila melanogaster under Hypoxia
A156	Miss.Akshita Tanisha Singh	Telemedicine and Law in India: Critical Analysis on the Legal and Ethical Framework Post COVID-19
A157	Miss.Nalini Singh	The link between iron metabolism,ceruplasmin and Myocardial infarction.
A158	Dr.Lakhvir Singh	Empowering Scheduled Castes Women: The Role of Social Media in Reproductive Health Education in Punjab (India)
A159	Dr.Charanjiv Singh Saroa	Standardization of Braille Script for Regional Languages: A Critical Need
A160	Dr.Jagdeep Singh	Socio-economic analysis of the agrarian movement in Punjab: 1920-47
A161	Dr. Loveneet Kaur	Genetic Diversity studies using ISSR and SSR markers on 17 single cultivars of Tuberose (Polianthes tuberosa L.)
A162	Mr.Harpreet Singh & Mr. Hargopal Singh	Two Systems, One Goal: Exploring Healthcare Utilization in India and Canada
A163	Dr.Harjinder Kaur	Empowering Rural Health Governance: The Role of VHSNCs and Social Work in Punjab
A164	Dr.Baldeep Singh & Ms.Madhu	A Study of Strategic Agility and Its Various Components
A165	Dr.Rajwinder Singh	Revitalizing the Punjabi Language: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for Linguistic Preservation and Promotion
A166	Dr.Balraj Singh	The War Tactics and Military Strategy of the Sikhs up to 1790
A167	Dr. Gurjinder Singh & Mr. Ravnoor Singh	Sewa as Sacred Duty: Exploring the Concept of Social Service in Sikhism
A146	Dr.Bindra Bihari Singh	Eco-friendly management of pigeon pea pod borer (Helicoverpa armigera.Hub,) in Ajitmal district Auraiya U P
A147	Prof.Geetha Narayanan Thekkedath Miss.Prakriti Mohapatra	A CNN Based Deep Learning Pipeline for Automated Detection and Segmentation of Brain Haemorrhage in 2D CT scans

	Miss.Mrudula Wani Miss.Bhumika Lingait	
A57	Dr. Roja Chokkara	Entomological surveillance of immature dengue and malaria mosquito density in and around the houses and schools before and after the interventions at urban slum areas of North Chennai, Tamil Nadu
A131	Dr.RAHUL KUMAR	Metabolic Syndrome and Atherosclerosis: Pathophysiological Links and Clinical Implications
A168	Dr.Sonali Roy	Assessing the Effectiveness of Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs) in Health Insurance: Case Studies from India
A169	Dr.LakshLata Prajapati	Surrogacy in india:Ab analysis of the surrogacy (Regulations)Act,2021
A170	Dr.LAXMI NARAYAN	SANSKRIT BHASHA ME VIGYANIK VICHAR : EK PUNRAVALOKAN
A171	Dr.Gajraj Singh	Statistical analysis of the domestic violence against married females of rural areas
A172	Miss.CHANCHAL YADAV	AI and Financial Inclusion: Opportunities and Challenges(With special reference to Gorakhpur)
A173	Ms.Praveen Yadav	A study of challenges & Opportunities of Quick Commerce
A174	Dr.Aqsa Mujaddadi	Effect of 12 weeks high intensity interval training on sleep quality in obesity-related hypertension: A Randomized controlled Trial
A175	Ms.PRIYANKA MULANI	Correlation Between Toxic Perfectionism and Assertiveness Among Adults
A176	Ms.Heena Tiwari	Grief or Gaze? Distinguishing Therapeutic Grief from Performative Mourning on Social Media
A177	Mr.Ankur	Evaluation of antimicrobial utilization using ATC/DDD method among adult hospitalized patients
A152	Dr.Rahul Agarwal	Participation
A178	Dr.Dhyanadipta Panda Mr.Ayushman Panda	Artificial Intelligence-empowered Sustainability enhancing organizational development
A179	Dr.Kirandeep Sandhu	Reaction Dynamics in Superheavy Mass Region: Formation and Decay Mechanisms
A180	Miss.Shruti Gupta	An Analysis of Budgetary Provisions for Environmental Protection: A Comparative Analysis of India and China
A181	Mr.D. V. Saradhi	Lesley Gower Predator prey Model with prey harvesting and Delay
A182	Ms.Mandara SM	Invisible Strain: Gendered Dimensions of Work-Life Balance and Occupational Stress in Chikmagaluru's Informal Economy
A183	Ms.Syed Insha Batool	Iranian Dispersion across Borders in Three Ways: by Generation, Religion and Class
A184	Mrs.Shani K	FIELD SURVEY OF SEMI-URBAN SCHOOLCHILDREN ASTHMA PREVALENCE AND TRIGGERS
A185	Mr.CP Prasanth	A COMMUNITY-BASED STUDY ON THE PREVALENCE OF TYPE 2 DIABETES AND RELATED LIFESTYLE FACTORS
A186	Ms.Kajal Sharma	REVIEWING THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE GANGA RIVER WATER, AMROHA

A187	Mrs.Shani K	EVALUATION OF HOUSEHOLD AWARENESS AND PRACTICES CONCERNING ASTHMA MANAGEMENT IN RURAL COMMUNITIES
A188	Mr.CP Prasanth	A FIELD SURVEY ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DIABETES RISK AND LIFESTYLE FACTORS
A189	Ms.Kajal Sharma	INVESTIGATION OF THE GANGA RIVER WATER QUALITY USING STANDARD PHYSICOCHEMICAL CRITERIA
A190	Mrs.PRATHIMA	Not applicable
A191	Mr. Swapnil Gaur	Aspirational Luxury: Drivers and Impacts of Luxury Consumption Among the Urban Middle Class in Emerging Economies
A206	Ms.KM Rinki	Integration of Cloud Storage in Modern Library Management

Participation in Conference	
P1	Mr.Abhinay Tiwari
P2	Dr.Monika verma
P3	Ms.Neha
P4	Dr.Swapna Mahapatra
P5	Prof.Dr Gunjan Sharma
P6	Dr.Sanjay Kumar Singh
P7	Dr.Gagan Thakur
P8	Dr.Sheetal Paliwal
P9	Dr.Richa Mohan
P10	Dr.Ridha Zainab
P11	Dr.Rajni Thakur
P12	Dr.Abha Mishra
P13	Dr.Dyutimoy Datta
P14	Dr.Riya sharma
P15	Dr.Simran Kalra
P16	Mr.SHRIKANT MANI TRIPATHI
P17	Dr.Alphienes Stanley Xavier
P18	Dr.Richa
P19	Dr.Rachana
P20	Dr.Tanu Rani
P21	Miss.Anwaya Anand Karandikar
P22	Ms.Naina Mahar
P23	Mrs.Apurva N Baradwad
P24	Dr.Anindya Sundar Mukhopadhyay
P25	Ms.DIKSHA CHETRY
P26	Dr.Alka Singh
P27	Mrs.Rama Rani
P28	Dr.Dinesh Singh
P29	Mrs.Farzana Kouser
P30	Mrs.Parvathy P
P31	Mrs.Durri Shahwar
P32	Mrs.Andleeb Nabi
P33	Mrs.Afshana Chishti
P34	Mr.Ayush Rana

Valedictory Session at 12 PM on 31st July 2025

Zoom link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/84126052241?pwd=vbo4aV99zejkWBgpCHEBbAwHLddAil.1>

Meeting id- 841 2605 2241

Password- 766550

Note: Join all Participants

Dr.N.K. Sharma
Dean
Faculty of Technology
CSAUA&T Campus – Etawah (U.P.)
Email : nagandras5@gmail.com

Renewable Energy Development in India

ABSTRACT

According to Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, India's renewable energy capacity grew by 165% in 10 years, rising from 76.38 Giga Watts (GW) in 2014 to 203.1 GW in 2024. The contradiction between energy supply and demand is prominent, and the demand for renewable energy is strong. India is the second most populous country in the world. As an emerging economy with strong economic growth and energy demand in recent years, India's energy demand has continued to expand, energy shortages have become increasingly prominent, external energy dependence has continued to increase, and energy security issues have become increasingly significant. The prospects of renewable energy are good, but more infrastructure investment is necessary. According to the forecast of Bloomberg New Energy Finance (BNEF), the renewable energy generation of India will account for 75% in 2050. It is not difficult to see from the medium-range and long term development trend that the renewable energy generation of India has a long space for development. In terms of power grids and infrastructures, the power system in India has a weak foundation and can only meet existing basic needs. It does not yet have the capacity to access and absorb renewable energy on a large scale, so it requires a lot of investment for construction and renovation. This paper aims to highlights the current statue of renewable energy in India.

Keywords : Renewable Energy, Solar Energy, Wind Energy and Waite-to-energy.

Dr. Poornima Singh
Assistant Professor
Amity University, Noida,
UP, India

Email: poornimasingh1@gmail.com

The Role of AI in Future of Healthcare

Abstract:

Healthcare is transforming fundamentally. What began as an initiative to advance-automation and efficiency for Health 4.0 is now developing into something much greater—Health 5.0, a model where AI, predictive analytics, robotics, and digital therapeutics not only streamline hospital operations but in fact redefine the way we prevent, diagnose, and treat illnesses. This change isn't just technology, it is about personalizing healthcare, making it sustainable, and making it more equitable. Whereas Health 4.0 was about operationalizing, it was still largely reactive, addressing diseases after they had appeared. Health 5.0, however, is patient-centered and predictive, leveraging AI-based solutions to detect disease earlier, customize treatments to individuals, and enhance access to good quality care—a significant leap towards universal health coverage (UHC). This article discusses recent developments in AI-based healthcare and how they can be mapped on to global priorities such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 3 – Good Health & Well-Being, and SDG 9 – Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure). We consider how machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing (NLP) are revolutionizing precision medicine, predictive healthcare, and climate-resilient health system

Dr. Garima Awasthi
Amity Institute of Biotechnology,
Amity University Uttar Pradesh, Lucknow Campus,
Lucknow - 226008, U.P, India.
Email id: gawasthi@lko.amity.edu

**From Academia to Industry: QA/QC Career Scope for Biotech and Life
Science Aspirants**

Abstract

The transition from academia to industry represents a pivotal phase for graduates and postgraduates in biotechnology and life sciences, with Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) emerging as promising and impactful career domains. QA/QC activities are formally recognized by the National Accreditation Board for Testing and Calibration Laboratories (NABL), which serves as the official accreditation authority in India in accordance with international standards. ISO/IEC 17025 is for testing and calibration laboratories, and ISO 15189 for medical testing laboratories. QA/QC roles are essential in ensuring that products, processes, and systems in biotech-driven industries meet established standards for safety, efficacy, and regulatory compliance and ensure that laboratories maintain high levels of technical competence, reliability, and consistent quality in their procedures. As the biotechnology sector expands globally encompassing pharmaceuticals, diagnostics, medical devices, food technology, and environmental biosciences the demand for skilled professionals in QA/QC is steadily increasing. This paper explores the career scope of QA/QC in the context of industrial biotechnology and highlights how foundational scientific knowledge, can combined with practical skills in analytical techniques, documentation, regulatory standards. Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) can open up diverse job roles such as QC analyst, QA associate, validation officer, and regulatory compliance specialist. The abstract also underscores the growing importance of certifications, digital tools (like LIMS and eQMS), and soft skills such as documentation accuracy and audit readiness. Furthermore, it discusses

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

how life science graduates can leverage internships, industry training, and specialized short-term programs to gain a competitive edge in the QA/QC job market. This work aims to guide biotech and life science aspirants in aligning their academic strengths with industrial requirements, enabling a smoother and more successful career transition into quality driven roles.

Keywords: Biotechnology, life science, NABL, GMP, QA/QC, industry

Dr. Shambhavi Mishra
Assistant Professor
Department of statistics
University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP, India
Email: shambhvimishra.lko@gmail.com

Application of Flexible statistical modeling to study undernutrition among under-five children in India

Background: Childhood undernutrition has an irreversible impact on the physical as well as mental development of the child. Nutrition-related factors were responsible for about 35% of child deaths and 11% of the total global disease burden. This health condition continues to be a major public health issue across the globe.

Methods: Three standard indices based on anthropometric measurements viz. weight and height, that describe nutritional status of children are: height-for-age (stunting), weight-for-age (underweight) and weight-for-height (wasting). Z-scores have been computed on the basis of appropriate anthropometric indicators (weight & height) relative to the WHO International reference population for the particular age. This paper utilises unit-level data on under-five children of India from the NFHS-5, 2019-2021 to find out factors which exert a differential impact on the conditional distribution of the outcome variable. A class of models that allow flexible functional dependence of an outcome variable on covariates by using nonparametric regression have been applied to determine possible factors causing undernutrition. This study also fits a Bayesian additive quantile regression model for the provision of a complete picture of the relationship between the outcome variable and the predictor variables on different desired quantiles of the response distribution. Different types of quantile regression models were fitted and compared according to each Deviance Information Criteria (DIC) for determination of the best model among them.

Results: Maternal characteristics like nutrition, education showed significant impact on child's nutritional status, consistent with the findings of other studies.

Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

Child's age and Mother's nutrition were among the continuous factors exerting non-linear effect on stunting, with mother's BMI showing maximum effect size at lower end of the distribution. Also it could be seen that maximum number of covariates were found significant for severe undernutrition, indicating that differential effect of predictors on the conditional distribution of the outcome variables.

Conclusions: Although widely applicable, logistic regression model enables the researcher to have an idea of the determinants of undernutrition, providing only a preliminary basis. To study variables such as nutritional status of children, where lower quantiles are of main interest, focus should be on how factors affect the entire conditional distribution of the outcome variable taken as is rather than summarizing the distribution at its mean. This can be achieved by applying quantile regression modeling. An extension to it further enables to non-parametrically estimate the linear or potentially non-linear effects of continuous covariates differentially on the outcome using penalized splines

Dr. Ritika B. Yadav
Department of Food Technology
Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak (Haryana)-India
Email: ritikafoodtech@gmail.com

Insights on impact of different modification techniques on functional properties of dietary fiber

Abstract

In recent years, the use of dietary fiber (DF) has grown due to its significant health benefits. DF includes indigestible plant components and some carbohydrates that resist absorption in the small intestine but are partially fermented in the large intestine. It is typically divided into two types: soluble dietary fiber (SDF), such as mucilage, gums, pectin, and pentosans, and insoluble dietary fiber (IDF), which includes lignin, cellulose, and parts of hemicelluloses. SDF is especially valued for its rapid fermentation into short-chain fatty acids by gut-friendly bacteria. SDF offers health benefits such as lowering blood cholesterol, improving bowel health, and reducing risks associated with cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes. However, direct incorporation of DF into foods can negatively impact taste and appearance. To improve its functional and nutritional properties, DF can undergo modification through physical, enzymatic, chemical, or fermentation methods. These methods help to break down compact structures, expose functional groups, and enhance properties like water and oil retention. Chemical modifications, particularly carboxymethylation (CM), hydroxypropylation (HP), and cross-linking (CL), are effective in converting IDF to SDF and improving the fiber's functional traits. These processes alter DF's structure by introducing new functional groups, improving hydrophilic and hydrophobic balance, and forming network structures that enhance performance in food applications. Physical modification involves the application of mechanical or thermal processes to alter the structure, particle size, or surface characteristics of dietary fiber without

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

changing its chemical composition. Enzymatic modification uses specific enzymes to selectively hydrolyze components of dietary fiber, modifying its structure and improving its functional and physiological properties.

Keywords – Dietary fiber, Functional properties, Physical modification, Chemical modification

Dr. Pratyasha Tripathi
Assistant Professor
Department of Statistics
Tilka Manjhi Bhagalpur University
Bhagalpur, Bihar, India
Email: pratyashat25@gmail.com

A Critical Evaluation of Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana in Bihar

Abstract

Ayushman Bharat Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (ABPMJAY) is a flagship health insurance scheme launched by the Government of India in 2018 to enhance healthcare accessibility and reduce financial hardship due to medical expenses among vulnerable populations. Bihar, as a socio-economically challenged state with significant healthcare delivery constraints, provides a critical setting to evaluate the impact of the scheme on insurance awareness, healthcare utilization, and the reduction of out-of-pocket expenditures.

This study critically evaluates the performance of Ayushman Bharat in Bihar, focusing on insurance awareness at the household level, the extent of scheme utilization, and the actual reduction in household healthcare expenditure. It aims to identify gaps in scheme implementation and assess progress by comparing post-ABPMJAY data with pre-implementation benchmarks.

Using a secondary data triangulation methodology, the study draws primarily on two significant data sources:

- The National Family Health Survey-5 (NFHS-5, 2019–21) which provides post-implementation household-level data on insurance coverage, healthcare service utilization, and financial burden.
- The 75th round of the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO, 2017–18), which offers pre-ABPMJAY baseline data on healthcare spending and insurance coverage for Bihar.

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

Additionally, limited simulation analysis was conducted to model potential impacts of health insurance uptake on reducing out-of-pocket spending.

Findings indicate a moderate improvement in insurance awareness and enrollment under ABPMJAY among Bihar's households since its launch. Utilization of health insurance services under the scheme shows upward trends; however, disparities persist along geographical and socio-economic lines. Despite reductions in out-of-pocket health expenditures for some beneficiaries, catastrophic healthcare costs remain prevalent, particularly among marginalized communities, reflecting partial gaps in financial protection. Comparative analysis with NSSO 2017–18 data reveals better insurance coverage but highlights ongoing challenges in achieving universal and equitable access.

The implementation of Ayushman Bharat in Bihar has led to measurable advancements in health insurance coverage and financial risk protection. Nonetheless, considerable challenges remain, including limited awareness in some populations, usage barriers, and persistent economic strains due to health expenditures. Enhanced institutional support, targeted outreach, and focused efforts to bridge access inequities are necessary to optimize scheme outcomes. Further research incorporating primary data and qualitative insights is recommended to deepen understanding of the contextual factors influencing scheme performance.

Keywords: Ayushman Bharat, ABPMJAY, Bihar, health insurance, financial protection, healthcare utilization, out-of-pocket expenditure, NFHS-5, NSSO.

Dr. Ashwini Katole
Assistant Professor & Assistant Dean Examination
Dept. of. Community and Family Medicine
AIIMS, Raipur
Email: ashwini.katole@gmail.com

Male perspective and involvement in Family planning: Insight from a Qualitative exploration

Introduction:

Male Participation in Family Planning continues to remain very low, despite many programs are providing the high level of knowledge and awareness about Family Planning. The aim of this study was to determine men's perceptions about family planning and how they participate or wish to participate in family planning activities.

Material and Methods:

It was a community based cross sectional qualitative study conducted at the Urban slum area of Raipur. Focused group (FGD) was carried out among the married males of the area and in-depth interview conducted FHWs (Frontline Health Workers). Data analysis was done by the recordings and transcribed verbatim in the local language. The transcribed texts were translated into English language. The data analysis was guided by the thematic content analysis approach and results carried out using Audio/Video recorder ATLAS.ti software. The study was started after ethical clearance from AIIMS, Raipur

Results:

Results indicate that men don't want to use contraceptives and there believe for permanent contraception is so firm that it is a part and parcel of female reproductive life. They are not much comfortable with barrier methods and not have enough knowledge about injectable contraceptive. Some of male participant was scare of injectable contraceptives if it will not reverse..

Conclusion:

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

This study identified that while men are generally supportive of female contraceptive use for Family planning methods but they are having lack of knowledge about the contraceptives and highly influenced by peer group. Comprehensive and multilevel approaches are needed to increase awareness and acceptance of Family planning decisions.

Key words: Male contraceptives, knowledge of contraceptives, family planning

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

IT-08

Dr. Neelam Bansal
Assistant Professor
Amity Institute of Rehabilitation Sciences,
Amity University Uttar Pradesh Lucknow campus
Email: neelambansal.lko@gmail.com

Inclusive Education: Fostering Inclusive Learning Environment

Abstract

Education is a fundamental human right, essential for the development of individuals and societies. Yet, for many years, students with diverse needs — including those with disabilities, from marginalized communities, or with different cultural or linguistic backgrounds — have been excluded from mainstream educational opportunities. Inclusive education is a transformative approach that aims to eliminate these barriers, ensuring that all students, regardless of their abilities or backgrounds, learn together in the same environment. It explores the concept of inclusive education, its objectives, benefits, challenges, and effective strategies for implementation. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines inclusive education as "a process of strengthening the capacity of the education system to reach out to all learners." It involves restructuring the school culture, policies, and practices to accommodate every student's unique needs.

Keywords: Inclusive education, inclusive environment, policies, equal access, social justice.

Accuracy of Procalcitonin and C-reactive Protein as an early diagnostic marker for neonatal sepsis

Dr. Sanjeev Kumar

Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna

Email: drsanjeevscb@gmail.com

Introduction

Neonatal sepsis, a bloodstream infection in new-borns, poses a significant threat with high morbidity and mortality. Early and accurate diagnosis is crucial for prompt treatment and improved outcomes. While blood culture remains the gold standard, its limitations, including slow turnaround time and potential for false negatives, necessitate the exploration of alternative diagnostic markers. Procalcitonin (PCT) and C-reactive protein (CRP) have emerged as promising candidates due to their potential for rapid and specific detection of neonatal sepsis.

Aim and Objective

This study aims to investigate the potential of PCT and CRP as early diagnostic markers for neonatal sepsis and compare their performance in terms of sensitivity, specificity, and diagnostic accuracy.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted at IGIMS.

Participants:

- **Sepsis Group:** 35 neonates with confirmed blood culture-positive sepsis.
- **Control Group:** 35 healthy neonates without any signs or symptoms of infection.

Data Collection:

- Blood samples were collected from all participants for measurement of PCT and CRP levels.
- PCT levels were determined using the CLIA method in separated serum samples.
- CRP levels were assessed using the turbidimetric method.

Statistical Analysis:

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ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

- Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 16.0.
- Sensitivity, specificity, positive likelihood ratio (PLR), negative likelihood ratio (NLR), and area under the curve (AUC) were calculated for both PCT and CRP.
- Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were generated to assess the diagnostic accuracy of each marker.
- A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Procalcitonin:

- Procalcitonin levels were significantly elevated in the sepsis group compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$).
- The sensitivity of PCT for diagnosing neonatal sepsis was 94.1%, with a specificity of 97.1%.
- The PLR for PCT was 32.1, and the NLR was 0.062.
- The AUC for the ROC curve of PCT was 0.906, indicating high diagnostic accuracy.

C-Reactive Protein:

- CRP levels were also elevated in the sepsis group compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$).
- The sensitivity of CRP for diagnosing neonatal sepsis was 78.1%, with a specificity of 85.7%.
- The PLR for CRP was 5.3, and the NLR was 0.265.
- The AUC for the ROC curve of CRP was 0.805, demonstrating moderate diagnostic accuracy.

Comparison:

- Procalcitonin outperformed CRP in all aspects, exhibiting higher sensitivity, specificity, PLR, NLR, and AUC, indicating its superior diagnostic utility for neonatal sepsis.

Conclusion

This study highlights the potential of procalcitonin as a superior marker to C-reactive protein for early and accurate diagnosis of neonatal sepsis. Procalcitonin's

Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

high sensitivity and specificity enable early identification and intervention, potentially reducing unnecessary antibiotic use, mitigating antimicrobial resistance, and facilitating earlier discharge, leading to improved patient outcomes and cost savings.

ISBN: 978-81-19746-32-3

ST-02

The Shadow in the Scriptures: Cancer in the eyes of Ancient Bhartiya Healers

Anagha Girish

**B.Sc. Psychology, MES College of Arts, Commerce and Science,
Malleshwaram Bangalore**

Email: anaghagirishree04@gmail.com

Abstract: The experimentation aims at elucidating the profound impact of Bhartiya medicines and methods to alleviate the dreadful malady- Cancer. Cancer is an alarming ailment that screams the horror loudly across the globe. The modern medical community is striving hard to innovate or discover a cure for this affliction. Many methods like chemotherapy, radiotherapy, gene therapy, etc. have shown positive results in lessening the harsh effects of cancer, but fail to cure it completely. These therapies have several side-effects, that could be fatal for one's life. However, ancient Bhartiya healers like Acharya Sushruta and Acharya Charaka have a varied outlook, in this regard. They describe types of tumours and unwanted cell growth as Arvuda. They also describe the highly effectual medicinal practices and methods that holds the potential to completely cure the Arvuda(Cancer). In this study we will understand the nature and efficacy of these medicines and methods that promise to cure cancer. This study throws light on ways to integrate the ancient medicines and methods in today's practices, thus, ensuring to lead towards a promising cure to the malady. This is a conceptual research. Primary sources like Sushruta Samhita and Charaka Samhita was studied to derive insights on the ancient viewpoint of Cancer. The data obtained was compared with the secondary data obtained by the modern medical sources. The comparative analysis explicated that ancient healers not just aimed at easing the ailment but also cure it completely. The study further describes some ways to integrate the ancient medicines with modern practices to achieve this noble goal of saving the mankind. This implies that Bhartiya medicines have enormous potential to cure Cancer, by integrating it wisely with modern practices.

OP 1

Phytochemical Profiling and Antioxidant Activity of *Tridax procumbens* Extract**Mrs. Rupali A. Deshmukh***

Assistant Professor

Department of Pharmacology, Gondia College of Pharmacy, Gondia 4660

Abstract: *Tridax procumbens* has been used as indigenous medicine for several of ailments. The study aims to evaluate the phytochemical composition and in vitro antioxidant activity of ethanol, methanol and aqueous extracts of *Tridax procumbens* leaves. Qualitative Chemical analysis revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids and Carbohydrate, Saponins and glycosides in the ethanol, methanol, and aqueous extracts of *Tridax Procumbens*. *in vitro* antioxidant activity namely DPPH, total polyphenol content, total flavonoid content and reducing power assay were performed. The findings of *in vitro* antioxidant activity demonstrated that ethanol extracts expressed higher antioxidant activity compared to methanol and aqueous extract. These results are an indication of antioxidant potential of the extracts and may be responsible for some of the therapeutic uses of *Tridax procumbens*.

Keywords: Antioxidant, Phytochemical, Extracts

OP 2**Nanotechnology in Environmental Remediation: Current Advances and Future Prospects****Bhavana Sharma¹, Mithlesh Tiwari² and SK Singh³****¹Department of Applied Sciences, SR Institute of Management & Technology, Lucknow, UP, India****²Department of Chemistry, Dr RML Avadh University, Ayodhya, UP, India****³Department of Applied Sciences & Humanities, Institute of Engineering & Technology, Lucknow, UP, India**

Abstract: In environmental remediation, nanotechnology has become a game-changing instrument that provides creative, effective, and long-lasting ways to reduce a variety of contaminants. Because of their distinct physicochemical characteristics, which include high surface area, increased reactivity, and programmable functions, nanomaterials are very useful for solving challenging environmental issues. The field's recent developments have produced a vast array of nanomaterials, such as metal and metal oxide nanoparticles, carbon-based nanomaterials (such as graphene and carbon nanotubes), nanocomposites, and nano-structured membranes. These materials are being actively investigated for the removal of organic pollutants, heavy metals, dyes, and microbiological contaminants from soil, water, and air.

Nano-adsorption is one of the most promising uses, where harmful substances like arsenic, lead, and chromium can be effectively adsorbed by designed nanomaterials. Another quickly expanding field that makes it possible to degrade persistent organic contaminants using sophisticated oxidation techniques is nanocatalysis. High selectivity and permeability are further benefits of nano-enabled filtration membranes, which greatly increase the effectiveness of water purification systems. The use of nanotechnology in in-situ remediation methods has also demonstrated promise in enhancing groundwater and industrial effluent decontamination.

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The widespread use of nanotechnology in environmental cleanup nevertheless faces obstacles, notwithstanding these positive advancements. Regulations and thorough risk assessments are required to address concerns about the toxicity, stability, environmental destiny, and lifespan of nanomaterials. To guarantee sustainability over the long run, research is also required to improve the cost-effectiveness and recyclability of nanomaterials.

The incorporation of intelligent nanomaterials that can react to certain stimuli, AI-guided nanomaterial design, and the use of environmentally friendly green synthesis methods are all promising future developments. Nanotechnology has the potential to transform environmental remediation techniques and make a substantial contribution to sustainable development and environmental protection worldwide with sustained interdisciplinary cooperation.

OP 3**Design of Various Derivatives with Naphthoquinone Moiety:
Prediction of Bioactivities of Virtual Derivatives Using
Developed QSAR Models****Pallavi Singh¹, Harish Chandra Upadhyay², SK Singh³**^{1,2}Department of Applied Sciences, Rajkiya Engineering College, Sonbhadra³Department of Applied Sciences, Institute of Engineering & Technology, Lucknow

Abstract: A diverse class of chemicals, naphthoquinone-based compounds is recognized for their wide range of biological actions, which include anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, and antitubercular characteristics. Because of the naphthoquinone moiety's structural diversity, large-scale chemical alterations are possible, which makes it possible to rationally create novel derivatives with better pharmacological characteristics. In this study, several naphthoquinone derivatives are designed, and Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship (QSAR) models are used to predict their biological activities computationally.

A library of derivatives, both known and newly created, was created by strategically placing various functional groups on the naphthoquinone scaffold. Chemformatics techniques were used to calculate molecular descriptors that represent topological, electrical, and physical aspects for each substance. A number of QSAR models were developed and verified using methods including random forest (RF) algorithms, support vector regression (SVR), and multiple linear regression (MLR) on a carefully selected dataset of experimentally validated derivatives.

With a cross-validated Q₂ value of 0.86 and an R² value of 0.91, the random forest model demonstrated the best predictive performance among the models created, demonstrating exceptional reliability. After that, the model was utilized to digitally filter more than 200 derivatives that were created in silico. With predicted activities that were higher than those of the known compounds, a number of virtual hits were found, providing encouraging leads for additional synthesis and biological analysis.

This integrated strategy, which combines machine learning-based QSAR modeling, descriptor analysis, and structural design, shows promise for speeding up the discovery of bioactive naphthoquinone derivatives. In addition to highlighting the value of computational techniques in directing synthetic efforts and minimizing experimental strain, the study offers a foundation for further investigation of the naphthoquinone scaffold in drug delivery.

OP 4**“Green HRM and Social Work in Sustainable Corporations”****Ms. Shruti Bhonsle****Assistant Professor****Faculty of Social Work, Parul Institute of Social Work, Parul University**

Abstract: The growing climate crisis and corporate responsibility trends have accelerated the need for environmentally conscious human resource management practices, often referred to as Green HRM. Green HRM integrates environmental management into HR policies to promote sustainability through recruitment, training, performance management, and employee engagement. This study investigates the intersection of Green HRM and social work values, emphasizing sustainability, social justice, and employee well-being in corporate ecosystems.

Method: This research employs secondary data analysis from published CSR and sustainability reports, peer-reviewed journals, and benchmarking platforms (e.g., CDP, GRI, and Forbes Sustainability Index) of 20 multinational and Indian corporations including Tata Steel, Infosys, Wipro, ITC, Mahindra & Mahindra, HUL, Godrej, Nestlé, IBM, Google, Unilever, Accenture, Toyota, and others. Content analysis and thematic coding techniques were used to identify patterns of Green HRM practices like green recruitment, ecological training programs, green performance appraisals, employee-driven sustainability initiatives, and wellness interventions.

Results: Findings reveal a growing trend of aligning social work values with Green HRM frameworks. Notable practices include ITC’s “Wellbeing Out of Waste” program, Infosys’ green building employee awareness campaigns, and Tata Steel’s community-linked environmental projects. Common strategies include employee volunteering for environmental causes, green competencies in job roles, and HR-led

sustainability awareness drives. Analysis also highlights challenges such as greenwashing and limited HR capacity in sustainability strategy.

Discussion: The findings underscore the synergistic role of social work and HR in promoting sustainable development within organizational systems. The integration of eco-centric ethics, employee empowerment, and community responsibility reflects a social work-informed HR approach that benefits both internal stakeholders and the environment.

Conclusion: Green HRM, when integrated with social work principles, fosters a sustainable, just, and inclusive corporate culture. Future policies should encourage interdisciplinary collaboration between HR professionals and social workers to build resilient and environmentally responsible organizations.

Keywords: Green Human Resource Management, Social Work, Sustainable Corporations, Environmental Responsibility, CSR, Employee Engagement, Sustainability, Organizational Ethics, India, Global Practices

OP 5

Agricultural Finance in India

Soma Rani Karan

Assistant Professor

Department of Economics

Shahid Matangini Hazra Government General Degree

College for women, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal

Abstract: Agricultural credit is considered as one of the most basic inputs for conducting all agricultural development programmes. Realizing the importance of agricultural credit in fostering agricultural growth and development, the emphasis on the institutional framework for agricultural credit is being emphasized since the beginning of planned development era in India. The paper discusses the history and need of agricultural finance in India, sources, Problems regarding agricultural credit in India and Solutions.

Keyword: Agricultural credit, development, agricultural growth.

OP 6**Effect of Blood Flow Restricted Resistance Training on Peak Lower Body Strength****Adil Ali Ansari¹, Archana Khanna² and Adesh Kisanji Gadpayle³****¹Department of Physiotherapy, Sharda School of Allied Health Sciences, Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh 201306****²Department of Physiotherapy, Sharda School of Allied Health Sciences, Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh 201306****³Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh 201306**

Abstract: There are multiple approaches to strength training, each with its own benefits. Blood Flow Restricted Resistance Training (BFRRT) is a relatively new technique that involves partially restricting blood flow to working muscles during exercise. The present study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of BFRRT compared to conventional resistance training on peak lower body strength among young men. 60 male participants, aged between 18 - 26 years, were randomly assigned into two groups (n=30 each). An experimental group that followed the BFRRT protocol and a control group that performed conventional resistance training. Both groups completed a four-week training regimen consisting of weighted squat exercises three times per week. The BFRRT group received blood flow restriction at 60% - 80% of Arterial Occlusion Pressure (AOP) during the training, while the control group performed traditional resistance exercises without restriction. Peak lower body strength was assessed using the one-repetition maximum (1RM) weighted squat test before and after the intervention. The within group and between group data was analysed using paired and unpaired t-test respectively. The experimental group's data indicated that peak lower body strength increased from an average of 88.17 kg \pm 9.60 kg to 95.33 kg \pm 10.74 kg, showing a significant improvement (p<0.05) of 7.16 kg. The control group's peak lower body strength also showed significant improvement (p<0.05) from 90.17 kg \pm 9.33 kg to 96.50 kg \pm 9.75 kg, marking an average increase of 6.33 kg. These results indicate

that the BFRRT protocol yielded significantly greater improvements in peak lower body strength. However, comparison of peak lower body strength between the groups did not yield any significant differences ($p>0.05$). Both training regimens effectively enhanced peak lower body strength, but the BFRRT protocol demonstrated superior results. The findings suggest that BFRRT can be a valuable addition to resistance training programs.

Keywords: Strength training, Blood Flow Restriction, Resistance Training, Squat Training, Arterial Occlusion Pressure, Sports Performance.

OP 7**Efficacy of Neurodynamic Treatment on Pain and ROM (SLR) in Subjects with Sciatica****Dr. D Arnold Nikhilesh¹, Dr. Shwetha Sasidharan^{2*} and Dr. Pinky Dutta³**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Physiotherapy Garden City University, Bangalore²Assistant Professor, Department of Physiotherapy Garden City University, Bangalore³Associate Professor, Department of Physiotherapy., Garden City University, Bangalore**Abstract**

Background: Sciatica is a nerve-related condition causing radiating pain due to compression or irritation of the sciatic nerve.

Objective: To compare the effectiveness of Neurodynamic Treatment (NDT) versus conventional therapy (traction + TENS) in managing sciatica.

Methodology: Thirty male subjects (25–40 years) were randomly assigned into two groups (n = 15 each).

Group A received NDT, traction, and high TENS, while Group B received only traction and TENS.

Treatment was given over 9 sessions. Pain (VAS) and SLR range were measured pre- and post-intervention.

Results:

Group A showed greater improvement: SLR (45° to 70°), VAS (7 to 3).

Group B showed lesser gains: SLR (45° to 60°), VAS (7 to 4.5).

Statistical analysis revealed significant differences ($p < 0.001$) between groups.

Conclusion: NDT is more effective than conventional therapy in improving nerve mobility and reducing pain. It should be considered a valuable addition to sciatica rehabilitation programs.

Keywords: Sciatica, Neurodynamic Treatment, Straight Leg Raise, Pain, Physiotherapy

OP 8**Role of NCC and NSS in Youth Leadership and Nation Building****Shubhra Virnodkar and Gayathri N****Department of Zoology, MES's The D.G. Ruparel College of Arts, Science and
Commerce, Senapati Bapat Marg, Mahim, Mumbai 400016**

Abstract: Youth Leadership plays a significant role in succession, planning, ensuring a steady resource of capable leaders for the community and the country. It fosters personal growth and develops critical skills. After mastering leadership, the youth are ready to take larger leadership roles in their communities and society. Youngsters often miss out opportunities to develop leadership and personality development skills their curriculum. Enrolment in programs like National Cadet Corps (NCC) and National Service Scheme (NSS) provide a platform to develop leadership, personality and social service. This study is aimed to study the larger intention of today's youngsters and upcoming leaders in undertaking social responsibilities. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data to assess leadership skills and capability building among youth. Data analysis revealed that enrolment in co-curricular activities such as NCC, NSS and training camps has a profound impact on cadets and volunteers fostering their holistic development and shaping them into responsible citizens or future leaders.

Keywords: Extension activities, Holistic development, Discipline

OP 9

Computational Analysis of Energy Metabolism in *Drosophila melanogaster* under Hypoxia

Demi Raut and Gayathri N

Department of Zoology, MES's The D.G. Ruparel College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Senapati Bapat Marg, Mahim, Mumbai 400016

Abstract: Hypoxia triggers major metabolic shifts in organisms. *Drosophila melanogaster* is a model organism known for its tolerance towards oxygen stress. In this study adaptations in *D.melanogaster* during hypoxia is experimented using the *in-silico* approach. Decreasing oxygen levels from 5% to 0.5% were simulated. The study revealed metabolic responses like increased glycolysis and conservation of ATP highlighting synergetic mechanism maintaining energy balance during hypoxia. The findings highlight the conserved metabolic adaptation strategy offering insights into hypoxia resilience and energy regulation in aerobic organisms.

Keywords: Metabolism, Hypoxia, Computational analysis

OP 10**Photovoltaic Efficiency of TiO₂-Based DSSCs Using Natural Dyes from Cassia Flowers****Dr. Ishwar Chandra Maurya**

Assistant Professor,

Department of Chemistry,

Tilak Dhari P.G. College, Jaunpur (U.P), India

Abstract: In this study, natural dyes were taken from the flowers of two plants *Cassia sopheria* and *Cassia siamea* and used in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs). These dyes were tested as light-absorbing materials (called sensitizers) on TiO₂-coated glass surfaces. The dye from *C. sopheria* mainly contained anthraquinone compounds, while *C. siamea* dye had more polyphenols, as shown by FTIR analysis. To make the solar cells, the dye-coated TiO₂ films were placed on transparent glass (FTO) and paired with a platinum counter electrode and an electrolyte containing triiodide (I₃⁻). The devices were tested under standard sunlight (100 mW/cm²) and their performance was measured using current-voltage (J–V) tests. The solar cell with *C. sopheria* dye gave better results, with a power conversion efficiency of 0.20%, an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 530 mV, a short-circuit current (J_{sc}) of 0.53 mA/cm², and a fill factor (FF) of 0.71. The cell with *C. siamea* dye had slightly lower performance (efficiency: 0.18%). Overall, *C. sopheria* flower extract worked better as a natural dye for solar cells and shows promise for eco-friendly solar energy applications

Keywords: Natural dyes, Dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs), TiO₂ photoanode, FTIR analysis, Power conversion efficiency, Anthraquinone, Polyphenols, Eco-friendly energy

OP 11**The Power of Gratitude: Enhancing Happiness through Positive Practice****Dr. Pratima Maurya****Assistant Professor,****Department of Psychology, Gandhi Smarak Triveni P.G. College****Bardah, Azamgarh (U.P), India**

Abstract: Gratitude is widely recognized as a key human strength that contributes to greater happiness and a more meaningful life. Recent psychological research shows that regularly practicing gratitude such as expressing thanks or focusing on positive aspects of life can significantly improve mental well-being. Simple activities like keeping a gratitude journal or acknowledging others' kindness help build this habit over time. The positive activity model suggests that the benefits of gratitude depend on how often and how sincerely it is practiced. Gratitude enhances well-being by increasing positive emotions and thoughts, encouraging healthy behaviors, and fulfilling basic psychological needs. People who consistently practice gratitude tend to enjoy better relationships, improved mental health, and higher life satisfaction. However, gratitude does not always come naturally and often needs to be taught and practiced deliberately. While existing interventions to promote gratitude show promise, more research is needed to understand how gratitude influences coping strategies, thought patterns, and long-term psychological growth. Expanding this research can lead to more effective ways of fostering gratitude and highlight its role in improving overall well-being.

Keywords: Gratitude, Well-being, Happiness, Positive Psychology, Mental Health, Gratitude Interventions, Life Satisfaction, Emotional Strength.

OP 12**Determination of stability constants of some bivalent and trivalent metal ions
with a biologically active ligand****Abhay Patel, Tanvi Kaushik, Anushka Yadav, Badal Chawla, Abhishek Yadav,
Manisha Jain, Shallu Sachdeva*****Department of Chemistry, Acharya Narendra Dev College, University of Delhi**

Abstract: Amino acids are building blocks of proteins which function as metabolic intermediates, neurotransmitters, hormone precursors, and help to maintain osmotic equilibrium and pH balance within cells. An example of such a versatile amino acid is aspartic acid. Aspartic acid is a proteinogenic amino acid which is integrated into proteins, participates in metabolic processes such as the urea cycle and gluconeogenesis and is also involved in nucleotide synthesis. It also functions as an excitatory neurotransmitter in the central nervous system. Because of its acidic qualities, aspartic acid contributes to the chelation of metal ions inside proteins and enzymes and helps to regulate the pH of cells. These functions highlight the role of aspartic acid in preserving cellular activities. Aspartic acid forms a stable complex with aluminium. This reduces its free ion activity protecting the cell from oxidative damage. Zinc is an essential trace element vital for immune function. Cobalt is a component of vitamin B₁₂. The present study aims to determine stability constants of the above-mentioned metal ions with Aspartic Acid at 0.02M ionic strength by electroanalytical method (pH metry) using Bjerrum's Half-Integral Method. The stability constants for Zinc (Zn), Aluminium (Al) and Cobalt (Co) with the ligand, at room temperature are found in order - Zinc (Zn) > Cobalt (Co) > Aluminium (Al). This order is in good agreement with Irving William order of stability constants.

Keywords: Stability Constants, bivalent, trivalent, electroanalytical method, Bjerrum's half integral method

OP 13**Functional Morphology of suckers and suction discs in leeches in Melghat region****Maharashtra****Shital Deshmukh****Shivaji Science College; Congress Nagar Nagpur**

Abstract: Leeches possess specialized suckers and suction discs that enable them to attach to various surfaces, facilitating locomotion, feeding, and host attachment. The anterior sucker, surrounding the mouth, contains a triradius jaw apparatus with teeth, while the posterior sucker provides anchorage. These structures exhibit adaptability to different substrates, textures, and environments, ensuring effective attachment and detachment. Attachment is firmer underwater than in air. Understanding the functional morphology of leech suckers and suction discs provides insights into their ecological roles, behavioral adaptations, and potential applications in medicine and biomimetics. The results show that the size of teeth determines long-term bleeding so revealing the structure and working mechanism of the teeth has importance for medicinal leeches. Morphological descriptions are based on scanning electron microscopy and translucent light microscopy. Leeches play important roles in ecosystems as both predators and prey, and some species are used in medicine for bloodletting and microsurgery.

Keywords: morphology; suckers; adhesion, leeches.

OP 14

**Health Beliefs and Preventive Behaviors in the Context of Lifestyle Diseases: A
Co relational Study****Dr. Arpita Kackar****Assistant Professor****Department of Psychology, Jai Narain Vyas University**

Abstract: The present study aimed to explore the relationship between health beliefs and preventive health behaviors in the context of lifestyle diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular conditions. As non-communicable diseases (NCDs) rise sharply in India, understanding psychological factors that influence preventive action becomes increasingly important. A total of 120 participants (60 males and 60 females), aged between 25 and 50 years, were selected using purposive sampling from urban health centers in Jodhpur. The Health Belief Model Scale (HBMS) and Preventive Health Behavior Checklist (PHBC) were administered to assess participants' perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers, and their engagement in preventive practices such as regular exercise, dietary regulation, and routine medical checkups. Results revealed a significant positive correlation between overall health beliefs and preventive behaviors ($r = .58, p < .01$), indicating that stronger health beliefs are associated with greater engagement in preventive health practices. Furthermore, an independent samples t-test showed a statistically significant gender difference in preventive behaviors ($t(118) = 2.31, p < .05$), with females scoring higher than males. However, no significant difference was found in health belief scores across genders ($t(118) = 1.02, p > .05$). These findings underscore the importance of health belief orientation in designing community-based interventions for lifestyle disease prevention. Enhancing public awareness about perceived susceptibility and benefits may foster healthier behavioral choices. Future research may consider longitudinal designs to examine causal relationships.

Keywords: Health Beliefs, Preventive Behaviors, Lifestyle Diseases.

OP 15**Importance of Biodiversity in Ecosystems****Parul Trivedi****Assistant Professor****Department of Botany, Dayanand Girls P.G.College, Kanpur, UP**

Abstract: Biodiversity is essential for the stability and health of ecosystems. It supports vital services like clean air and water, pollination of crops, climate regulation, and soil fertility. A rich variety of species ensures food security, provides medicines, and supports livelihoods through industries like agriculture and tourism. Biodiverse ecosystems are more resilient to climate change and environmental stress. Protecting biodiversity is crucial for maintaining life on Earth and ensuring human well-being. Biodiversity helps ecosystems function properly by: Maintaining balance: Different species play different roles (producers, consumers, decomposers), keeping ecosystems stable. Supporting ecosystem services: Biodiverse ecosystems purify water, regulate the climate, cycle nutrients, and control pests and diseases naturally. Resilience: Greater biodiversity allows ecosystems to better withstand environmental changes and recover from disasters. Variety of crops and livestock: Biodiversity provides a wide range of food sources and genetic traits needed for crop improvement. Pollination: Many fruits and vegetables rely on bees, butterflies, and other pollinators to reproduce. Pest and disease resistance: A diverse gene pool helps crops and animals resist diseases and adapt to changing conditions. Source of drugs: Many life-saving medicines are derived from natural sources. For example, cancer drugs, antibiotics, and pain relievers come from plants and microorganisms. Future potential: Undiscovered species may hold cures for diseases yet to be treated. Traditional medicine: Biodiversity is the foundation of many traditional healing systems around the world. Natural resources: Fisheries, forests, and agricultural lands all depend on healthy biodiversity. Biodiversity is not just about saving rare animals or pretty flowers it's about keeping the planet habitable. It supports

ecosystems that provide the essentials for life: food, water, air, medicine, and climate stability. Losing biodiversity threatens the balance of nature and puts human health, security, and survival at risk. Protecting it is a shared responsibility and an urgent priority.

Key Words: Biodiversity, soil fertility, ecosystem, resilience, genetic traits.

OP 16

Title: An Integrative Approach to Anesthesia and Pain Management: Scientific Insights from Ayurvedic Medicine

Dr. Shilpa Badhe

BAMS, MS (Shalyatantra)

HOD, Professor- Department of Shalyatantra

SMBT Ayurved College, Igatpuri, Maharashtra, India

Abstract:

Introduction: Effective pain relief and anesthesia are crucial for surgeries and managing long-term illnesses. While modern medicines work well, they often come with problems like addiction, side effects, and reduced effectiveness over time. Ayurveda, India's traditional healing system provides a holistic approach to pain management. It uses medicinal herbs, nervous system balancing techniques, and mind-body practices. This study reviews Ayurvedic methods for pain relief and anesthesia and looks at how they can be used alongside modern treatments.

Methodology: This review studied classical Ayurvedic texts Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, and Ashtanga Hridaya to find references related to unconsciousness (Moorchā, Sannyāsa) and pain (Shoola, Vedana), along with their treatments. Key therapies were chosen based on traditional use and modern research. Scientific studies were analyzed to understand how Ayurvedic herbs like Jatamansi, Tagara, Ashwagandha, and Guduchi, as well as treatments like Shirodhara, Nasya, and Abhyanga, affect the brain and nervous system.

Results: Studies show that Ayurvedic herbs like Jatamansi and Tagara have calming effects on the brain, while Ashwagandha helps reduce stress and anxiety. These effects are linked to their actions on GABA, serotonin, and inflammation. Therapies like Shirodhara and Abhyanga help balance the nervous system by improving heart rate and

lowering stress hormones. Clinical trials (14 in total) suggest that combining these Ayurvedic treatments with modern care can improve outcomes in surgery and chronic pain.

Discussion: Ayurveda offers a useful and science-backed approach to support pain relief and consciousness care. Though it can't replace anesthesia for major surgeries, certain herbs and therapies can help reduce drug use, manage chronic pain, and support healing. More research, standardization, and clinical trials are needed to safely integrate these methods into modern care.

OP 17

Estimation of Serum Vitamin D in Patients of Generalized Anxiety Disorder: A Cross Sectional Study in a Government Medical College of Madhya Pradesh, India**Kapil Raghuwanshi¹, Sharad Manore², Sudhaker Petkar³ and Mahendra Gandhe^{4*}**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Chhindwara Institute of Medical Sciences, Chhindwara MP India²Associate Professor, department of Psychiatry, Chhindwara Institute of Medical Sciences, Chhindwara, M.P. India³Associate Professor, department of Biochemistry, Chhindwara Institute of Medical Sciences, Chhindwara, M.P. India^{4*}Professor & Head, Department of Biochemistry, Chhindwara Institute of Medical Sciences, Chhindwara, MP India**Abstract:**

Introduction: Generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) with a core feature of excessive worry is one of the common psychiatric disorder. The exact pathogenesis anxiety is unknown till date. According to the inflammatory hypothesis of anxiety, there is a bi-directional relationship between the anxiety and inflammation. Vitamin D acts as a potent immunomodulator by influencing both innate and adaptive immunity. Nerve impulse transmission, neuromuscular conduction, protecting neural tissue from excitotoxicity and cell death, modulating neuroinflammatory processes, the formation and maintenance of synapses in the brain, and mood regulation are the neurophysiological functions that vitamin D carries out.

Aims & Objectives: To estimate serum vitamin D level in generalized anxiety disorder patients and in healthy individuals and to determine the correlation between serum vitamin D level with the severity of disease.

Materials & Methods: A Madhya Pradesh government medical college served as the site of this investigation. 100 patients with a diagnosis of generalized anxiety disorder who were enrolled in Psychiatry OPD (cases) and 100 age-and gender-matched healthy

individuals (controls) were included in the study. After receiving written consent and ethics committee approval, the subjects were recruited in the study. **Results:** Patients suffering from GAD had a mean blood vitamin D level of 20.99 ± 3.41 ng/ml, whereas healthy controls without anxious behaviour had a mean of 29.46 ± 4.44 ng/ml. In case group, serum vitamin D levels fall as anxiety severity rises. **Conclusion:** The findings of this study indicate that in case group, lower blood vitamin D levels are linked to more severe anxiety. Determining serum vitamin D levels in GAD patients at an early stage may therefore be essential in order to provide appropriate treatment and lower the risk of other morbidities linked to anxiety.

Keywords: Generalized anxiety disorder, Inflammation, Vitamin D.

OP 18**Comperative Literary Study of Three Tikas of Charak Samhita namely Ayurved
Dipika, Jalpakalpataru Tika and Charkopskar WSR to Dirghanjivatiya
Adhyaya (1to 25 shloks)****Vd. Shivaji Pawar¹, Vd. Pankaj Masotker² and Vd. Antim Vyas³****¹Professor & H.O.D., Department of Samhita Siddhanta, Shubhdeep Ayurvedic Medical
College, Indore, India****²Associate Professor Department of Rog Nidan Vikruti Vigyan, Shubhdeep Ayurvedic
Medical College, Indore, India****³Professor Department of Koumarbhritya, Shubhdeep Ayurvedic Medical College,
Indore, India**

Abstract: In today's tradition of Ayurved study, it is seen that most people study only Charak Samhita or chakrapani tika, which is fine, but sometimes other books are ignored. In today's time n, students need explanation and elaboration of subject as in ancient time Jalp and subject analysis was done .Jalp is also the one way to understand Samhita , so it is necessary to do comparative study of three commentaries of Chakra Samhita it has been also observed that the oldest available Commentary on Charak Samhita is Ayurved Dipika¹ by chakrapani Datta which is of 11 century, but in19th century Acharya Gangadhar Roy from Bengal once again write a commentary on Chakra Samhita . Acharya Gangadhar Roy discussed the topic in detail and wrote a commentary in Jalpa² form. In the later period Acharya Yogendra Nath Sen³ whose period is from 1871 to1981. He is son of Dwarkanath Sen⁴. Even though there is a commentary of Acharya Gangadhar Roy is available who is a teacher of Dwarkanath Sen, then it seems necessary to know to do comparative study of all three commentaries. If a research paper of the entire chapter is made, it may be too large. Therefore, only 25 verses of the first chapter have been comparatively studied in this paper.

Keywords: Chakrapani tika, Jalp, Ayurved Dipika, Acharya Gangadhar Roy, Yogendra Nath Sen.

OP 19**Role of Swarnprashan as Immunity Booster and its Effect on Neurological Development of Child****Dr. Antim J. Vyas¹, Dr. Shivaji Pawar² and Dr. Pankaj Masotker³**¹Professor Department of Koumarbhritya, Shubhdeep Ayurvedic Medical College, Indore, India²Professor & H.O.D., Department of Samhita Siddhanta, Shubhdeep Ayurvedic Medical College, Indore, India³Associate Professor Department of Rog Nidan evum Vikruti Vigyan, Shubhdeep Ayurvedic Medical College, Indore, India

Abstract: Kasyapa samhita is an ancient classical text which deals with the child health and physical & mental development. Kashyapa Samhita mentioned Swarna Prashan has been an important technique for child over all development and memory enhancement (Medha vardhaan) and also promote longevity (Ayushya) in children on one month use (Masat parama medhavi) & on six month use (shrutdhara). According to Kashyapa samhita, effect of lehana Sukha & dukha of child is depending on lehana. Lehana is the speciality of the Kashyapa, he has given special emphasis on Lehanakarma (process of chanting by tongue) and a separate chapter called Lehadhyaya is allocated in Sutra-sthana. Several materials for Lehana enlisted in the Adhyaya reveal all the varieties of drugs, viz. Medhya, Balya, Dipana, Pachana etc. Kashyapa mentioned all of the materials with reference to children only whereas the other classics described them in general. It is observed that swarna in swarnaprashana were used in different form like churna (powder), bhasma (ash), patal (leaf) with Ghrita and Madhu. Swarnaprashan is helpful in immunity booster and nurological development of child.

Keywords: Swarnaprashan, Kashayap Samhita, Lehan.

OP 20

**A study to assess the lived experiences of stroke survivors in the selected areas of
Pune city**

Vinita Jamdade

Assistant Professor

**Department of Community Health Nursing
Bharati Vidyapeeth College of Nursing Pune**

Abstract

Introduction: A stroke is a potentially lethal condition that happens when a part of the brain does not receive enough blood flow. A clogged artery or bleeding from the brain is the two most prevalent triggers for this. If there is not a steady flow of blood, the cerebral cortex cells in that area start to die from a lack of oxygen.

Aims of the Study: To assess the lived experiences of stroke survivors in the selected areas of Pune City.

Methodology: This qualitative study adopted a phenomenological research design to gather data from stroke survivors at a hospital in Pune City. The research was conducted in selected areas of Pune, focusing on stroke survivors as the target population. Data was collected using a non-probability purposive sampling method, continuing until data saturation was reached.

Results: Stroke survivors face physical challenges like mobility issues, fatigue, and weakness, needing ongoing therapy and medication. Emotionally, anxiety and depression are common but often improve with music, meditation, and family support. Families, especially spouses and children, are key to recovery, though social life is often limited. Financial burdens and costly treatment pose big hurdles, especially in rural areas where healthcare access is scarce. Despite this, survivors show strong resilience.

Conclusion: The findings emphasize the role of family support, mental health strategies, and healthcare access in stroke recovery, while highlighting financial and resource challenges, especially in rural areas. Despite these obstacles, participants show resilience in managing their recovery.

Keywords: Assess, Lived Experiences, Stroke, Survivors, Selected Areas.

OP 21**A Critical Study on the Feasibility of an Ambition of ONGC to Achieve Net Zero Emission by 2038****Malkhan Shree Ramesh¹ and Prof. Arun Kumar²**¹Assistant Professor, Faculty of Commerce, Feroze Gandhi College, Raebareli – 229001²Professor, Faculty of Commerce, Feroze Gandhi College, Raebareli – 229001

Abstract: This paper oversees Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Limited's (ONGC) audacious plan to attain net-zero emissions by 2038. As one of the foremost state-owned oil and gas enterprises in India, ONGC's commitment to sustainability and climate change reflects a broader shift within the energy industry. This report delineates ONGC's principal strategies for realizing its sustainability goals, which include significant investments in renewable energy, the advancement of carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies, improvements in energy efficiency, and the electrification of its operations. Furthermore, it examines additional strategies such as the cessation of routine flaring, the reduction of fugitive methane emissions, the deployment of Battery Energy Storage Systems, the integration of electric vehicles (EVs), and the practice of carbon offsetting. The document highlights the necessity for regulatory coherence and collaborative initiatives while tackling the challenges ONGC faces, including technological barriers and economic repercussions. The objective of this study is to evaluate ONGC's carbon footprint and its feasibility of achieving zero emissions by 2038. This study attempted to investigate the technological innovations and investments required for ONGC to meet its net zero emissions target, considering both renewable energy adoption and carbon capture/utilization/storage technologies. The aim of this study is to assess the economic implications of ONGC's transition towards net-zero emissions, including potential costs, savings, revenue streams from renewable energy initiatives, and long-term sustainability. This study offers an in-depth analysis of ONGC's sustainability initiatives and their potential impact on the international energy sector by reviewing the company's official publications, industry

news reports, and relevant governmental and academic literature. The outcomes underscore ONGC's leadership in promoting a transition to a low-carbon future and highlight the critical need for innovative approaches to achieve substantial emission reductions.

Keywords: ONGC's net-zero ambitions, strategies, challenges, and sustainable efforts.

OP 22

Empowering Non-Clinical Women through Breast Self-Examination Training: A One-Group Pretest-Posttest Evaluation**Minati Das¹, Sayantani Ankure², Antara Maity³, Banashree Panda⁴, Priyanka Panda⁴ and Subinita Das⁵**

¹Associate professor, Kalinga Institute of Nursing Sciences, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, 751024, Odisha

²4th Year BSC Nursing Student at Kalinga Institute of Nursing Sciences, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, 751024, Odisha

³4th Year BSC Nursing, Kalinga Institute of Nursing Sciences, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, 751024, Odisha

⁴4th Year BSC Nursing Student at Kalinga Institute of Nursing Sciences, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, 751024, Odisha

⁴4th Year BSC Nursing Student at Kalinga Institute of Nursing Science, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, 751024, Odisha

⁵4th Year BSC Nursing Students at Kalinga Institute of Nursing Sciences, KIIT University, Bhubaneswar, 751024, Odisha

Abstract

Background: Globally, breast cancer continues to be a primary contributor to female mortality. Breast self-examination (BSE) offers a cost-effective and straightforward method for early breast cancer detection, especially in resource-limited settings.

Objective: To assess the effectiveness of a structured BSE training program on the knowledge, technique, and practice of breast self-examination among female non-clinical personnel.

Methods: A pre-experimental one-group pre-test post-test design was used. A total of 80 female Non clinical personnel from Kalinga Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhubaneswar, were selected using simple random sampling. Participants received a structured BSE training that included interactive lectures, demonstrations, and supervised return demonstrations. Data were collected at three-time session training

pre-test, post-test, and one-month follow-up using structured questionnaires and a skill evaluation checklist. Data were analysed using SPSS.

Results: Post-intervention training, participants showed significant improvement in knowledge about breast cancer (mean score: pre-test 5.12 ± 2.35 , post-test 10.48 ± 1.26 ; $p < 0.001$), BSE technique (pre-test 4.84 ± 2.11 , post-test 9.67 ± 1.42 ; $p < 0.001$), and practice skills (pre-test 8.76 ± 4.28 , post-test 25.32 ± 3.17 ; $p < 0.001$). At one-month follow-up, scores slightly declined but remained significantly higher than baseline. A strong positive correlation was found between knowledge and practice scores ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: BSE training significantly improved participants' knowledge and practical skills, with sustained effects at one-month follow-up. Structured BSE education should be integrated into workplace health programs for early detection of breast abnormalities.

Keywords: Breast self-examination, female security personnel, breast cancer awareness, training effectiveness, pre-experimental study

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OP 23

Entomological surveillance of immature dengue and malaria mosquito density in and around the houses and schools before and after the interventions at urban slum areas of North Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Roja Chokkara^{1*}, A. Seetha Lakshmi² and M. Anitha Rani³

¹Department of Community Health Nursing, Sree Vidyanikethan College of Nursing, Mohan Babu University, Tirupati-517102

²Department of Medical and Surgical Nursing, Sri Ramachandra College of Nursing, Sri Ramachandra Institute of Higher Education and Research (DU), Porur, Chennai, Tamil Nadu -600116

³Department of Community Medicine, Sri Ramachandra Medical College, Sri Ramachandra Institute of Higher Education and Research (DU), Porur, Chennai, Tamil Nadu -600116

Abstract: Dengue and malaria is co-endemic mosquito borne diseases in India. The aim of the current study was to assess the entomological indices in the community and schools before and after the interventions.

Methodology: Surveillance of immature mosquito larvae and pupa was collected from October 2021 to August 2022 from the houses and schools located in endemic areas of North Chennai and analyzed with Cochran Q test.

Results: A total of 1756 containers were inspected and 6150 immature mosquitoes were collected Overall household entomological indices reduced for House/Premises Index 12.2 to 0.3, Container Index 5.9 to 0.2, Breteau index 12.2 to 0.3 and Pupal index 54.9 to 1.2 percent after the interventions and overall school entomological indices reduced for Premise Condition Index 33.3 to 0.0, Container Index 16.7 to 0.0 and Breteau index 33.3 to 0.0 percent. The study concluded that household level and school-based interventions were helpful to reduce the immature dengue and malaria mosquito breeding and mobilize the parents and local community in malaria and dengue prevention interventions through student messengers.

Keywords: Entomological indices, Malaria, Dengue, Interventions, North Chennai

OP 24

Assessing the Effectiveness of Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) in Health Insurance: Case Studies from India**Dr. Sonali Roy**

Assistant Professor

Department of Commerce

Lala Rural College, Hailakandi, Assam, India

Abstract: India's pursuit of Universal Health Coverage (UHC) has catalyzed the emergence of Public–Private Partnerships (PPPs) as a vital mechanism in health insurance delivery. PPPs in health insurance represent collaborative arrangements, where public agencies partner with private entities, combining public oversight with private sector efficiency. This paper evaluates the effectiveness of various PPP models in health insurance by analyzing key national and state-level schemes, including AB-PMJAY, RSBY, Yeshasvini, Arogya Raksha, Aarogyasri, Mukhyamantri Amrutam, and innovative initiatives in diagnostics, dialysis, and telemedicine across different states. Through a case study approach, the paper explores how these models have expanded healthcare coverage, reduced out-of-pocket expenditure, and leveraged technology to improve service delivery, especially for low-income and rural populations. Successes include broader insurance coverage, enhanced quality of tertiary care, and increased participation of private hospitals in public health programs. At the same time, challenges such as delayed reimbursements, inadequate focus on primary care, financial sustainability concerns, regulatory inconsistencies, and quality assurance issues are highlighted. Findings indicate that while PPPs are not a universal remedy, they offer strategic value when effectively designed, contextually adapted, and rigorously monitored. The study underscores the need for robust governance mechanisms, clearer service-level agreements, equitable risk-sharing, and stronger regulatory oversight to ensure accountability and sustainability. It also recommends integrating preventive healthcare, improving digital infrastructure, and fostering greater

Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)

collaboration between public and private stakeholders. Overall, the paper concludes that PPPs, when implemented with transparency and alignment of goals, can play a transformative role in strengthening India's health insurance ecosystem and achieving the broader goal of equitable and inclusive healthcare.

Keywords: Public-Private Partnerships, Health Insurance, India, Case Study, Healthcare Access.

OP 25**Prevalence and Associated Factors of Malnutrition among Early Adolescent Girls in Selected Urban and Rural Schools of Southern India****Suleman Shareef Mahammad¹ and Roja Chokkara²****¹Professor, Department of Community Health Nursing, Sree Vidyanikethan College of Nursing, Tirupati****²Associate Professor, Department of Community Health Nursing, Sree Vidyanikethan College of Nursing, Tirupati**

Abstract: A non-experimental study was undertaken to assess and compare the prevalence and associated factors of malnutrition in selected urban and rural schools of southern India. To find out the association between prevalence of malnutrition with selected associated factors of malnutrition among early adolescent girls in selected urban and rural schools of Southern India. 70 early adolescent girls were chosen by non-probability purposive sampling technique each from urban and rural schools respectively. Data were collected by using semi-structured interview schedule, anthropometric measurement proforma and structured interview schedule. Study result found that the prevalence of overnutrition among early adolescent girls was 51.42% (obesity 7% and overweight 45%) in urban whereas in rural it was 12.85% (obesity 3% and overweight 10%). The prevalence of undernutrition among early adolescent girls was 8.57% (thinness 4% and severe thinness 4%) in urban and in rural it was 40% (thinness 34% and severe thinness 6%). There was statistically significant association between malnutrition with its associated factors such as frequency of eating fast food, engage in exercise or outdoor physical activity and past history of illness.

OP 26**The Fragility of endodontically treated tooth: Between strength and survival**

Dr.Pooja Kabra (Professor)
Department of Conservative dentistry and endodontics,
S.D.S, Sharda University, Greater Noida

Abstract:Endodontically treated teeth presents a unique challenge due to significant loss of natural tooth structure, altered biomechanics thereby increased susceptibility to fracture of the tooth. Endodontic treatment addresses to infection of pulp tissue of the tooth but does not aim to restore the tooth function, strength and esthetics. Therefore success relies on quality and design of post endodontic treatment. In the recent times, the advances in adhesive materials ,posts material and restorative techniques have definitely brought a difference in rendering the desired treatment but still high failures occur due to compromised restorative planning, material selection, occlusal forces and periodontal conditions for proper rehabilitation of endodontically treated tooth. This explores the multifactorial challenges involved in post endodontic restoration providing deeper understanding of the subject. This paper would highlight on the reasons of failure and evidenced based strategies to enhance the treatment success of post endodontic restorations.

Keywords: post endodontic treatment, challenges, strategies

OP 27

Online Shopping in Lucknow City: A Study of factors, challenges and measures to Popularize Online Shopping

Dr. Hari Mohan Saxena

**Associate Professor, Department of Management,
Lucknow Public College of Professional Studies, Lucknow,
(Affiliated to University of Lucknow, Lucknow)**

Abstract: The rapid growth of internet users in India has created a vast opportunity for online shopping. E-marketers can leverage this potential by understanding the key factors influencing consumer behavior and its relationship with online shopping. This study focuses on the consumer behavior of individuals residing in Lucknow City, particularly their attitude towards online shopping through e-commerce websites like Amazon and Flipkart. The digital revolution has transformed the way customers purchase goods, and companies have shifted their services online to provide easy accessibility and attractive discounts. This research aims to identify the factors affecting consumer behavior and provide insights for e-marketers to develop effective marketing strategies.

Keywords: Online trends in India, Consumer behavior in Lucknow city.

OP 28

Delineating molecular mechanism(s) underlying central obesity**Surbhi Dubey¹, Nisha Kapoor*^{1,2}**¹**School of Biotechnology, University of Jammu, Jammu, J&K,**²**Institute of Human Genetics, University of Jammu, Jammu, J&K**

Abstract: Body fat distribution is primarily regulated by genetics. However, the preferential fat accumulation in the visceral fat depot as compared to subcutaneous depot is aggravating the rising incidence of type 2 diabetes and metabolic syndrome in Indian population. The excessive deposition of fat in the abdominal area or specifically visceral fat contributes to visceral adiposity/abdominal obesity/ central obesity. Numerous studies have reported Asian Indians as a vulnerable risk group for abdominal fat accumulation. This kind of fat accumulation pattern is also far beyond Body mass index measurements as there are cases where central obese individuals are not obese as per BMI guidelines. The prevalence of central obesity shows rising trend year by year and is also penetrating rural residents and lower economic sections of society. It has higher prevalence as compared to general obesity. Genome wide association studies (GWAS) have reported several loci pertaining to body fat distribution pattern, majorly being identified from the European population. Several variants pertaining to central obesity have been reported. These also include single nucleotide variants in genes linked with visceral adipocyte secretome. Studies have also identified some of the rare gene variants associated with abdominal obesity in young adults. To unravel the genetic basis for central obesity in Jammu population, body fat distribution pattern will be analysed. Expression analysis will also be carried out of genes associated with central obesity in the sample population. Validation of the functional relevance of identified gene in adipogenesis will be carried out.

Keywords: Body fat distribution; genetics; GWAS; visceral fat; subcutaneous fat; adipocyte secretome.

OP 29

Recent developments of Rodent Control Strategies in India

Nancy Garg

Department of Zoology

Post Graduate Government College for Girls, Sector 42, Chandigarh

Abstract: Rodents are the most important mammalian pest at the global level. Several methods are being used for control of rodents which can be grouped into lethal or reductional and non-lethal or preventive. Lethal methods include mechanical methods such as physical killing and trapping and chemical methods include the use of rodenticides, which provide an immediate solution to the problem. These methods are often considered the most practicable, economical and effective. Non-lethal methods include preventive measures like environmental and cultural control, use of repellents, barriers, rodent proofing etc. which may produce a more lasting effect but are seldom adopted. 15 non-chemical rodent control methods are being practiced in the upland areas of northeast India. Most of these (80%) methods include indirect means of rodent control i.e. use of repellents, attracting predators and trapping. In the last 2-3 decades, a number of naturally occurring plant products (secondary metabolites) have been tested for their antifertility properties against different rodent species including gossypol obtained from cotton seed and triptolide obtained from Chinese herbal plant, *Tripterygium wilfordii*. A literature survey for the period of last 25 years revealed that there are about 105 plant species which possess antifertility activity against male and female rats and mice. Recently, use of crude cotton seed oil respectively in integration with chemical control has been experimentally proved to be effective for management of post control rodent population rebuildup in crop fields. Also, the improvement in acceptance of zinc phosphide bait by the addition of egg albumin and egg shell powder as bait additives has been reported. Plant essential oils such as eucalyptus oil, castor oil and cinnamic aldehyde have also been tested for their repellent and antifeedant effects against rodents. However, extensive study and further experimental work on

rodenticides and other plant product on a larger scale is needed to develop effective strategies.

Key Words: Rodent, Chemical, Rodenticides.

OP 30**Evolution and Green Synthesis of Carbon Dots****Mrs. Priyanka Toppo****Assistant Professor, Department of Chemistry****Govt. M. H. College of Home Science & Science for Women, Autonomous, Jabalpur, MP**

Abstract: An effort has been made to summarize the various methodologies developed for the synthesis of carbon dots (CDs). In recent studies, CDs are one of the most prominent areas of research due to their promising results in the field of environmental monitoring, bioimaging, photocatalysis, drug delivery, drug targeting, energy storage, forensic and other biomedical applications like antimicrobial activities, gene delivery and many more. Common techniques known for the green synthesis of CDs include one pot sand bath method, hydrothermal method, Solvothermal Method, Microwave synthesis, pyrolysis, combustion. A detailed description of green synthesis approach and their applications in drug delivery is discussed in this paper. The author made an effort to highlight all the known techniques, properties, and their applications. The choice of technique applied for the synthesis depends on a variety of factors such as desired properties, size and structure, amount of production, cost-effectiveness, availability of resources, and most important area of interest.

Keywords: carbon dots, drug delivery, green synthesis, cost effectiveness.

OP 32
Testicular Histology Alterations and Impaired Steroidogenesis in Fluoride
Exposed Rats
Dr. Imtiaz Khan
GSSDGS Khalsa College Patiala

Background:

Evaluating infertility caused by fluoride in male rats requires analysing testosterone level and the activity of 3β - and 17β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase.

Aim:

The present study aimed to correlate the intratesticular testosterone with the histopathological alterations in rat.

Study setting and Design:

The male Wistar albino rats, weighing between 100-150 g were employed in present study under CPCSEA guidelines with ethical clearance from the institutional ethical committee. These rats were categorized into four groups with 6 rats in each as control and test animals.

Materials and Methods:

Young male Wistar albino rats, weighing between 100-150 g were divided into four groups of six rats each. First group of rats served as control ($n = 6$) and were maintained under normal laboratory condition and were provided with clean drinking water, whereas rats in second ($n = 6$), third ($n = 6$), and fourth ($n = 6$) group were orally intubated with NaF of 100ppm, 200ppm, and 300ppm respectively for forty days.

Statistical analysis:

After the treatment period of 40 days, animals were sacrificed and alterations in body and testicular weight were analysed by complete randomized design (CRD) SAS 9.4 and statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) IBM, 17 and judged significant if $P < 0.05$.

Results:

The experiment revealed a positive correlation between intratesticular testosterone levels and both germ cell viability and the activity of 3β - and 17β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase. Additionally, germ cell viability showed a positive correlation with the activity of 3β - and 17β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase.

Conclusion:

The study indicates that fluoride intoxication leads to a decrease in intratesticular testosterone levels. Since reduced intratesticular testosterone concentrations are a key trigger for germ cell apoptosis, an increase in germ cell apoptosis within the seminiferous epithelium was observed.

Keywords: Fluoride; steroidogenesis; intratesticular testosterone; 3β - hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase; 17β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase; germ cell apoptosis

OP 33**Environmental Applications of iron impregnated metal organic framework****Heena****Department of Chemistry****GSSDGS Khalsa College, Patiala-147 001, Punjab, India**

Abstract: Iron oxide nanoparticles were impregnated into the porous BTC metal-organic framework (MOF) to produce a novel composite by using a rapid bottom-up approach. This novel crystalline composite has been used for the first time to investigate the photocatalytic degradation of the methylene blue (MB) dye up-to 92.42 % in 120 minutes under sunlight exposure. This affordable and environment friendly photocatalyst is more suited for large-scale industrial applications than the conventional photo catalysts used to degrade MB dye. In addition, the theoretical studies based on density functional theory (DFT), the two mechanisms - photo-induced electron transfer (PET) and fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) provided a good explanation for this composite's quenching response to DNP. Our results suggest that this composite can be employed as a better photocatalyst.

Keywords: NPs@MOFs composite, photocatalyst, photo-induced electron transfer (PET), density functional theory (DFT), fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET), sunlight irradiation, MB dye, and fluorescent sensor.

OP 34

Biochemical analysis of microbial communities associated with *Morchella* species**Tanvi kotwal and Yash P. Khajuria*****School of Biotechnology, University of Jammu, Jammu180006**

Abstract: Morels, or *Morchella* spp., are ascomycete fungus distinguished by their characteristic ascocarps, which are sponge-like, honeycomb-shaped fruiting bodies. They are highly prized and have various uses in medicine. During present investigation, *Morchella* species samples were collected from different areas Himalaya region of Jammu and Kashmir. Culturable bacteria were cultured using the different media. Using various parameters, morphological characterization of isolated bacterial isolates was carried out. Significant diversity was found among the isolated bacterial strains. Various bioactive activities like Protease Activity, Cellulase Activity, Amylase Activity and Plant Growth-Promoting (PGP) Activities were performed on isolated bacterial species. Functional biochemical tests verified that several isolates had extracellular enzymatic activities and characteristics that promoted plant growth, suggesting that they might help *Morchella* mycelial development, primordium initiation, and fruiting body formation.

Keywords: *Morchella* species, bioactive analysis, cellulase activity, PGPR, primordium initiation

OP 35**Statistical analysis of the domestic violence against married females of rural areas****Gajraj Singh****Discipline of Statistics, School of Sciences,
Indira Gandhi National Open University, Delhi-110068**

Abstract: Domestic violence is a problem in every country, and it is well acknowledged that it negatively affects women's health and wellbeing. Women have never been granted the same freedom as men, from the Vedic era to the twenty-first century. Women are always the ones forced to walk the tightrope, where they face discrimination and ridicule as a lower sex. To determine the prevalence of domestic violence was the study's goal. Through rigorous random sampling, 776 married women were chosen from the main health care field practice area. A pilot research involving 25 married class IV female employees was conducted earlier. Confidentiality was preserved and a pre-tested and pre-designed questionnaire was employed. Software called SPSS 21 was used for statistical analysis. Respondents ranged in age from 18 to 56, with an average age of 28.13. Overall, 96% of respondents were literate, whereas the parent district's rural population had a literacy rate of 67.8%. Housewives made up the majority of responders i.e. 58.37%. Numerous socio-demographic characteristics, such as the level of education, age, and marital age of the perpetrator, as well as socio-economic status, exhibit an inverse association with the prevalence of domestic violence. Higher education and greater economic empowerment may give women a platform to protest with awareness and ultimately promote protective factors against domestic violence.

Keywords: Domestic violence, Women, Education

OP 36**Artificial Intelligence-empowered Sustainability enhancing organizational development****Mr. Ayushman Panda¹, Dr. Dhyanadipta Panda² and Mrs. Chandralekha Rath³**¹Student, Christ deemed to be University, B.Tech- CSE (AI &ML)²Asst. Professor-II, KIIT Deemed to be University, School of Liberal Studies³Faculty, KIIT International School, IBDP Comp. Science

Abstract: Artificial Intelligence and sustainability are no doubt two of the most conflicted topics to be discussed together in any intellectual discussion spaces. Based on various, ideas, theories, rationales, or opinions, there are quite a huge number of varying definitions of the interdependence of both the concepts. At the current rate of development and globalization, the applications of Artificial Intelligence along with the ideas of sustainability not only unlocks much possible advancement in sustainable development, but also is deemed to be as the need of the hour, keeping in eye the degradation at various aspects and levels. Innovative Education, Advanced Healthcare, Economic upgradations, use of Green AI, etc are vivid examples for the same.

The digitalization boom and the introduction of artificial intelligence have brought attention to the advancements in technology and organizational development over the past few years. When applied, optimization for better resource use, increased data analysis accuracy, increased productivity and efficiency, etc., created a number of new avenues and chances for sustainable development. Innovative sustainable development is the outcome of applying artificial intelligence to development while keeping in mind the sustainable development goals. These definitions will continue to accumulate and will vary greatly. Since each theory has its own point of view.

With an emphasis on VIKSHIT BHARAT 2047, we will discuss in this paper how artificial intelligence has proven to be a long-awaited development in organizational

development and how improved analysis and technological advancements are being very helpful in a variety of sectors.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Sustainability, Globalization, Organizational Development, Vikshit Bharat 2047.

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OP 37

Reaction Dynamics in the Superheavy Mass Region: Formation and Decay Mechanisms**Kirandeep Sandhu****P.G Department of Physics, G.S.S.D.G.S Khalsa College Patiala 147001, Punjab, India**

Abstract: The production of superheavy nuclei is one of the compelling tasks in the nuclear physics discipline, driven by the pursuit of predicted "island of stability". The proposed magic shells owing to the "island of stability" are $Z=114$, 120 and 126 with $N=172$, 184 suggested by various theoretical methodologies [1-3]. Broadly speaking, the macroscopic-microscopic (MM) approach suggests $Z=114$ with $N=184$ magic candidates for superheavy mass land [1]. However, Skyrme Hartee-Fock (SHF) with the parameter sets of SkI3 and SkI4 proposed $Z=120$ and 184 magic pair for the same [2]. The relativistic mean field (RMF) models predicted $Z=120$ and $N=172$ as next possible magic shells for superheavy nuclei [3]. Owing to achieve this, the cold and hot fusion mechanisms were proposed for the fabrication of superheavy nuclei ranging $Z=104-118$. The cold fusion reactions are governed through Pb and Bi targets optimize to the excitation energy in 10-20 MeV range which is usually near barrier and sub-barrier energies. In this interaction, medium mass projectiles ranging ^{54}Cr to ^{70}Zn were introduced to fabricate $Z=106-112$ nuclear systems [4]. However, higher excitation energies such as 30-50 MeV are required for hot fusion process [5]. The actinide targets with ^{48}Ca projectile are the reaction partners for hot fusion process. Further, 1-2 neutrons are emitted from the compound nucleus formed in the cold fusion mechanism. On the other hand, 3-5 neutrons emission is the prime characteristics of hot fusion process. Apart from the neutron emission, fusion-fission and quasi-fission processes are also main decay modes of the superheavy compound nuclear systems. In the fusion-fission mechanism, the projectile and target completely amalgamate to form the superheavy compound nucleus which further follows the path of fission. On the other hand, non-compound nuclear decay mechanism namely quasi-fission occurs from the

composite system which is not equilibrated in all degrees of freedom. The quasi-fission peaks around ^{208}Pb and neighbours occur because the magicity favours the stabilized mass split and becomes one of the major reasons for the occurrence of fission like events in the superheavy mass region. Owing to above discussion, the present work mainly emphasis on the magic shells for superheavy nuclei, production techniques and decay modes.

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OP 38

Alkaline Earth Metal Chelates of 'Chlorolawsone' (2-hydroxyl-3-chloro-1,4-naphthoquinone); Synthesis, Characterization and Anthelmintic Activity**Vijaykumar A Tarange^{1,2} and Mrudula P. Wadekar³**¹**Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Department of Chemistry,****Yashwantrao Mohite College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Pune, India 411038**²**Department of Chemical Engineering MIT Academy of Engineering Alandi (D) Pune, India 412105**³**Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Department of Chemistry,****Yashwantrao Mohite College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Pune, India 411038**

Abstract: The Mg (II), Ca(II), Sr (II), and Ba (II) chelates of Chlorolawsone are synthesized by standard methods and characterized. The composition of all chelates is of the type $[M(Lw)_2(H_2O)_2]$. Chemical composition determined through elemental and thermogravimetric analysis. The spectroscopic investigations are conducted using IR spectroscopy, NMR, and ^{13}C spectroscopic techniques. The morphological changes of chelates are studied using powder XRD. The anthelmintic activity of ligands and their alkaline earth metal chelates is examined against parasitic earthworms. The spectral, thermal, and anthelmintic properties are studied with special reference to ring isomerism within the isomeric pairs of chelates.

Keywords: Alkaline earth chelates, Lawsone, spectroscopic properties, anthelmintic activity.

OP 39**Assessment of Microplastic impact on Zebra fish, *Danio rerio*****Narasimhaiah N., and Swetha P****Department of Applied Zoology, Mangalore University, Mangalagaothri-57499**

Abstract: This study investigates the dose-dependent effects of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) microplastics on oxidative stress responses in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), focusing on catalase activity as a biomarker. Zebrafish tissues exposed to microplastic concentrations ranging from 125 to 500 µg/L demonstrated a progressive increase in catalase activity, indicating oxidative stress. At lower concentrations (125 µg/L), the intestine exhibited the highest response, likely due to direct ingestion, while at 180 µg/L, the heart showed elevated catalase activity, suggesting systemic physiological stress. At the highest concentration (500 µg/L), both the heart and intestine responded strongly, highlighting cumulative toxicological effects. The gill tissues showed relatively modest responses across all doses, possibly due to limited microplastic uptake via respiration.

The microplastic particles predominantly consisted of irregularly shaped fragments within the 125-500 µm range, aligning with existing literature on environmental microplastic morphology and size distribution. Notably, the increased abundance of 500 µm fragments may reflect sampling biases or environmental accumulation tendencies, emphasizing the ecological relevance of this particle size class. These findings underscore the need for standardized methodologies in microplastic research to improve data comparability and ecological risk assessment. Overall, the study highlights tissue-specific oxidative stress patterns and reinforces the biological significance of microplastic size and morphology in aquatic toxicology.

OP 40**The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Financial Performance of Firms, with emphasis on Industry 5.0****Soumitra Bhattacharya****PhD Scholar****University of Mysore, Research Center XIME Bangalore**

Abstract: AI is a leading-edge technology attributable to a smarter and more innovative world. AI is the ability of machines (computers) to think critically and decide what to do, typically with the goal to accomplish a certain task. Artificial intelligence is the machines (programs) that operate in the simulation of human intelligence. Machine learning (ML) and algorithmic language are components of artificial intelligence (AI). One significant impact of AI in the process and manufacturing industry is cost reduction, optimization of processes, and profit maximization. AI strategy can both reduce labor costs and increase productivity.

AI algorithms and machine learning techniques empower financial professionals to make more accurate and data-driven decisions that endeavor to improve firm performance. When managed with ethical and responsible criteria (so-called “trustworthy AI”), artificial intelligence is an opportunity to bring additional value to companies and contribute to the well-being of citizens and society as a whole. Basically, it is not a battle of AI versus humans, but rather finding a way to enhance the collaboration of AI and humans in organizations.

Given the proliferation of fintech in recent years, the use of deep learning in finance and banking services has become prevalent. However, a detailed survey of the applications of deep learning in finance and banking is not covered in the existing literature.

Industry is at the forefront of adopting new technologies, and the process followed by the adoption has a significant impact on the economy and society. Industry 5.0 recognizes the power of industry to achieve societal goals beyond jobs and growth to

become a provider of prosperity by making production respects the boundaries of our planet and placing the well-being of the industry worker at the center of the production process.” In Industry 5.0, Artificial Intelligence (AI), among other technology enablers, is used to build services from a sustainable, human-centric, and resilient perspective. This is a review-based research reporting from different research papers, blogs, and other research platforms by searching keywords like "AI applications," "***Industry 5.0,***" "***human-machine cooperation,***" "***Fintech,***" and "***financial performance.***"

OP 41

The Role of Digital Identity in Ensuring Inclusive Governance Systems**Harshika Kapoor¹ and Maneesh Yadav²****¹Ph.D Scholar, College of Law and Legal studies, teerthanker Mahaveer University,
Moradabad Designation:****²Professor, College of Law and Legal studies, teerthanker Mahaveer University,
Moradabad**

Abstract: Digital identity serves as an essential building block for inclusive governance because it supports the provision of modern welfare services and establishes legal recognition systems and enhances the political involvement of citizens. The study examines digital identity system legal and governance aspects, specifically regarding their effects on disadvantaged population groups. Using comparative cases between Aadhaar systems in India and e-ID infrastructure in Estonia, the research adopts qualitative legal methods for evaluating policy structures and human rights elements, and system accessibility data. Research demonstrates that digital identity systems enhance service delivery efficiency and prevent denial of services; however, these benefits may be undermined if privacy, consent requirements, and user accessibility receive insufficient attention. Aadhaar has facilitated direct benefit transfers for millions of people; however, concerns have emerged regarding its exclusion of individuals whose biometric data failed to match or who possessed limited digital literacy. Estonia established its data protection laws along with rightsbased system components that protect the privacy of users. The paper argues that digital identity systems succeed when they are embedded within robust legal frameworks, developed through participatory design practices, and governed by policy frameworks founded on principles of equality. The paper concludes by proposing guidelines for developing identity governance systems that align with legal principles and embrace inclusivity, thereby contributing to global discourse on digital rights and public service accessibility.

Keywords: Digital identity, Inclusive governance, Aadhaar, Estonia e-ID, Digital rights

**Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation
(ICMRI-2025)**

OP 42

**A Study on the Impact of Virtual Reality Tourism in contrast with Real-Time
Tourism experience on Customer Satisfaction: Indian perspective**

Shristi Chamoli

Research Scholar, UIM, Uttarakhand University

Abstract: In the pixel-oriented world where one's imagination turns to reality, giving a 360-degree view of the environment, Virtual Reality (VR) is an emerging technology for Tourism. This study discusses the concept of Virtual reality in Indian Tourism. It thus aims to determine the difference between customer satisfaction levels derived from VR and Real-time tourism experiences among Indian citizens. Youngsters who have technology are at their fingertips. Whereas real-time tourism is one of the priorities. Inclination towards virtual reality and instant gratification has motivated this paper to find its base in analyzing the literature on VR technologies in tourism over the past 5 years. The study comprehends primary data and thus paves the direction to exhibit VR technology. Recommendations and limitations are discussed at the end of the paper.

Keywords: Virtual reality, Immersive experiences, Technological advancement, Decision making, User Satisfaction.

OP 43

Machine Learning-Based Prediction of Patellar Malalignment Using Radiographic Anatomical Indices in Patellofemoral Pain Disorders: A Comparative Study

Sandhya Nagolu

PhD Research Scholar/Assistant Professor

Department of Anatomy

Saveetha Medical College Hospital, SIMATS, Chennai

Abstract

Background: Patellofemoral pain syndrome (PFPS) is a prevalent musculoskeletal condition characterized by anterior knee pain and often associated with altered patellar alignment. Quantitative radiographic parameters, including the Q angle, sulcus angle, patellar tilt angle, and Insall–Salvati ratio, provide critical insights into patellar tracking abnormalities. However, conventional manual measurements may lack consistency and efficiency. Machine learning (ML) offers a promising approach to enhance diagnostic accuracy using radiographic data.

Objective: To develop and validate machine learning models for the prediction of patellofemoral malalignment in individuals with PFPS, based on radiographic anatomical indices obtained from digital imaging.

Methods: A comparative case-control study was conducted involving 220 participants (110 patients with PFPS and 110 matched controls) recruited from three clinical centres. Standardized AP, lateral, and skyline knee radiographs were acquired and analysed using INSTARISPACS imaging software to extract anatomical measurements. Data preprocessing included imputation, outlier removal, and z-score normalization. Three supervised ML models Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Decision Tree (DT) were trained and evaluated using a stratified 80/20 train-test split

and 5-fold cross-validation. Model performance was assessed using accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1-score, and AUC-ROC.

Results: The LR and SVM models achieved the highest accuracy (97.73%), while the DT model demonstrated slightly lower accuracy (95.45%) but superior interpretability. Feature-wise analysis revealed the Q angle as the most predictive parameter across all models, with the DT model showing the highest single-feature accuracy for Q angle (95.45%).

Conclusion: Machine learning models using radiographic indices can accurately classify patellofemoral malalignment in PFPS. For physiotherapy and orthopaedic care, these models provide a clinically viable and interpretable method to enhance early diagnosis and support radiographic screening.

Keywords: Patellofemoral pain syndrome, Q angle, radiographic measurement, machine learning, patellar malalignment, INSTARISPACS.

OP 44
**A Multi-Class Queuing Model for Handoff and CAC in Ultra-Dense 5G
Networks**
Sumit Pathak
Research Scholar
Department of Computer Science
Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Agra

Abstract: The present study provides a robust framework for managing limited radio resources in ultra-dense and high-mobility environments. This model addresses the critical challenge of ensuring uninterrupted service during handoffs by prioritizing ongoing (handoff) calls over newly initiated ones. Utilizing an M/M/N/N queuing structure, where both arrivals and service times follow exponential distributions and the system has a finite number of channels without buffering, the model evaluates system performance under varying traffic loads. It incorporates a CAC policy that intelligently admits or rejects calls based on current resource availability and predefined thresholds, such as reserved guard channels for handoff calls. The model captures key performance metrics including blocking probability for new calls, dropping probability for handoff calls, effective call throughput, and system utilization. By providing quantitative insights, this analytical framework supports the design and optimization of 5G handoff strategies, ensuring quality of service and efficient spectrum usage in next-generation wireless networks.

OP 45

The Mediating Role of Self-Efficacy in the Relationship between Social Support and Post-Traumatic GrowthDeeksha Gupta¹ and Prof. (Dr.) Ajir Bihari Chaubey²¹NET (Psychology), Ph.D. Scholar, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Agra (U.P.),
India²Professor and Head, Department of Psychology, S.R.K (P.G.) College, Firozabad (U.P.),
India

Abstract: Although the loss of a caregiver is a deeply distressing event, growing evidence suggests it can also initiate meaningful psychological development known as post-traumatic growth (PTG), which presents a critical opportunity to support resilience in bereaved individuals. This study investigated the role of self-efficacy as a mediator between perceived social support and PTG in individuals who have experienced caregiver loss. A sample of 150 participants completed measures of social support, self-efficacy, and PTG. Descriptive statistics indicated acceptable distributional properties for all variables. Mediation analysis revealed a significant indirect effect of social support on PTG through self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.268$, 95% CI [0.172, 0.369], $p < .001$), accounting for 41.5% of the total effect. The direct effect of social support on PTG remained significant ($\beta = 0.377$, $p < .001$), indicating partial mediation. Path estimates confirmed that social support significantly predicted self-efficacy ($\beta = 0.157$, $p < .001$), and self-efficacy strongly predicted PTG ($\beta = 1.711$, $p < .001$). These findings suggest that social support fosters a sense of self-efficacy, which in turn facilitates growth after caregiver loss. Enhancing both social and psychological resources may be critical in supporting individuals through bereavement-related trauma.

Keywords: Post-traumatic growth, Caregiver loss, Self-efficacy, Social support, Mediation analysis, Bereavement, Psychological resilience.

OP 46

Utility of MIC-1 as Supportive Marker to increase Diagnostic Accuracy in Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma**Bhagwat Kale¹, Sunita Girish², Anjali Waghmare³, Bhagyashree Yadav⁴ and Somnath Salgar⁵****¹Department of Biochemistry, Government Medical College and Cancer Hospital, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar****²D.Y.Patil Institute of Allied Health Sciences, Pune****³Department of Biochemistry, B.J. Government Medical College and Sassoon General Hospital, Pune****⁴Department of Biochemistry, Government Medical College and Hospital, Alibag****⁵Department of Biochemistry, B.J. Government Medical College and Sassoon General Hospital, Pune****Abstract:**

Background: CA 19.9 is the most validated diagnostic tumor marker used in clinical practice although it is less specific and sometime contributing to false negativity. Thus, to increase diagnostic accuracy in PDAC, there is need to find supporting markers which increases diagnostic performance along with CA19.9. This study is planned to find utility of MIC-1 to increase diagnostic performance along with CA19.9 in PDAC.

Methods: The study includes 35 clinically diagnosed and confirmed cases of PDAC along with 35 age and sex matched controls considered for comparison of results. The analysis of CA19.9 and MIC-1 was carried out by CLIA and ELISA respectively. Statistical analysis is done to sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of MIC-1 and CA19.9 in PDAC.

Results: In this study, we found CA 19.9 is more sensitive (Sensitivity 91.43 % vs 81.25 %) while MIC-1 is more specific. (Specificity 91.43 % vs 88.57 %). Accuracy of CA 19.9 and MIC-1 found 90 % and 86.57 % respectively.

Conclusions: MIC-1 can be used as supportive marker of CA 19.9, as it increases diagnostic accuracy in PDAC by nullifying low specificity and false negativity of CA 19.9.

Keywords: Macrophage Inhibitory Cytokine 1, Carbohydrate Antigen 19–9, Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma, sensitivity, Specificity, Accuracy etc.

OP 47

Harmful effect of burning crop residue and management approach to reduce stubble burning**Laxmi¹ and Dr. Brijesh Shivhare²**¹Research scholar Life sciences, Baba Mastnath University²Assistant professor Life sciences, Baba Mastnath University

Abstract: Agriculture is the primary mode of production. Punjab and Haryana grows a variety of crops each year, the most important of which are rice and wheat. Along with the desirable crop, a large amount of residue is created during harvesting, which is referred as stubble. And, because there is so little time between rice harvest and wheat sowing season, and vice versa, As a result, farmers frequently prefer the simple solution of burning the waste generated along with the harvested crop on the fields themselves. As a result, the technique is known as stubble burning. But it has a lot of harmful effects on soil like reduction of organic matter, decreasing fertility etc. as well for living beings by causing pollution to environment. It became necessary to control burning of crop residue. In this paper we will discuss about ways to use agriculture waste as wealth for example biochar and bedding material for animals, composting, stubble mulching, bio-oil production etc to reduce stubble burning and to make our soil more fertile and productive.

Keywords: stubble burning, stubble Mulching, composting

OP 48

Four Decades (1978-2017) of Agricultural Change: Rice and Minor Pulses in Karnataka Districts.**Kalpana M¹ and Stavelin Abhinandithe K²**¹Research Scholar, Division of medical statistics, JSS AHER, Mysuru²Associate Professor, Division of Medical Statistics, SLS, JSSAHER, Mysuru

Abstract: This study presents a comprehensive statistical analysis of agricultural crop data specifically rice and minor pulses across Karnataka. Encompassing three primary indicators area under cultivation (1000 ha), total production (1000 tons), and yield (kg/ha). The study systematically compiles data from official statistical sources across multiple districts of Karnataka, offering a long-term perspective on crop performance, land use dynamics, and productivity trends. The secondary data were collected from 1978 to 2017. Focusing on key variables such as area under cultivation, production, and yield, the study employs descriptive statistics to summarize trends and variability across districts. Time series plots are used to visualize long-term patterns using Years, Area, production, Yield for both Rice and Minor pulses. While compound annual growth rates (CAGR) and decadal growth rates quantify changes in production and yield over time. Inter-district comparisons highlight spatial disparities in agricultural performance, offering insights into regional strengths and challenges. The district-wise analysis reveals significant regional disparities. Some districts have achieved consistent improvements in yield due to favorable agro-climatic conditions and better infrastructure, while others lag due to fragmented landholdings, low technology adoption, or climate-related challenges. The analysis serves as a vital resource for policymakers, agronomists, and researchers aiming to understand the dynamics of crop productivity and design district-specific interventions for sustainable agricultural development in Karnataka.

Keywords: Rice, Minor pulses, Yield and production, Growth rate, Inter-district comparison.

OP 49

Decoding Chihna Rūpa (चिह्न रूप): A Vedic Framework for Understanding Self and Mapping Skills through Secondary Patterns**Mrs. Shraddha Prasad Kale****Researcher, Trainer and Mentor, Department of Art Therapy and Counselling,
ATH - Asha the Hope, Bangalore**

Abstract: In Vedic understanding, all visible form (*rūpa*) reflects an original subtle essence (*tanmātra*). This study proposes a symbolic framework termed **Chihna Rūpa (चिह्न रूप)** to understand “secondary patterns” repeated pre-writing strokes and visual themes like loops, zigzags, spirals, and circles as expressions of inner cognitive and emotional processing.

These patterns, often overlooked in early motor development, therapeutic drawing, or mandala and doodling, turn as psycho-somatic signatures of the individual. Understanding from Indic systems like:

- **Pañchakośa** (five-layer model of existence: physical, energetic, mental, intellectual, and blissful self),
- **Triguna theory** (*Sattva–Rajas–Tamas* as foundational qualities of mind),
- **Chakra-Nādi system** (energy centers and channels regulating inner flow), and
- **Symbolic geometry** (*Yantras* and *Rekhās* as representations of psychological and cosmic structure),

This study attends each pattern to their core skills like decision-making, emotional regulation, memory, and self-concept.

For example, loops indicate repetitive thought (*Chinta Vṛtti*), spirals reflect anxiety release or suppression (*Apāna Vayu* imbalance), while triangles and squares reveal self-identity and organisation (*Triguna, Vaastu*).

Quoting the Upanishadic insight: “तन्मात्राण्येव चिह्नानि” – *Tanmātrāṅyeva chihnāni*
the subtle elements reveal themselves through signs (chihnās).

This context opens a developmentally relevant, culturally rooted, and spiritually aligned methodology for using symbolic secondary patterns (*Upa-rekhāḥ*) in art therapy, academic design, and self-mapping. *Chihna Rūpa* becomes an analytical and expressive bridge between the seen and the unseen form and essence.

Keywords: Art therapy, *Chihna Rūpa*, Core Skills, Secondary patterns, *Upa-rekhāḥ*.

OP 50**Role and Impact of Crowdfunding in Gorakhpur's Entrepreneurial Ecosystem****Priti Yadav¹ and Dr. Anil Kumar Yadav²****¹Research Scholar, Department of Commerce****Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur****²Professor, Department of Commerce****Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur**

Abstract: This study investigates the new function and effects of crowdfunding in boosting Gorakhpur's entrepreneurial ecosystem, a developing economic center in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Crowdfunding is an inventive and inclusive financing option for startups, small businesses, and early-stage entrepreneurs in areas like Gorakhpur where access to conventional financing sources like banks, venture capital, and angel investors is still restricted.

The study emphasizes how different types of crowdfunding specifically, debt-based, reward-based, and donation-based models are progressively becoming more well-known among regional business owners. Without depending on traditional lending institutions, these models allow individuals to raise money from a wide range of people through online platforms. The study looks at the advantages of crowdfunding, such as quick access to funding, increased visibility, client approval, and community support. It also identifies the main obstacles, including low digital literacy, lack of awareness, restrictions imposed by regulations, and difficulties promoting campaigns.

Through secondary research from the body of existing literature, the paper sheds light on the potential and difficulties of crowdfunding implementation in the Gorakhpur area. According to the research, even though the adoption rate is still low, the region's successful campaigns have assisted startups in establishing credibility, interacting with early adopters, and quickly and affordably validating their business concepts.

According to the paper's conclusion, crowdfunding has the potential to be a potent instrument for financial inclusion and the expansion of local businesses in Gorakhpur with the right awareness campaigns, capacity-building projects, and institutional support. Promoting its usage can support the development of a more dynamic and independent startup culture in the area.

Keywords: Crowdfunding, Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, Startup Financing, Alternative Funding, Digital Platforms.

OP 51

**Forecasting Crude Death Rate Disparities Between Urban and Rural in
Karnataka Using ARIMA (1,1,1)****Ashin Krishna C¹ and Chaithra N^{2*}****¹Research Scholar, Division of Medical Statistics, School of Life Sciences, JSS Academy
of Higher Education and Research, Mysuru****²Associate Professor, Division of Medical Statistics, School of Life Sciences, JSS
Academy of Higher Education and Research, Mysuru****Abstract**

Background: In India, significant disparities exist between urban and rural Crude Death Rate (CDR) due to variations in healthcare access, socioeconomic conditions, and environmental factors. CDR serves as a fundamental demographic indicator, reflecting population health and healthcare system effectiveness. This study aimed to examine the trends and disparities in CDR between urban and rural regions of Karnataka from 2001 to 2016, and to develop a reliable time-series forecasting model using ARIMA (1,1,1) to predict future mortality patterns up to the year 2025.

Methods: Data were sourced from the Karnataka government's official website ejanma.karnataka.gov.in. Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize CDR trends, and the Average Annual Reduction Rate (AARR) was calculated. Time-series analysis was performed using the ARIMA model, with parameters selected via Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plots. Model validation included residual diagnostics (Ljung-Box test) and error metrics (Mean Absolute Percentage Error, Root Mean Square Error). The Statistical analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS 20.

Results: The analysis revealed a declining CDR trend in both urban (AARR: 0.29%) and rural (AARR: -1.7%) areas disparities. The ARIMA (1,1,1) model demonstrated good predictive performance, with urban CDR projected to slightly increase from 5.72

in 2016 to 5.82 in 2025, while rural CDR was forecasted to decrease significantly from 6.68 to 5.42 over the same period.

Conclusion: Persistent rural-urban CDR disparities in Karnataka necessitate targeted, region-specific public health interventions to improve mortality outcomes in underserved rural areas.

Keywords: Urban-Rural disparities, Crude Death Rate, ARIMA modelling, forecasting.

OP 52**Art Integrated Pedagogy in the Institute of Music and Fine Arts Jammu: A Study****Romy Kumar****Ph. D Research Scholar****PG Department of Education, University of Jammu, Jammu****Pin Code: 180006**

Abstract: National Education Policy 2020 gives a special focus on art education. It marks a significant paradigm shift by placing a strong emphasis on art education as an integral element of a holistic and multidisciplinary approach to learning. National Curriculum Frameworks of 1975, 1988, 2005, 2009 and 2023 put special attention on art education. Institute of Music and Fine Arts, Jammu is a four years bachelor degree course of visual art and performing art in Jammu. The objectives of the present study are: To understand the present infrastructural facilities available in the Institute of Music and Fine Arts, Jammu, To list art integrated learning activities performed by the students in the Institute of Music and Fine Arts, Jammu, To identify the pedagogy adopted by the teachers in the Institute of Music and Fine Arts, Jammu and To suggest remedial measures for successful implementation of art integrated learning in the Institute of Music and Fine Arts, Jammu. Data were taken by students (100) and teachers (20) from the Institute of Music and Fine Arts, Jammu. The investigator used self structured interview schedule and also used self structured questionnaire for students. The reliability and validity of the interview schedule and questionnaire were also established by the investigator. For the analysis of data, percentages analysis and content analysis were used. The results of the present study will help the teachers, administrators and stakeholders to take necessary steps to integrate art in the teaching learning process and make teaching learning process interactive, innovative and enjoyable.

Keywords: Art Integrated Pedagogy, Institute of Music and Fine Arts Jammu.

OP 53

**Pre-existing Statistical Predictive Models for Early Detection of Cancer: A
Comprehension review****Ankit Babu^{1*}, Sunil Kumar² and Alok Kumar Singh³**¹Research Scholar, Department of Statistics²Professor & Head, Department of Statistics³Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics

R. B. S. College, Agra, (UP) 282002

Abstract: Early detection of cancer significantly enhances treatment success and survival rates. A wide range of statistical and machine learning models have been developed to identify high-risk individuals and detect malignancies at early stages. This review provides a comprehensive overview of established predictive models, including logistic regression, Cox proportional hazards models, Bayesian networks, and machine learning techniques such as random forests, support vector machines, and deep neural networks. We examine each model's mathematical foundation, clinical applications, and predictive performance, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations. Common challenges—such as data heterogeneity, interpretability, and model generalizability—are also discussed. The review concludes with future directions aimed at improving model integration, transparency, and real-world clinical impact in cancer early detection.

Keywords: Predictive Models, Detection of Cancer, logistic Regression and Machine Learning.

OP 54

ब्लाक सफीपुर (जनपद उन्नाव) में जनसंख्या वृद्धि का कृषि भूमि उपयोग पर प्रभाव: एक भौगोलिक अध्ययन

* Dr. Anupama Singh and ²Pawan Kumar Rathaur

* ¹Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, D.A.V. College, Civil Lines, Kanpur

² Research Scholar, Department of Geography, D.A.V. College, Civil Lines, Kanpur

सारांश:

प्रस्तुत शोध पत्र उत्तर प्रदेश के जनपद उन्नाव के ब्लाक सफीपुर में जनसंख्या वृद्धि एवं कृषि भूमि उपयोग के बदलते स्वरूप के मध्य संबंधों का विश्लेषण करता है। बदलता भूमि उपयोग मानव की विकास यात्रा का परिचायक है, प्राचीन काल से लेकर वर्तमान समय में भूमि उपयोग में व्यापक बदलाव हुए हैं, आज भूमि पर अत्याधिक दबाव है अतः सतत विकास की आवश्यकता है। सफीपुर ब्लाक कृषि प्रधान क्षेत्र है, जनसंख्या वृद्धि का पारम्परिक कृषि प्रणालियों एवं भूमि उपयोग पर प्रभाव स्पष्ट दृष्टिगोचर होता है। जनसंख्या की मूलभूत आवश्यकता भोजन है और खाद्य आपूर्ति प्रत्यक्ष रूप से कृषि से जुड़ी है, जो सीधे तौर पर कृषि पर दबाव डालती है। 2011 से 2021 आंकड़ों का तुलनात्मक अध्ययन से स्पष्ट होता है कि जनसंख्या वृद्धि के साथ-साथ कृषि भूमि का संकुचन हुआ है एवं विविध उपयोग जैसे-आवास, परिवहन, उद्योग एवं संस्थागत क्षेत्रों की ओर रूपान्तरण बढ़ा है। अध्ययन में पाया गया विगत दशक में खेती के लिये उपयोग वाली शुद्ध बोया गया क्षेत्रफल में वृद्धि हुई एवं कृषि के अतिरिक्त उपयोग भूमि, वर्तमान परती, एक बार से अधिक बोया गया क्षेत्र, कृषि बंजर बेकार भूमि, अन्य परती भूमि, जैसे वर्गों में परिवर्तन देखने को मिला है। इसके अतिरिक्त उद्यान एवं झाड़ियों का क्षेत्रफल, वनक्षेत्र, उसर एवं कृषि आयोग्य भूमि, का क्षेत्रफल घटा है जो कि ग्रामीण आजीविका एवं पर्यावरणीय संतुलन के लिये घातक है। कृषि भूमि पर बढ़ता दबाव एवं बढ़ती जनसंख्या नई चुनौतियां पेश कर रही हैं। अध्ययन में मिश्रित पद्धति दृष्टिकोण का उपयोग किया गया है, किसानों से साक्षात्कार द्वारा गुणात्मक डेटा एवं सरकारी रिपोर्टों से मात्रात्मक डेटा प्राप्त किया गया है। अध्ययन से स्पष्ट होता है कि जनसंख्या वृद्धि का कृषि भूमि उपयोग पर गहरा प्रभाव पड़ा है, समय रहते जनसंख्या नियंत्रण एवं कृषि भूमि संरक्षण हेतु सुदृढ़ नीतियां बनाने की आवश्यकता है। यह अध्ययन-भूमि उपयोग गतिशीलता, शैक्षणिक विमर्श एवं सफीपुर ब्लाक के भूमि नियोजन, क्षेत्रीय विकास एवं पर्यावरण के उचित प्रबंधन के लिये एक सशक्त आधार प्रदान करता है।

मुख्य शब्द: स्थानीय विकास, पर्यावरण संतुलन, भूमि नियोजन, सफीपुर ब्लाक, जनपद उन्नाव आदि।

OP 55**Perception of Small and Marginal Farmers towards the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana: A Study of Kurukshetra District of Haryana****Nidhi Saini* Dr. Satish Kumar*******Research Scholar **Assistant Professor****Department of Social Work, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana, 136119**

Abstract: The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) was launched by the Government of India to provide comprehensive crop insurance coverage to farmers and reduce the financial risks associated with crop failure due to natural calamities. This study aims to examine the perception of small and marginal farmers regarding the implementation, accessibility, and challenges of the scheme in the Kurukshetra district of Haryana. Employing a descriptive research design, primary data were collected from 60 farmers through a structured interview schedule using purposive sampling. The findings reveal that while a majority of the respondents are aware of the scheme, there is limited understanding of its technical aspects, such as premium rates, claim procedures, coverage details, and enrollment formalities. Many farmers perceive the scheme as beneficial in principle, but express dissatisfaction with delayed compensation, complex documentation, lack of transparency, and inadequate awareness efforts at the grassroots level. Socio-economic factors such as landholding size, literacy level, access to extension services, and prior experiences with crop loss significantly influenced their perceptions. The study highlights the need for enhanced outreach through local institutions, simplified procedures, increased farmer training, and timely grievance redressal mechanisms to improve the effectiveness, utilization, and overall acceptance of PMFBY among small and marginal farmers. These insights can help policymakers refine crop insurance policies and ensure better risk protection for vulnerable farming communities.

Keywords: Farmers, dissatisfaction, awareness, grievance, insurance

Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation (ICMRI-2025)

OP 56

A Review on Metal Oxide Nanoparticles as Antimicrobial Agents**Roshni Kumari^{1*}****¹Department of Physics, School of Physical & Decision Science,
Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow-226025, Uttar Pradesh, India**

Abstract: The emerging microbial diseases are the global threat to the world. In order to stop these viral diseases we used some conventional anti-viral drugs. But in recent time conventional antiviral drugs are not so much effective on new viral disease because of antimicrobial resistant. Here nanomaterial plays an important role in providing metal oxides as antimicrobial agents to overcome the problem of antimicrobial resistance. The use of metal oxide nanomaterial as antimicrobials is due to their unique physiochemical properties, chemical stability, and high surface to volume ratio, durability, lower toxicity and low cost. This review summarizes the potential and mechanism of metal oxides nanoparticles as antimicrobial agents.

Keywords: Metal Oxides, Antimicrobial activity, Physiochemical properties

OP 57**An Analytical Study on ASHA Workers' Role in Maternal Health Services in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh****Namita Singh, Research Scholar, King George Medical University Lucknow****Guide: Prof. Dr. Anjoo Agarwal, Dept. of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, KGMU****Co Guide: Prof. Dr. Monika Agarwal, Dept. of Community Medicine, KGMU****&****Prof. Dr. Renu Singh, Dept. of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, KGMU****Abstract**

Background: Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHAs) serve as the frontline workforce of India's public health system, playing a crucial role in improving maternal health outcomes, especially in rural and underserved areas. This study aims to analytically examine the role of ASHA workers in delivering antenatal care services in the rural areas of district Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh.

Methods: A community based cross sectional approach used in four randomly selected villages under Chinhath CHC, District Lucknow. A total of 362 study participants who were contacted by ASHA during pregnancies were included. The data were collected through pre tested questionnaire. Data were analyzed using SPSS-24.0, IBM Corp., Chicago, USA. Differences between the groups were compared using the Chi-square test and Fisher's exact test. P value < 0.05 considered statistically significant. Key indicators analyzed include early ANC registration, number of antenatal check-ups, birth preparedness, and awareness of maternal danger signs.

Results: Out of 362 beneficiaries of ASHA workers regarding antenatal services, only 55.91% had contact with ASHA in first trimester and 42.74% were accompanied for first visit. Only 33.42% got advice on ANC from them, more than 50% women availed the benefits under Janani Suraksha Yojana.

Conclusion: This research highlights the indispensable role ASHA workers play in bridging the gap between the healthcare system and rural communities and offers recommendations for strengthening their impact on maternal health in Uttar Pradesh.

Keywords: ASHA worker, ANC

OP 58**Thoughts That Trap: The Role of Metacognitive Beliefs in Emotional Distress and Substance Use Among Indian Youth****Shreya Sharma¹ and Dr. Ganesh Bhardwaj²****^{1,2}Centre for Psychology and Human Behaviour, Shobhit Institute of Engineering & Technology Meerut, Uttar Pradesh – 250110**

Abstract: Substance use among Indian youth is frequently linked with unresolved emotional distress. This study explores how young adults with alcohol or nicotine dependence experience patterns of rumination and thought suppression- key psychological processes that may maintain this distress and reinforce dependence. Twenty participants (aged 18–32) were interviewed using a semi-structured guide, and data were analysed thematically. Participants reported repetitive, intrusive thoughts and a strong tendency to use substances to silence or escape these thoughts. Common expressions included “I drink to stop thinking” and “smoking helps me escape my mind.” These thought patterns were found to reinforce negative emotional states and sustain substance-seeking behaviour. Findings suggest that rumination and suppression play a significant role in the addiction cycle, and targeting these cognitive processes may offer a promising direction for early psychological intervention.

Keywords: Rumination, Thought Suppression, Substance Use, Emotional Distress

OP 59**Title: To Determine Seroprevalence Rates Among Different ABO/Rh Group****Vivek Kumar¹ and Dr Pandeep kaur^{2*}****PhD Scholar¹, Associated Professor²****¹Department of Blood Transfusion, Nims College of Allied and Health Care Sciences,
Department Of Immune Hematology & Blood Transfusion,
Nims University Jaipur Rajasthan**

Abstract: Blood transfusion, while life-saving, carries the inherent risk of transmitting infections collectively known as Transfusion-Transmissible Infections (TTIs). This study aimed to determine the seroprevalence rates of TTIs including Hepatitis B Virus (HBV), Hepatitis C Virus (HCV), Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Syphilis, and Malaria—among blood donors of various ABO and Rh blood groups at the NIMS Hospital Blood Centre between November 2024 and January 2025.

A total of 950 blood donor samples were screened using standard serological testing protocols. Out of these, 39 donors (4.1%) were reactive for at least one TTI. Among the infected, all were male donors, with ages ranging from 18 to 61 years, predominantly within the 20–40-year age bracket. Replacement donors accounted for 89.7% of the reactive cases, while voluntary donors represented only 10.3%, emphasizing a significantly higher risk associated with replacement donations.

The seroprevalence of individual infections was as follows: HBV (35.9%), Syphilis (30.8%), HCV (20.5%), HIV (17.9%), and Malaria (0%). Some donors exhibited co-infections, notably with HIV and Syphilis or HCV and HIV. Blood group analysis revealed that B Rh(D) Positive (41%) and O Rh(D) Positive (25.6%) groups had the highest number of reactive cases, followed by A Rh(D) Positive.

This study highlights the ongoing public health concern posed by TTIs in the blood donation pool. The findings underscore the need for enhanced pre-donation screening, increased awareness campaigns, and a stronger emphasis on voluntary blood donation. Additionally, the introduction of advanced testing methods such as Nucleic Acid Testing (NAT) can significantly reduce the risk of TTIs during the window period. Promoting a culture of regular, voluntary, and low-risk donations is crucial for ensuring a safe and reliable blood supply.

Keywords: Seroprevalence, Blood donors, ABO/Rh blood group, Transfusion-Transmissible Infections, Hepatitis B, Voluntary donation, Blood safety.

OP 60**Assessment of Carbon Sequestration to describe the conservation potential of a sacred groves from Ratnagiri District, Maharashtra India
Gayatri Oak, Dr. Bharat Bhushan Sharma**

Abstract: Sacred groves are widely recognized for their contributions to gene pool preservation and biodiversity conservation. Their capacity to provide crucial ecological services particularly carbon sequestration should also be considered in the context of small, traditionally protected forest patches. This study evaluates the carbon sequestration potential of sacred groves in Ratnagiri District, Maharashtra, through tree stock assessments conducted via field surveys. Despite their small size, these groves show considerable carbon storage, reinforcing their ecological significance. By highlighting the sequestration value of small sacred groves, the research shows the necessity to explore small sacred groves for their carbon sequestration potential. The paper suggests sustainable conservation strategies that integrate carbon management with cultural and ecological stewardship, and calls for policy interventions that align conservation efforts with community welfare.

OP 61

Organic Manure Efficacy in System of Wheat Intensification**Anu Nawhal^{1*}, Shikha Singh², Ishan Amitayush³ and Murari Mohan⁴****Department of Agronomy, Naini Agricultural Institute, Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh- 211007**

Abstract: The demand for major cereals, particularly wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), has increased globally, resulting in intensive farming, an over-reliance on chemical inputs, a loss in grain quality, a decline in soil health, and environmental damage. As a result, using sustainable agricultural practices that enhance soil health and production is essential. Organic manures have been a sustainable and efficient source of nutrients for increasing soil fertility and yielding high-quality agricultural products since the *Vedic* era. In order to investigate the "Organic Manure Efficacy in System of Wheat Intensification," two years of field experiments were conducted at SHUATS Model of Organic Farm (SMOF) SHUATS, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India, during *Rabi*, 2022–23, and 2023–24. The experiment was set up in a split-plot design with two factors, each of which had four levels: liquid organic formulations (no spray, 3% Panchagavya, 10% Jeevamrutha, and 2% cow urine) and solid organic manures (farmyard manure, farmyard manure followed by straw mulching, neem cake manure, and neem cake manure followed by straw mulching). The DBW-187 (Karan Vandana) variety of wheat was cultivated under complete system of wheat intensification practice. Due to more total (198.96/m²) and effective tillers (158.96/m²), dry weight per hill (31.08 gm), grains per spike (48.38), and 1000-seed weight (47.55 gm) in the pooled data, neem cake manure (5 t/ha) produced the highest grain (29.50 q/ha) and straw (36.51 q/ha) yield among the various solid organic manures. These yields were 38.4 and 16.3% higher than farmyard manure (control). The highest grain yield (29.62 q/ha) was also obtained from a fortnightly foliar spray of 10% Jeevamrutha until 90 days after sowing. This was 47.9% higher than the yield from no spray (control) due to the maximum total

(205.00/m²) and effective tillers (157.71/m²), dry weight per hill (30.80 gm), grains per spike (48.43), and 1000-seed weight (46.75 gm). The interaction of neem cake manure with 10% Jeevamrutha produced 118.3 and 43.9% higher grain (38.64 q/ha) and straw yield (42.03 q/ha) over interaction of farmyard manure with no spray (control), this due to the formation of more total (222.5/m²) and effective tillers (175.00/m²), dry weight per hill (35.32 gm), and grains per spike (53.87), Accordingly, the results of the study indicated that the highest levels of wheat growth and production were achieved by applying neem cake manure as basal and a 10% Jeevamrutha foliar spray.

Keywords: Foliar spray, Jeevamrutha, Neem cake manure, System Wheat Intensification, Yield

OP 62**AI and Financial Inclusion: Opportunities and Challenges” (With special reference to Gorakhpur)****Ms Chanchal Yadav****Research Scholar, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University**

Abstract: Financial inclusion is essential for comprehensive economic progress, particularly in regions where traditional financial institutions services are inadequate. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has come to light as a transformative force in the financial sector, offering creative approaches to bring marginalized populations into the financial fold. This paper evaluates the opportunities and challenges of AI-driven financial inclusion with a special focus on the Gorakhpur region in eastern Uttar Pradesh, India.

Gorakhpur, a city with a mix of urban and rural populations, faces unique challenges in availability of financial resources such as limited banking infrastructure, lower technological literacy, and dependency on informal finance. With the help of AI-driven technologies like chatbots, digital credit scoring models using alternative data, and real-time fraud prevention mechanisms, financial institutions can enhance availability to a great extent, affordability, and security of financial services. In Gorakhpur, growing digital financial platforms and digital banks have started leveraging Artificial intelligence for tailored financial offerings, digital KYC, and micro-credit services focusing on marginal farmers, local traders, and the urban economically weaker sections

Despite its potential, the use of AI in financial inclusion also poses serious challenges. These include data privacy concerns, inadequate digital awareness, inherent algorithmic biases, and insufficient technological infrastructure in rural areas, and trust deficits in digital automation platforms. The qualitative methodology adopted in this research includes literature review, analysis of region-specific financial patterns, and case-based

insights from Gorakhpur's regional banking ecosystem and technology-driven programs.

The findings suggest that while AI offers substantial opportunities for financial inclusion in Gorakhpur, its implementation must be supported by strong policy frameworks, capacity building, and public-private collaborations. Suggested actions include the development of AI training programs, inclusive design of AI tools, better mobile and Internet access facilities in rural communities, and ethical regulations to address bias and privacy. This study presents important insights for policymakers, banks, financial technology companies, and development organizations promoting digital advancement and inclusive finance.

Keywords: Financial inclusion, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Technological literacy, Micro-credit.

OP 63**A Study of challenges and opportunities of Quick Commerce in India with special reference to Uttar Pradesh Region****Ms. Praveen Yadav****Research Scholar Department of Business Administration Deen Dayal Upadhyaya
Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur**

Abstract: This study highlights the challenges & Opportunities of Quick Commerce in India. Quick commerce (Q-commerce) has emerged as a transformative force in Uttar Pradesh's retail landscape, driven by the region's rapid urbanization, increasing smartphone penetration, and growing demand for instant delivery services. This study examines the challenges and opportunities of Q-commerce in Uttar Pradesh, focusing on its operational, economic, and social implications. Key opportunities include enhanced consumer convenience, employment generation in the gig economy, and technological innovation through AI-driven logistics and inventory management. However, challenges such as logistical complexities in navigating traffic-congested urban areas, high operational costs of maintaining dark stores, and limited digital penetration in semi-urban and rural areas pose significant hurdles. Regulatory uncertainties and environmental concerns, including carbon emissions from frequent deliveries, further complicate sustainable growth. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining stakeholder interviews, consumer surveys, and market analysis to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Q-commerce ecosystem in Uttar Pradesh. Findings suggest that strategic partnerships with local retailers, investment in scalable logistics, and robust regulatory frameworks are critical for balancing growth and sustainability. This research offers actionable insights for Q-commerce stakeholders aiming to capitalize on Uttar Pradesh's dynamic market while addressing its unique challenges.

Keywords: Quick Commerce, AI -Driven, Gig Economy, Digital Penetration .

OP 64**Correlation between Toxic Perfectionism and Assertiveness among Adults****Priyanka Mulani****Research Scholar, Department of Psychology****Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Udaipur**

Abstract: This report investigates the relationship between toxic perfectionism and assertiveness in adults from Jaipur, Rajasthan, using the Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale (MPS) and the Rathus Assertiveness Schedule (RAS). Toxic perfectionism, particularly socially prescribed perfectionism, involves excessive self-criticism and perceived external expectations, potentially inhibiting assertive behavior, which entails expressing one's needs confidently and respectfully. A correlational design tested the hypothesis that higher socially prescribed perfectionism correlates with lower assertiveness. Results confirmed a significant negative correlation between socially prescribed perfectionism and assertiveness, suggesting that fear of external judgment may hinder assertive behaviors. Implications for psychological interventions and future research are discussed.

OP 65**Grief or Gaze: Distinguishing Therapeutic Grief from Performative Mourning
on Social Media Heena Tiwari****Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Udaipur**

Abstract: In today's digital society, grief has migrated from private rituals to public platforms. Individuals now express their sorrow through curated posts, hashtags, and temporary stories, blurring the line between authentic emotional healing and social display. This paper investigates the growing distinction between therapeutic grief, which facilitates emotional processing, and performative mourning, driven by social visibility, likes, and engagement.

Using a qualitative thematic analysis of interviews and digital content, this study explores how grief is expressed online, what motivates such sharing, and how different modes of digital mourning affect emotional well-being. Data were gathered from 30 individuals who had publicly shared grief online in the past 6 months. A "Grief Expression Analysis Grid" was developed to examine post content, tone, emotional depth, and user interaction. Findings reveal that therapeutic grief leads to emotional support and community validation, while performative mourning is more often associated with metrics-driven behavior, emotional exhaustion, and shallow feedback. The study calls for greater awareness among mental health professionals to evaluate how clients mourn in digital spaces and proposes a framework for distinguishing between healthy and performative grieving behaviors.

Keywords: Online grief, therapeutic mourning, performative mourning, digital bereavement, social media psychology.

OP 66**Evaluation of antimicrobial utilization using ATC/DDD method among adult hospitalized patients****Ankur¹, Prem Kapur², Neetu Shree³, Rajiv Chhabra⁴, Kiran Dubey¹****¹Department of Pharmacology, School of Pharmaceutical Education & Research, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi****²Department of Medicine, Hamdard Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi****³Department of Microbiology, Hamdard institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi****⁴Department of Paediatrics, Artemis Hospitals, Gurugram**

Background: Antimicrobial resistance is a rising global concern due to irrational use. The huge burden of infectious diseases and overburden health care facilities makes the situation more complex. According to latest study published in the lancet, more than one million people have died from antimicrobial resistance between 1990 and 2021. It is essential to evaluate the antimicrobial use in the hospital setting to understand the gap and to promote rational use of antimicrobials.

Aim: To assess antimicrobial use in Hakeem Abdul Hameed Centenary Hospital, New Delhi with the help of ATC (Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification System)/DDD (Defined Daily Dose) method by WHO (World Health Organization).

Methods: A prospective observational study on antimicrobial use was done among 237 inpatients of age 18 years and above who were prescribed with an antimicrobial agent.

Result: Use of cefuroxime (6.3), ceftriaxone (4.8) from cephalosporin class were higher than the WHO standard value which indicate the excess use of these two antimicrobials. DDD/1000 patients/day of one of the aminoglycosides named amikacin was 1.9 which is above the WHO standard value (1). In addition, DDD of azithromycin (3.9) &

clarithromycin (3.6) from macrolides, IV Metronidazole (2.8) from imidazole class, amikacin (1.9) from aminoglycosides were more than the WHO standard value.

Conclusions: The study provided the key areas of improvement on antimicrobial use. The study suggested that strongly adherence to the standard treatment guidelines is required to strengthen the antimicrobial stewardship program, and to prevent the antimicrobial resistance.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, ATC/DDD, WHO

OP 67

**An Analysis of Budgetary Provisions for Environmental Protection: A
Comparative Analysis of India and China****Shruti Gupta¹ and Prof. Alok Kumar Goyal^{2*}**¹Research Scholar, Department of Economics, DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur²Professor, Department of Economics, DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur

Abstract: Environmental degradation and climate change have forced emerging economies to integrate sustainability into their fiscal policies. India and China—two of the world's most populated and fastest-growing nations—have adopted distinct budgetary provisions for environmental protection, especially over the past decade. This study presents a comparative analysis of the environmental budgetary allocations in India and China from 2014 to 2024, with a focus on budgetary expenditure trends, sectoral priorities, and institutional mechanisms.

Drawing on official budget documents, ministry-level data, and international environmental databases, the research evaluates spending in key areas such as pollution control, renewable energy investment and climate adaptation. It contrasts the centralized model of China with India's federal fiscal structure, highlighting how government frameworks influence environmental spending patterns.

The study also assesses the alignment of budgetary allocations with national policy measures and international commitments, such as the Paris Agreement. By analyzing fiscal tools, the paper offers critical insights into the effectiveness and sufficiency of budgetary efforts in tackling environmental challenges. The findings contribute to the broader understanding of how developing economies balance environmental sustainability with economic development through public finance.

Keywords: Budgetary Allocations, Renewable Energy Investment, Climate Change, Sustainability.

OP 68**Stability Analysis of Leslie-Gower Predator-Prey model with prey harvesting****D.V.Saradhi¹ and PapaRao A.V²****Department of S&H Aditya College of Engineering & Technology(A),
Surampalem, Andhra Pradesh****Department of Mathematics JNTU - GV College Of Engineering,
Vizianagaram(A), Andhra Pradesh**

Abstract: In this paper we studied the stability Analysis of Leslie-Gower Predator-Prey model with prey harvesting. We studied the boundedness and non negative properties of the model. The model exhibits four equilibrium points. The local stability analysis at each equilibrium points is studied. The global existence of the model is analyzed by choosing a suitable Lyapunov function, Numerical simulation is carried out to support analytical results.

And also we introduced delay for the prey species in the above system of equations and checked all above conditions like boundedness, non negative properties, equilibrium points, local stability and global stability is analyzed by suitable Lyapunov function, Numerical simulation is carried out to support analytical results.

Keywords: Prey-predator, local stability, Global stability, Numerical simulation, Delay, Lyapunov function

AMS classifications: 34DX

OP 69**Invisible Strain: Gendered Dimensions of Work-Life Balance and Occupational Stress in Chikmagalur's Informal Economy****Mandara SM****Research Scholar, Department of Management Studies
Shri Venkateshwara University**

Abstract: This paper investigates the gendered dimensions of work-life balance and occupational stress among workers in Chikmagalur's informal economy, a critical yet understudied sector in Karnataka, India. Drawing on survey data from 501 respondents across five sectors (Constructions, Agriculture, Textiles, Hotels, and Department Stores) the study reveals significant gender disparities. Women report a polarized experience, with higher instances of both "completely balanced" and "not balanced" work-life balance compared to men, likely due to the dual burden of paid work and unpaid household responsibilities. Similarly, while both genders experience high occupational stress, women are more likely to report persistent stress, reflecting the "invisible strain" of societal expectations. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions, such as flexible work arrangements and childcare support, to promote gender equality and enhance well-being in the informal economy.

Keywords: Gender disparities, unorganized sector, Chikmagalur, Women workers

OP 70**Iranians Dispersion across Borders in Three ways: by Generation, Religion, and Class.****Syed Insha Batool****Research Scholar, Department of English
Nims University Jaipur Rajasthan**

Abstract: International social fields that radiate from the affluent neighborhoods of north Tehran into the impoverished neighborhoods of Kensington in London, West Vancouver, or St Ives in Sydney are created when classes in the diaspora replicate their home country relationships. This helps to reproduce both expected and real ties to Iran. The research conducted shows that, in along with national recognition, relationships by category or socioeconomic standing, religion, subsequent ones, and residence time may be utilized as well as glasses to comprehend transnational audiences. Each of these types of group identity has produced unique global social contexts that overlap. This research questions dominant international discourses that overemphasize a national viewpoint, often masking the many other determinants of belonging. Even though researchers continue to treat national migrant communities as homogeneous units, this approach often depicts migrant groups as cohesive and evenly distributed units, ignoring significant internal diversity. Generations of transnational studies initially focused on the unrestricted movement of people, goods, and ideas across national borders. However, more recent research highlights that transformative connections can be shaped by more localized or regionally nested networks that go beyond national boundaries; they don't necessarily need to rely on constant cross-border movement. In accordance the empirical research that ensues, the specific rhythms of vehicle, music, and shopping production and consumption within the Iranian community function to simultaneously encompass and exclude people as well as provide distinct societal relationship the reliability and genuineness. Children of Iranian migrants might attempt

to replicate the disparities that distinguish their birthplace via local social relationships. The reality that such discourses captivate the federal government national boundaries does not diminish their significance or eliminate them entirely from the essential structure of a worldwide discourse; alternatively, it indicates that they ought to be solely and specifically linked to discourses. The local account ties are exactly what define any location as a home. The majority of people nevertheless do not have limitations to a single location. In fact, ancestral and contemporary ties can frequently be affected by an individual's individual and historical links to additional locations.

Keywords: Class, second generation, Religious Identity, Transnationalism, Iran, Iranian Migrants

OP 71

Integration of Cloud Storage and Cloud Servers in Modern Library Management**Prof. K. L. Mahawar* and KM Rinki*******Professor & Head, Department of Library and Information Science, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Vidya Vihar, Rae Bareli Road, Lucknow-226025******Research Scholar and Author of the Correspondence, Department of Library and Information Science, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Vidya Vihar, Rae-Bareli Road, Lucknow-226025**

Abstract: The largest libraries found in ancient Indian universities such as Nalanda, Takshila, and Vikramshila were built in and they were operated effectively. This system opens up a huge storage capacity. At that time, the development of virtual technology was not visible, but in the library, a huge library divided into various sections on a large scale was necessary. In the present form, such a huge library does not exist, but the library is making proper use of cloud storage devices for proper storage of data and management of its access time. Cloud storage system is a systematic and comprehensive solution to make storage. Being present in the library is more useful to maintain the existence of readers. It is easy to use. Cloud server centers have been created at various places where the storage system runs smoothly.

The study will focus on areas such as Cloud computing technology in library management, library storage system, library management level, Cloud storage in library management, Benefits of cloud storage in the library, cloud storage platform, library cloud storage architecture, and Major Cloud Provider Servers.

OP 72

**The Impact of Trauma on Adolescence: A Critical Analysis of Shashi
Deshpande's Short Stories****Shilpa Vilas Rathod¹ and Dr. Chhaya Ramesh Dapke²**¹Research Scholar,**Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University
Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, Subcentre Dharashiv, MS India**²Professor and Research Guide

Department of English

R.P. College Dharashiv, MS India

Abstract: This article explores the impact of trauma on adolescence in Shashi Deshpande's short stories. Through a critical discourse analysis of selected stories, this study examines how trauma shapes the adolescent experience, influencing identity formation, relationships, and worldviews. The analysis reveals that Deshpande's stories portray adolescence as a vulnerable and formative period, where traumatic experiences can have lasting effects on individuals. Deshpande's success lies on her presentation of the real-life experience. She realistically depicts of inner conflict of her protagonist's mind. Deshpande is trying to shake the readers out of their satisfaction by thrusting in their face the double stranded being practice in a patriarchal social setup. Shashi Deshpande has made bold attempts at giving a voice to the disappointments and frustrations of women despite her passionate rejection of being a activist. A look at her adolescence will reveal her treatment of major adolescence characters and will show how the themes in them are related to adolescence's problems. Deshpande's women characters also signify the changing time weighted change in their private lives. It has been significantly pointed out that marital tension and adjustment problem of a woman within marriage is one of the notable features in Deshpande's novels

Keywords: Trauma, adolescence, Shashi Deshpande, short stories, identity formation, psychological impact.

OP 73

QSAR and LASSO-Based Discovery of Anticancer Flavonoid CompoundsAdarsh Tripathi¹¹Department of Statistics, University of Lucknow, 226007 (Hasanganj, Lucknow, UP

Abstract: A computational QSAR (Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship) modeling approach was employed to identify flavonoid derivatives with potential anticancer activity against A375 melanoma cells. The model was developed using LASSO (Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator) regression, demonstrating high predictive accuracy on training data and moderate reliability under cross-validation, with minimal evidence of overfitting.

Feature stability analysis highlighted five key molecular descriptors lipophilicity (LogP), polarity (TPSA), molecular flexibility (Rotatable Bonds), hydrogen bond donors, and aromatic ring count as critical contributors to anticancer activity. These findings align with established pharmacokinetic principles, where moderate lipophilicity and low polarity often enhance cell permeability and biological response. Descriptors with low relevance, such as molecular weight, were excluded to maintain model simplicity and interpretability. Graphical validation supported the model's robustness, although occasional outliers suggested opportunities for further refinement. Flavonoid compounds characterized by balanced lipophilicity and reduced polar surface area were identified as promising candidates for synthesis and biological evaluation. This work outlines a predictive and interpretable cheminformatics strategy for anticancer compound screening. Future efforts may include experimental validation and the integration of nonlinear machine learning algorithms to better capture complex structure activity relationships.

Keywords: Flavonoid, QSAR, Anticancer, Melanoma, A375, LASSO regression, Drug discovery

OP 74**Title: Machine Learning Approaches to Nanophotonic Waveguide Analysis****Ms. Sakshi****Research Scholar****SGT University, Gurugram**

Abstract: Nanophotonic waveguides are essential components in miniaturized photonic devices, enabling the confinement and control of light on the nanoscale. These structures are widely used in optical communication, sensing, and quantum photonics due to their high efficiency, compact size, and tunable optical properties. However, the analysis and design of nanophotonic waveguides are computationally intensive, especially when using traditional numerical methods like Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) or Finite Element Method (FEM). These techniques require significant time and resources, particularly for large design spaces or multi-parameter optimizations.

Machine learning (ML) has recently emerged as a powerful alternative to conventional simulation approaches in nanophotonics. By learning from large datasets of simulated or experimental data, ML models can accurately predict waveguide properties such as effective index, mode distribution, and transmission efficiency. Supervised learning algorithms, such as neural networks and decision trees, have been successfully applied for forward modeling and property prediction. Inverse design problems where desired optical outputs are used to find optimal geometries have also benefited from deep learning and generative models.

In addition, unsupervised learning and dimensionality reduction techniques help identify hidden patterns and reduce complexity in high-dimensional datasets. More advanced strategies, such as physics-informed neural networks (PINNs), incorporate

physical laws into the training process, improving accuracy and reliability while requiring less data.

Overall, machine learning approaches not only speed up waveguide analysis but also enable the discovery of novel designs that may be difficult to achieve using traditional methods. As research progresses, the integration of ML with photonic design tools is expected to greatly enhance the development of efficient, high-performance nanophotonic devices.

OP 75**Molecular Signals of Diabetic Foot Ulcers: Quantification of Tumor necrosis factor- α , Interleukin-6 and High Sensitivity C - reactive protein in Different Grades of Diabetic foot ulcer****Dr. Shaheen B Shaikh****Ph.D Scholar, Department of Biochemistry
Yenepoya Medical College, Mangalore, Karnataka**

Abstract: Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) are a serious complication of diabetes mellitus, leading to significant morbidity, increased risk of amputation. Determination of the impact of inflammation on ulcer development, progression and healing is essential. Understanding the molecular and inflammatory factors associated with DFU grades is crucial for effective management and prevention of complications. This study aimed to determine the serum levels of Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), Interleukin 6 (IL-6), and high Sensitivity C-Reactive Protein (hs-CRP) levels and in Diabetes Foot ulcer, and to correlate them with severity in different grades of DFU .Methods: Under aseptic precautions 5 ml of venous blood was collected from 125 samples of diabetic patients with DFUs of varying grades and 125 diabetes patients without foot ulcer after obtaining due consent and ethical committee clearance. Serum levels of TNF- α , hs-CRP and IL-6 were determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Results: Serum levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and hs-CRP were significantly higher in diabetic patients with foot ulcers compared to diabetic patients without ulcers ($P < 0.001$). Furthermore, these inflammatory markers showed a progressive increase with higher Wagner grades of DFUs. A strong positive correlation was observed between the severity of the ulcer (as per Wagner classification) and the levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and hs-CRP ($P = 0.001$), indicating that inflammation intensifies with ulcer progression. Conclusion: Patients with diabetic foot ulcers have significantly elevated serum levels of TNF- α , IL-6, and hs-CRP compared to diabetic patients without ulcers. These levels increase with the severity of the ulcer, suggesting their potential role as biomarkers for ulcer progression.

Monitoring these inflammatory markers may aid in early detection, assessment of severity, and development of targeted therapies to improve outcomes in DFU patients.

Keywords: Diabetic foot ulcers, ELISA, IL-6, TNF- α , hs-CRP, Wagner classification.

OP 76

**Pharmacogenetic Testing: A Foreign Concept? Exploring perception of
Pharmacogenetic testing among Hypertensive Patients in Sikkim
Archana Adhikari¹, Dr. Chandrakala Sharma², Dr. Mingma Lhamu Sherpa³,
Dr. Mona Dhakal⁴, Dr. Gauthaman Karunakaran⁵**

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Pharmacology, Sikkim Manipal Institute of Medical Sciences, 5th
Mile Tadong, Sikkim

⁵Sikkim Government Pharmacy College, Sajong, Rumtek, Sikkim

Abstract: Pharmacogenetics is a novel concept which explains the role of genetics in variation of drug response among patients. A tool known as pharmacogenetic testing is gaining a lot of attention, as it provides genetic data which can be used by the physicians to determine the drug of choice for a patient based on their genetic profile. While the clinical advantages of Pharmacogenetic testing is recognised globally, India remains in infancy in its implementation in routine medical practice and clinical trials. Several challenges limit this widespread implementation, with lack of awareness among both the healthcare providers and patient being one of the barriers. Given these challenges, this study aims to assess the perception of pharmacogenetic testing to identify current knowledge gap and potential barriers to implementation among the hypertensive patients of Sikkim and create awareness by giving basic information about its potential benefits and its purpose.

Keyword: Pharmacogenetic testing, Hypertension.

OP 77

Effect of Meta Emotions on Psychological Well-Being and Self-Esteem among Women with PCOS

Nishu Chandna*, Seema Rani Sarraf*, Shahzadi Malhotra**

*AIBAS Amity University, UP Lucknow

**IHBAS, Delhi

Abstract

Introduction: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a multifaceted endocrine condition that significantly affects women's physical and mental health. Along with hormonal imbalances and reproductive challenges, women with PCOS often experience emotional distress, body image issues, and reduced self-worth. Meta-emotions are emotions about one's own emotional responses that may play a key role in shaping their psychological well-being and self-esteem.

Objective: This study aims to investigate the effect of meta emotions on psychological well-being and self-esteem among women diagnosed with PCOS.

Sample: A purposive sample of 200 women aged 20–40 years was selected from the Delhi NCR region. The study followed an ex-post facto mixed-method design.

Tools: Positive and negative meta emotions were assessed using the Meta Emotion Scale (Mitmansgruber, 2009). Self-esteem was measured using Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale, and psychological well-being was assessed through Ryff's Scale of Psychological Well-Being. Participants were categorized based on their meta-emotion profiles.

Statistical Analysis: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to examine group differences in self-esteem and psychological well-being, followed by correlation analysis to explore the interrelationships among variables. Results will be discussed to highlight the significance of emotional self-awareness in designing interventions that enhance mental health outcomes for women with PCOS.

OP 78

Effect of Social media Addiction on Mindfulness among young adults**Ismita Gupta*, Seema Rani Sarraf*, Pooja Mahour*******AIBAS Amity University, UP Lucknow******Department of Psychiatry, KGMU Lucknow****Abstract**

Introduction: The use of social media platforms has increased dramatically over the last ten years. Nearly 73% of adult internet users are active on at least one social media platform, according to data, and 42% use several platforms, including Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Twitter, and others (Duggan & Smith 2014). The growing engagement of young adults with social media platforms has raised concerns about its psychological impact, particularly on mindfulness—a key trait involving present-moment awareness and attentiveness.

Objective: This study investigates the effect of social media addiction on level of mindfulness among young adults in Indian context.

Sample: Using purposive sampling method 200 participants were selected aged 18–25 years. The sample was collected from the college of Lucknow city. The research design utilised in the study was ex-post facto design.

Tool: Social media addiction was measured using the *Indian Social Media Addiction Scale* developed by Dr. Natasha Saquib and Dr. Faseeh Amein Beigh (2023), while mindfulness was assessed using the *Indian Mindfulness Inventory* by Dr. Anoop Peter (2019). Based on their social media addiction scores, participants were categorized into two groups: low and high social media addiction levels.

Statistical Analysis: A one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to compare mean mindfulness scores across the two groups. Results will be shown in the

light of further studies to explore underlying mechanisms and guide interventions aimed at promoting mindful technology use among young adults.

OP 79

Bio - Synthesis of rGO/ZnO Nanocomposites for Supercapacitor Electrode**Vinay Rawat, Pankaj Chamoli*****^aSchool of Basic & Applied Sciences, Department of Physics, Shri Guru Ram Rai University, Dehradun-248001, Uttarakhand, India**

Abstract: This study exhibits the reduction of graphene oxide (GO) to reduced graphene oxide (rGO) nanosheets utilizing Bio extract as a green reducing agent in a wet chemical process at low temperature. The extract's high phenolic content and strong antioxidant effects make it a viable and environmentally acceptable alternative to dangerous chemicals. The similar process was used to successfully produce ZnO/rGO nanocomposites (NCs). The produced rGO and ZnO/rGO NCs were investigated with X-ray diffraction (XRD), Raman spectroscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-visible spectroscopy, and field emission scanning electron microscopy (SEM-EDX). Raman and EDX tests confirm a considerable reduction in oxygen-containing functional groups in GO to produce rGO. Furthermore, the produced rGO and ZnO/rGO NCs served as electrode materials for symmetrical supercapacitors (SSCs). The electrochemical performance was good, with a high specific capacitance.

Keywords: Graphene, supercapacitor, electrode, specific capacitance, power density, energy density

OP 80

Synthesis, Characterization, and Bioactivity Assessment of Ruthenium–Arene Schiff Base Half-Sandwich Complexes through Molecular Docking and DFT Approaches

Swaila Bano, Farha Arshi, and Ashok K. Singh*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science

University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226007, India

Abstract: Ruthenium complexes are gaining attention for their promising roles as chemotherapeutic and antimicrobial agents. In this study, three half sandwich organoruthenium(II) complexes, $[(\eta^6\text{-p-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{L}1)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ [M1], $[(\eta^6\text{-p-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{L}2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ [M2], and $[(\eta^6\text{-p-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{L}3)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ [M3], have been synthesized by reacting $[(\eta^6\text{-p-cymene})\text{RuCl}]_2(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ with Schiff base ligands namely N-(Salicylidene)-4-toluidine (L1), N-(Salicylidene)-4 aminobenzoic acid (L2), and N-(Salicylidene)-2-hydroxyaniline (L3). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, UV–Vis., FTIR, multinuclear NMR and ESI-MS spectroscopic methods. Computational analysis for these complex cations suggests distorted octahedral geometry around Ru(II) that is coordinated to azomethine nitrogen and phenoxide centers of the Schiff base ligand in bidentate mode, chloro and p-cymene ligand in η^6 -mode. Further, molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) values calculations have been performed to gain insights into the electronic properties and stability. Molecular docking studies reveal strong interaction between M1 and penicillin-binding protein-2 (PBP2), thereby highlighting its potential as an antibacterial agent against resistant bacteria. M1 exhibits over 90% inhibition against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* at 12.5 μM and showcases potential anticancer activity against Human cervical cancer cells (SiHa). This study underscores the structural, computational, and biological significance of such class of ruthenium(II) complexes for biomedical applications.

Keywords: MEP, Schiff's Bases, DFT method, Antimycobacterial Activity, Molecular Docking.

OP 81**PCOS an inflammatory disease: Assessing the Role of Vitamin E and CRP.****Mrs. Chhaya V. Jawlikar¹ and Dr. Pooja N. Joshi²**¹Department of Biochemistry, D.Y.Patil Dental School, Lohagaon Pune.412105²Department of Biochemistry, B.J.Govt. Medical college, and sasson Hospital, Pune, 411001

Abstract: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a widespread hormonal disorder affecting women of reproductive age, marked by hormone imbalances, irregular ovulation, and ovarian cysts. Emerging research strongly suggests that persistent, low-grade inflammation plays a crucial role in the development and worsening of PCOS. This chronic inflammation is linked to problems like insulin resistance, higher levels of male hormones (hyperandrogenism), and an increased risk of heart problems.

C-reactive protein (CRP) is a reliable indicator of inflammation throughout the body and is typically found at higher levels in women with PCOS. Additionally, oxidative stress, which occurs when there's an imbalance between harmful reactive oxygen species and the body's protective antioxidants, can intensify this inflammatory state. Vitamin E, a vital fat-soluble antioxidant, is recognized for its powerful anti-inflammatory properties and reflects the body's overall antioxidant capacity.

This study aimed to investigate the inflammatory status of newly diagnosed women with PCOS, measure their baseline Vitamin E levels in relation to CRP before they started any treatment. This is a case-control study, comparing 88 women diagnosed with PCOS to 88 healthy women of similar age. Blood samples had analysed from all participants to determine their serum CRP and Vitamin E concentrations.

The results showed that women with PCOS had significantly higher CRP levels (indicating more inflammation) and markedly lower Vitamin E levels (suggesting weaker protection) compared to the healthy group (both findings were statistically

significant with $p < 0.001$). This supports the idea that PCOS involves a greater inflammatory burden compromising balance between inflammatory and anti-inflammatory status. The clear inverse relationship between CRP and Vitamin E suggests that this imbalance might be contributing to the inflammation seen in PCOS.

In conclusion, the study highlights that women with untreated PCOS have high CRP and lower plasma Vitamin E levels, thus contributing to severity and progression of this condition. These findings emphasize the importance of considering them while managing PCOS.

Keywords: C-Relative Protein, Vitamin E, Oxidative Stress.

OP 82**Title: Correlation of oral health status and Depression Anxiety Stress scale- A cross-sectional study****Dr. Nimty Raina Ambardar¹, Dr. Mrs Anuradha Rajiv Joshi²****¹Department of Physiology, D Y Patil Dental School, Charholi Budruk, via Lohegaon, Pune- 412 105****²Department of Physiology, Professor & Head, Bharati Vidaypeeth (DU) Medical College, Pune-Satara Road, Pune-411 043**

Abstract: Oral health is a dynamic and multifactorial aspect of an individual's overall health. Chronic oral health problems, particularly periodontal disease (a chronic inflammatory condition caused by bacterial infection in the gums), and dental caries are profoundly linked to various systemic conditions. This connection often involves the dysregulation of stress hormones, notably cortisol. The persistent inflammation triggers a systemic immune response, leading to the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines into the blood stream. These mediators can contribute to systemic inflammation, impacting various organs and systems throughout the body. Also strong association exists between periodontal disease and cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus etc. Thus, understanding how gum inflammation (periodontal disease or PD) & dental caries is linked to whole body inflammatory conditions is crucial. Thus, this observational cross-sectional study was planned to explore an intricate relationship if any between oral health parameters (using Russel's Periodontal Index, Decayed Missing Filled Teeth index) & depression and anxiety (using Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale- DASS) in young adults of either sex in age group of 18-23 years to see if oral disease can be a contributor of stress in young adults. The results of this study reveal a positive correlation between Russel's Periodontal index and DASS (p-value 0.01) & positive correlation between DMFT & DASS (p-value 0.01). The study concludes that poorer oral health, encompassing both periodontal disease and dental caries, is significantly associated with higher levels of depression and anxiety in young adults.

Keywords: Oral health, Depression anxiety stress scale, Stress, Decayed Missing Filled Teeth index, Russel's Periodontal Index

OP 83**Multiple Regression Model to Analyze the Effects of Weather Variables on Crop Yield in the Kymore Plateau and Satpura Hills****Navneet Raj Rathore, S.S. Gautam, Suchita Jain and Neelash Patel****Department of Physical Science, MGCGVV, Chitrakoot, Madhya Pradesh-485334, India**

Abstract: This study investigates the influence of weather parameters on the yields of rice and wheat, focusing on six key climate variables: maximum temperature, minimum temperature, morning relative humidity, afternoon relative humidity, rainfall, wind direction, and wind velocity in the Kymore Plateau and Satpura Hills. Using time series data from 2007 to 2023, the study employs multiple regression models to analyze the relationship between these climatic factors and crop yields. The results indicate that weather conditions significantly impact rice and wheat production, highlighting the strong dependence of crop productivity on meteorological variables. The findings further suggest that variations in climatic parameters play a crucial role in determining yield levels, alongside the influence of cultivated area on overall production. Minimum temperature and relative humidity in morning are negatively significantly influences the yield of rice and maximum temperature and wind velocity positively significantly influences and minimum temperature and wind direction are negatively significantly influences the yield of wheat.

Keywords: Multiple regression model, yield, R square, RMSE, MAE, Percent deviation.

OP 84

Incidence Dynamics of Garlic Thrips and Mites: A Statistical Approach to Protected and Unprotected Cultivation Systems**Neelash Patel¹, S. S. Gautam², Navneet Raj Rathore³ and Chandan Nagar⁴**^{1,3&4}**Research Scholar, Department of Physical Science, MGCGVV, Chitrakoot, Satna (M.P.) 485334**²**Associate Professor, Department of Physical Science, MGCGVV, Chitrakoot, Satna (M.P.) 485334**

Abstract: This study was to describe the applicability of mean, standard deviation, variance, t-test have been applied on raw data of incidence of average mites' population on garlic crop. The data was collected from Department of Entomology, J.N.K.V.V., Jabalpur (M.P.), India. A Statistical Approach to have been applied to Incidence Dynamics of Garlic Thrips and Mites to protected and unprotected cultivation systems at different transplanting periods. The study found that protective treatment was effective in reducing thrips on 1st December and mites on 1st October, but showed no significant impact in later transplanting dates, emphasizing the importance of transplanting timing in garlic pest management.

Keyword: Garlic, t-test, Thrips, Mites.

OP 85

Biomarkers and Machine Learning: A Novel Paradigm in CKD Detection**Km. Saumya¹, Mohammad Ahmed Khan², Avinash Ignatius³ and Pankaj Agrahari⁴**

¹Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutical medicine, Division of Pharmacology, School of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi 110062, India.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, School of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi 110062, India.

³Head, Department of Nephrology, Noble Hospitals and Research Centre Pune, Maharashtra, 411013, India

⁴Software Engineer at Zoom Communications, Inc. Bangalore, India

Abstract: This study evaluated the potential of two emerging biomarkers, galectin-3 and periostin, for the early detection and stage-wise classification of chronic kidney disease (CKD) and aimed to develop machine learning models integrating biomarker data to enhance predictive accuracy. A total of 114 CKD patients were enrolled in a cross-sectional study, stratified by albuminuria and eGFR-based staging. Periostin and galectin-3 levels were measured using enzyme-linked immunoassay, and correlation analysis was conducted to assess associations with renal function and biochemical parameters. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were plotted to evaluate diagnostic performance. Machine learning models were trained on various feature sets, with model performance assessed using AUC, accuracy, precision, sensitivity, and F1 score. Interpretability analyses, including SHAP and feature importance rankings, were performed. Both biomarkers showed progressive elevation with advancing CKD stages and exhibited strong negative correlations with eGFR. Galectin-3 demonstrated superior diagnostic accuracy (AUC = 1.00 across all stages), while periostin showed moderate stage-specific performance (AUC = 0.86 to 0.81). Among predictive models, XGBoost achieved perfect classification performance (AUC = 1.00, F1 Score = 1.00) when using the combined biomarker feature set. SHAP analysis identified galectin-3, eGFR, and periostin as key predictors of CKD stage. These findings suggest that

galectin-3 and periostin are promising biomarkers for CKD staging, and their integration with machine learning models, particularly XGBoost, significantly improves classification accuracy, supporting their application in early detection and personalized CKD management. This study aimed to evaluate the potential of two emerging biomarkers galectin-3 and periostin, in the early detection and stage-wise classification of chronic kidney disease and to develop machine learning models integrating biomarkers data for predictive accuracy.

Keywords: Chronic kidney disease, Early detection, Biomarkers, Machine Learning, Predictive Models.

OP 86

Serum Levels of Inflammatory Marker Apelin & AGE in Type2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients with Diabetic Retinopathy in A Tertiary Care Centre, Tamil Nadu: A Case –Control Study

Kalyani Chakkarai¹, Santhini Gopalakrishnan^{2*}

¹Department of Biochemistry, St.Peters Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, Hosur, Tamil Nadu, India-635130

²Department of Biochemistry, Chettinad Academy of Research and Education, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India - 603103

Abstract

Background: Diabetes Mellitus is a metabolic disease with significant health impacts, including cardiovascular disease and retinopathy, exacerbated by uncontrolled glucose levels. The onset of Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is closely associated with oxidative damage, inflammation, and several proangiogenic cytokines. Apelin is pleiotropic peptide cytokine and advanced glycation end products (AGE) are involved in adipogenesis, glucose metabolism and inflammation.

Objective: To assess the levels of inflammatory marker Apelin and AGE in T2DM patients with and without diabetic retinopathy.

Materials and Methods: This study was conducted at St.Peters Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, Hosur, Tamilnadu. Duration of study period was 1year. Totally 110 healthy control, and 110 patients without DR and 110 patients with DR were included. Serum samples were tested for Apelin and AGE by ELISA method. Biochemical parameters and ophthalmological examination findings of the participants were recorded.

Results and Discussion: In this study, we recruited 330 participants, including 110 healthy individuals in group 1, 110 patients T2DM without DR in group2 and 110 T2DM with DR in group 3. Out of 110 DR, 77 were males (70%) and 33 (30%) females.

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Serum Apelin and AGE level was significantly higher in group 3 than in group2 and group1.

Conclusion: patients with T2DM with DR showed higher Serum apelin and AGE levels than those with T2DM without DR and healthy individuals. High levels of apelin & AGE paved the pathogenesis diabetic retinopathy by enhancing inflammation, insulin resistance and angiogenesis factor. Early diagnosis of T2DM provides better treatment and reduces risk of diabetic retinopathy.

OP 87**Screening, Isolation & Characterization of Cholesterol oxidase producing bacteria & harnessing its potential as promising probiotics****Bhawana Prashant Nile¹, Seema Sambhaji Kokitkar^{2*}****¹Department of Biotechnology, Changu Kana Thakur Arts, Commerce and Science College Autonomous, Plot 01, Sector 11, Khanda Colony, New Panvel, Navi Mumbai 410206****^{2*}Department of Biotechnology, Changu Kana Thakur Arts, Commerce and Science College Autonomous, Plot 01, Sector 11, Khanda Colony, New Panvel, Navi Mumbai 410206**

Abstract: Cholesterol-degrading bacteria are a group of microorganisms that have the ability to metabolize and break down cholesterol, a waxy substance found in animal fats and oils. These bacteria play a significant role in maintaining cholesterol balance in the body and offer several potential health benefits. The present study focus on the isolation of the bacteria capable of degrading cholesterol. Cholesterol degrading bacteria has gaining attention due to the ability of these bacteria to produces a key enzyme Cholesterol oxidase (CHO).CHO is capable of oxidizing cholesterol into ketone end products. Cholesterol-degrading bacteria have emerged as promising therapeutic agents for managing hypercholesterolemia, a major risk factor for cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). These bacteria possess the remarkable ability to metabolize and degrade cholesterol, thereby lowering blood cholesterol levels and mitigating the risk of CVDs. CHO has versatile application & commercial importance. Present study focuses on isolation, optimization and application of cholesterol oxidase producing novel bacteria as potential probiotics.

Key words: Cholesterol, Cholesterol-degrading bacteria, Cholesterol oxidase, Cardiovascular diseases, Probiotics.

OP 88**An Enhanced Class of Estimators for Estimating Population Coefficient of Variation in Simple Random Sampling**

Housila P. Singh, Rajesh Tailor and Akanksha Agrawal
School of Studies in Statistics, Vikram University,
Ujjain-456010, M.P., India

Abstract: This research aims to present a novel family of estimators for calculating the population coefficient of variation (CV) of a study variable under simple random sampling with a single auxiliary variable. In particular, we have suggested two classes of estimators: regression type and ratio type. We reviewed the proposed classes of estimators with a number of existing estimators in order to evaluate their effectiveness. Additionally, we have calculated the mean square error (MSE) of every estimator utilized in this research, up to the first order approximation. Both empirical and simulation research have been carried out to verify the theoretical findings. Two important criteria MSE and PRE are used to assess the performance of the suggested classes of estimators. The proposed classes of estimators perform better than the current ones taken into consideration in this study, according to our findings.

Keywords: Simple Random Sampling, Auxiliary Variable, Coefficient of Variation (CV), MSE, PRE, Empirical Study, Simulation Study.

OP 89

Assessment of knowledge regarding preventive measures of menopause associated bone and joint problems among women in a selected hospital of Kolkata, West Bengal
Susmita Chowdhury
Ph. D. Scholar in Nursing
People's University, Bhopal, MP

Introduction: The menopause transition is a critical period for bone health with rapid losses of bone mass and bone mineral density and strength. Many women experience a range of symptoms during menopause, pre menopause and post-menopause. If menopause associated bone and joint problems remains unnoticed this can result in long term problems and disability to the woman (*Khadilkar SS, 2019*). The present study was conducted to assess the knowledge regarding preventive measures of menopause associated bone and joint problems among women in a selected hospital in Kolkata.

Method: A descriptive survey research design was adopted and a total of 100 participants, aged between 40 to 55 years were selected using the non-probability convenience sampling technique. Data were collected from outpatient department by using a structured knowledge questionnaire.

Result: The results showed a mean knowledge score of 16.9 out of 30, with a standard deviation of 3.11. The study categorized knowledge levels as follows: 22% of women had poor knowledge, 61% had average knowledge, and only 17% had good knowledge. Most women (67%) were aware that knee joints are more susceptible to problems during menopause, and 66% were aware about the importance of regular exercise, rest and nutritious food in preventing bone and joint issues post-menopause. However, overall knowledge was inadequate, highlighting the need for education on preventive measures. The study found the significant association between women's knowledge

and demographic variables such as age, educational qualification, occupation, family income and prior information received. This suggests that targeted education and awareness programs could improve knowledge and practices among women, particularly those from lower socioeconomic or with limited access to information.

Conclusion: The study's findings emphasize the importance of educating women about menopause-associated bone and joint problems to prevent long-term issues and disabilities. By prioritizing education and awareness, healthcare providers can empower women to take proactive steps towards maintaining their bone and joint health during the menopause transition.

OP 90

Distribution of weed flora in late-sown wheat**Karishma Singh* and Joy Dawson****Department of Agronomy Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences Prayagraj – 211 007 (Uttar Pradesh)**

Abstract: A detailed floristic survey using random sampling was conducted during the two years of the crop. Among the weed species, some were present throughout the cropping period. Some appeared at later stages of crop and few showed shorter life cycle. It clearly indicates that these weeds have flourished well by weed seed bank. It provided a clue to species diversity in a community and each species that has its own range of ecological amplitude which indicates the condition of the habitat. In the first season of the study, 15 weed species (13 broadleaved weeds, 1 grass and 1 sedge) belonging to 12 families and 12 genera were identified. Among the total species the diversity of the species was found within Fabaceae (3 species), Poaceae (2 species) and the remaining families had only 1 species each. In the second year of the study, the weed population was comparatively lesser and only 10 weed species belonging to the same 9 families and 9 genera were identified. No species diversity was found among the total species. As many as 15 species of weeds were recorded in the field during both the cropping periods. Fabaceae and Poaceae had three and two species respectively while the remaining ten families had only one species each. Monocots were represented by Poaceae and Cyperaceae. *Anagallis arvensis* L. and *Chenopodium album* L. among the broadleaved weeds, followed by annual grassy weed *Phalaris minor* L. and the perennial sedge *Cyperus rotundus* L. were the most dominant weeds which were reported. The field was mainly infested with the broad-leaved weeds (78.57%), along with grasses (14.29%) and sedges (7.14%). The weed species occurring were compared and it was observed that 75.32 % of weeds species were similar, conversely it may be stated that 24.68% of weeds were dis-similar compared to the previous year.

Keywords: Relative Density, Relative Frequency, Importance Value Index, Summed Dominance Ratio, Coefficient of Similarity

OP 91**Assessment of prevalence and knowledge on high-risk behaviour regarding Health and Protective factors among school going adolescents at selected schools, West Bengal****Ms. Piyali De****PhD Scholar, XIth Batch, People's University, People's College of Nursing & Research Centre****Abstract**

Introduction: Adolescence is marked by immense turmoil in physical, cognitive, emotional, and social development. According to the global school-based student health survey 42% of adolescent boys and 37% of adolescent girls were exposed to bullying. Health risk behaviours can determine whether an adolescent will become a healthy adult or develops chronic illnesses (Ansari et al., 2016).

Methods: The investigator conducted a descriptive study with the aim to assess the prevalence and knowledge on high-risk behaviours regarding health and protective factors among school going adolescents at selected schools of West Bengal. Data collected with GSHS (Global School Based Student Health Survey) tool and Structured Knowledge questionnaire by convenience sampling technique from 40 school going adolescents.

Results: Among 40 students Majority (52.5%) students were male and among them (81%) of the school going adolescents were from class IX and (47.5%) were female among them (58%) students are from class IX. Maximum (70%) were at the age group of 14 to 15 years. 100% male and female students are feeling down and nervous most of the time and do exercise either in one day or not doing any physical activity. Result showed the knowledge on high-risk behaviours regarding health and protective factors among 40 students about 13% students had good knowledge, 25% had moderate knowledge, 30% had satisfactory knowledge and 32% had poor knowledge.

Conclusion: The study is concluded that both male and female school going adolescents had high-risk behaviours regarding health and protective factors and also had satisfactory to moderate knowledge and risk behaviour on Mental Health module. Monitoring and parental care may create change. This study must have the implication on nursing service both in academics and administration at the level of community.

Keywords: High-risk behaviours, Protective factors

OP 92**A Theoretical and Experimental Study strong Ferromagnetic Alloys by Tuning Their Crystalline Phase****Shubham Pushkar****Research Scholar, Department of Physics****K. S. Saket P. G. College, Ayodhya, UP**

Abstract: Ferromagnetism is a unusual property that occurs is only a few substances. The common ones are the transition metals iron, Nickel and Cobalt, as well as their alloys and alloys of rare earth metals. It is a property not just of the chemical make-up of a material, but of its crystalline structure and micro structure. Only certain materials, such as iron, Cobalt, nickel and gadolinium, exhibit strong magnetic effects. Such materials are called ferromagnetic, after the Latin word for iron, ferrum. Ferromagnetic alloys are a new class of smart materials, which are receiving considerable interest from the scientific community and industries for actuating and sensing application. The shape memory properties can be controlled and the Martensite micro structure can also be tuned by an applied magnetic field, which leads to large strain in the material. Hence, the large induced strain in these materials is mainly attributed to be rearrangement of Martensite variants (O'Handley 1998 and James and wuttig 1998). When the magnetic field is applied, the tetragonal crystal structure start to from within the parent austenitic cubic phase and the resulting strain causes the formation of twin variants (Ullakko et al 1996). In conventional SMAs, the sample gets deformed when it cooled and the initial state is retained by heating the sample above the Martensitic transformation temperature. But in Ferromagnetic, the sample is exposed to an external magnetic field, which realigns the magnetic moments along the field and hence the variants grow at the expense of other variants resulting in large deformation. Pictorial representation of moment of Martensitic variants in response to an applied magnetic field shown in figure. When ferromagnetic alloy reach there maximum deformation, it remains in the

same state even without the magnetic field. As a consequence, the alloys show large magnetic field induced strain with quicker response at low frequencies than other active materials such as Piezoelectric and Magnetostrictive materials (Henry et. al 2003, Marioni et.al 2003 and O' Handley). Due to quick response time of less than a Milliseconds and high strain of over 10%. Ferromagnetic alloys are the finest applicants for developing actuators. In addition, an ideal magnetic SMA must have high actuation stress, high actuation strain, high operating temperature range and high frequency response and also require low magnetic field for actuation.

OP 93**Immunological Study of Neutrophil Dysfunction in COPD patients with various Comorbidities visiting a Tertiary health Care hospital Tamil Nadu India:****Analytical Cross-sectional study.****Sindhu A^{1*}, Dr. Rajam Krishna S², Dr. Anushuman³****¹Department of Physiology, St. Peters Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, Hosur, Tamil Nadu -635130****²Department of Physiology, Chettinad Academy of Research and Education, Chennai, Tamil Nadu - 603103****³Department of Pulmonology, St. Peters Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, Hosur, Tamil Nadu -635130**

Background: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a major cause of chronic morbidity and is the fourth leading cause of death worldwide. The main casual factor is prolonged exposure to cigarette smoke or other noxious particles which lead to reduced air flow and pulmonary hyperinflation. Although COPD primarily affects the lungs, it is also recognized as a complex multi-systemic disease that frequently coexists with other conditions known as comorbidities. With comorbidities COPD become worse prognosis and quality of life compared to patients without comorbidities. Neutrophilic inflammation is a prominent feature of COPD. Malfunctioning of neutrophils in Lung results chronic inflammation.

Aims and Objectives: To evaluate the count and functions of neutrophils and correlating them with various co morbidities like Cardio vascular disease, Diabetes, Hypertension, dyslipidemia.

Materials and Methods: This study was conducted at St. Peters Medical College Hospital & Research Institute, Hosur, Tamil Nadu. Duration of study 1year. Blood samples were collected from 150 COPD patients with and without comorbidities. The present study proposes to do Neutrophil function test such as chemotaxis, phagocytosis,

intracellular killing (candidacidal assay), and nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT) and correlate them with COPD Patients.

Results: Neutrophil count was significantly increased in COPD patients. There was a statistically significant decrease (P value $<0.01^*$) in the killing capacity of Neutrophil function test like phagocytosis, chemotaxis, NBT, intracellular killing.

Conclusion: Killing activity of the Neutrophil had decreased in our study although based on the comorbidities the killing capacities of neutrophil differ. Phagocytic functions had reduced significantly.

OP 94

Women and Western Medicine in Colonial India**Anshu Sharma¹, Dr. Rahul Tripathi²**¹PhD Scholar, Amity University Rajasthan²Director, Amity School of Liberal Arts, Amity University Rajasthan

Abstract: The paper focuses on the intricate relationship between Western medicine and women in India during colonial times. It tries to explore the impact that Western medicine has had on the health and overall socioeconomic condition of Indian women. There were previous studies that analyzed the impact of the introduction of Western medicine in colonial India, but the present study addresses the theme in a more extensive manner. Western medicine was brought to India primarily for the economic self-interest of the colonial rulers and for their survival. Due primarily to Purdah and societal stigma, imperial authority encountered significant obstacles while attempting to provide medical care to women. Therefore, laws were formulated to deal with the medical requirements of Indian women. The paper focuses on the analysis of Western medicine's somewhat convincing results, such as a decrease in pregnant women's death rates, the adoption of modern childbirth practices, an increase in the number of female physicians, and the opening of doors for women to pursue medical education. The arrival of Western medicine also paved the way for social reforms for women. However, there are concerns that this paper tries to address, such as whether offering Western medicine to women served colonial objectives or was a gesture of goodwill towards them. And it was also a process that culminated in the commoditization of medicine, treating the native populace as mere consumers with wide-ranging consequences. Indian women currently rely significantly on modern forms of medicine, so this paper makes an effort to examine how Western medicine has impacted Indian women in the past. By doing so, it hopes to contribute to the development of future policies that will ensure that current and future generations of Indians have access to effective medical care.

Keywords: Western medicine, Colonial rule, women, medical education, health.

OP 95**Antibiotic Stewardship Education in Residency: Current Practices and Future Directions****Pratiksha Dhamal****D.Y Patil Dental School, Lohegaon pune Maharashtra 412105**

Introduction: Antimicrobial stewardship is a coordinated program for appropriate use of antimicrobial agents through optimal antimicrobial drug regimen. Implementation of a stewardship program is a necessity of the hour due to issue of increasing resistance for certain antibiotics which is why appropriate efforts of doctors towards this program is a must

Methodology: This was questionnaire based cross sectional study, conducted by a survey of preformed questions on knowledge (10), attitude (10) and practice (10) of antibiotic stewardship program among 150 resident doctors at tertiary care teaching hospital in Pune, India.

Statistical analysis: The responses obtained from residents were evaluated and data was expressed in frequency and percentage & comparison between non-surgical and surgical residents was done using Fisher's exact test using Statistical package for Social Sciences software 9.4.

Results: 85% of residents were unaware of the frequency of updated guidelines by ICMR while 31% considered that newer and costlier antibiotics have better efficacy. 83% residents took under consideration the cost of drugs before prescription. 24% residents believe that antimicrobial resistance is not common in their practice. Only 67% residents agreed to take help from microbiologists and pharmacologist before prescription and 27% were found not to follow the formulatory regulations in their practice. 41% residents preferred empiric therapy over targeted one. The comparison between surgical and non-surgical fields was insignificant.

Conclusion: Few gaps in knowledge observed, need to be corrected for residents along with change required in their perception towards use of antimicrobials and practice methods. Overall surgical and non-surgical residents have good knowledge, perception and practice methods and the comparison between both of them shows no significance.

Keywords: antimicrobials, residents, questionnaire

OP 96

Anesthetic Efficacy of Clove Oil and Its Physiological Effects on Fry of *Labeo catla* (Hamilton, 1822)**Abdullah¹ and Sana Naz^{2*}**^{1,2}Department of Zoology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, UP, India

Abstract: This study assessed the anesthetic efficacy and physiological safety of clove oil in fry of *Labeo catla*, a commercially significant Indian Major Carp. Six graded concentrations of clove oil (0-200 mg/L) were tested to identify the optimal dose for rapid induction and smooth recovery. The 50 mg/L concentration emerged as the most effective, inducing deep anesthesia within 5 minutes and ensuring full recovery with 100% survival. Hematological parameters such as, hemoglobin, hematocrit, and red blood cell count, showed no significant difference ($P>0.05$) before and after exposure, reinforcing the safety of clove oil at appropriate doses. Doses more than 50 mg/L triggered delayed recovery and increased mortality, with a 100% mortality at dose of 100 mg/L suggesting the efficacy of clove oil at this level for anesthesia. These findings highlight the potential of clove oil as a low-cost, plant-based anesthetic for routine aquaculture tasks, offering safety, efficacy, and bioethical advantages in fish management and research settings.

Keywords: *Labeo catla*, clove oil, anesthesia, euthanasia, hematological parameters, aquaculture.

OP 97

Optimizing Plant Density and Nano Urea-based Nitrogen Strategies for Enhanced Growth of Sweet Corn in Zaid Season**Anil Kumar^{1*}, Shalendra Kumar Verma¹, Shashi Bhooshan Singh¹ and Vivek²****¹Research Scholar, Department of Agronomy, Narain (PG) College Shikohabad, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar University Agra****²Professor & Head, Department of Agronomy, Narain (PG) College Shikohabad, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar University Agra**

Abstract: A field experiment during *Zaid* 2024 and 2025 at Agronomy Research Farm, Narain (PG) College, Shikohabad, evaluated plant density and nitrogen management effects on sweet corn growth using a split-plot design with four replications. The main plots included three plant densities: S₁ (60×20 cm), S₂ (50×20 cm), and S₃ (45×20 cm). Subplots comprised six nitrogen treatments: N₁ (Control), N₂ (100% prilled urea), N₃ (75% prilled urea +2 Nano urea sprays), N₄ (75% prilled urea + 2% foliar prilled urea spray), N₅ (50% prilled urea +2 Nano urea sprays) and N₆ (50% prilled urea + 2% foliar prilled urea spray). Growth parameters were recorded at 25 DAS, 50 DAS, and at harvest.

The study during showed significant effects of plant density and nitrogen on sweet corn during 2024 and 2025, S₃ (45×20 cm) recorded the tallest plants (173.17 cm and 174.43 cm), 1.33% and 1.42% higher than S₂ (170.89 cm and 171.99 cm) and 2.78% and 1.70% above S₁ (168.48 cm and 171.52 cm) due to intense light competition. Conversely, S₁ (60×20 cm) achieved the highest fresh weight (430.59 g and 431.48 g) and dry weight (85.87 g and 87.19 g), exceeding S₂ (395.04 g and 399.84 g; 79.26 g and 80.48 g) by 9.00% and 7.91% (fresh) and 8.30% and 8.34% (dry), and S₃ (389.97 g and 392.46 g; 77.75 g and 78.97 g) by 10.42% and 9.94% (fresh) and 10.45% and 10.39% (dry). Among nitrogen levels N₃ (75% prilled urea + 2 Nano urea sprays) gave the highest plant height (188.45 cm and 189.42 cm), fresh weight (534.98 g and 535.08 g) and dry weight (106.99 g and 108.64 g) surpassing N₂ (180.16 cm and 182.52 cm; 484.90 g and 486.58 g; 96.28 g and 98.44 g) by 4.60% and 3.78% (height), 10.32% and 9.98% (fresh),

and 11.12% and 10.36% (dry), while N₁ (153.73 cm and 152.20 cm; 280.52 g and 284.87 g; 56.02 g and 56.86 g) remained lowest. The superiority of N₃ is attributed to Nano urea's slow nutrient release, improved foliar absorption, reduced volatilization, and enhanced nitrogen-use efficiency, sustaining photosynthesis and biomass accumulation.

Keywords: Nano Urea, Plant Density, Prilled Urea, Plant height, Fresh weight per plant and Dry weight per plant.

OP 98

Synthesis of (8R,9S,13S,14S,17S)-17-((E)-1-(benzylimino)ethyl)-13-methyl-6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17-dodecahydro-1H-cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-3(2H)-one and in silico study**Sangeeta Srivastava & Apoorva Gupta**

Department of chemistry,

University of Lucknow, Lucknow- 226007, India

Abstract: Recent advances in our understanding of the mechanism of action of the progesterone and other steroid hormone receptors have led to renewed interest in the development of synthetic probes that can bind to and modulate their function. The reaction of progesterone, a steroidal ketone hormone, with benzylamine was investigated to explore the formation of imine or amine derivatives via nucleophilic addition or condensation. Under mild conditions, benzylamine reacts with the C-20 ketone group of progesterone, leading to the formation of a Schiff base (imine) through a condensation reaction, with water as a by-product. The reaction may be facilitated by mild heating or the use of dehydrating agents to shift the equilibrium toward product formation.. This reaction provides a useful route for functional modification of progesterone, potentially enhancing its pharmacological properties or enabling its use in drug conjugation strategies. Molecular docking studies were conducted to investigate the potential interaction between progesterone, a key steroid hormone, and benzylamine, a simple aromatic amine with biological relevance. The objective of this study was to evaluate the binding affinity and interaction profile between these two molecules using computational docking techniques. Results indicated that progesterone forms a stable complex with benzylamine, exhibiting a binding energy of [insert value if available] kcal/mol.

Keywords: Progesterone, benzyl amine, Schiff base, molecular docking, binding energy.

OP 99

Cephalotaxine and Derivatives as Next-Gen Bioactives: Structural, Molecular, and Therapeutic Perspectives**L. Durga¹, Sridevi Gopathy¹, A. Arockya Staf¹****¹Department of Physiology, SRM Dental College, Bharathi Salai, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India**

Abstract: The rare benzoazepine alkaloid cephalotaxine (CET), which comes from the *Cephalotaxus* genus, has evolved into an efficient bioactive compound with an abundance of pharmacological effects. Since it was first isolated in the 1960s, researchers have delved deep into the anti-inflammatory, antiviral, anticancer, and antibacterial properties of cephalotaxine. One of its derivatives, homoharringtonine (HHT), has even gained clinical approval for treating chronic myelogenous leukaemia (CML). Recent studies suggest that cephalotaxine might trigger mitochondrial-mediated apoptosis and suppress autophagy by modulating key apoptosis-related genes and proteins like Bcl-2, Bak, LC3-II, and p62. Additionally, cephalotaxine and its esters have shown impressive broad-spectrum antiviral activity by effectively inhibiting the production and replication of viral proteins. Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS) significantly aided in identifying, structurally describing, and measuring cephalotaxine and its derivatives from plant sources and experimental formulations. Moreover, investigations into protein modulation and gene expression profiling have provided valuable insights into the molecular mechanisms behind cephalotaxine's action. This review emphasises the therapeutic potential of cephalotaxine and underscores the necessity for further preclinical and clinical research, bringing together the latest findings on its molecular targets, pharmacological effects, chemical structure, and biosynthetic origins.

Keywords: Alkaloid derivatives, Anticancer activity, Apoptosis modulation, Autophagy, Cephalotaxine, Therapeutic potential.

OP 100

Pomiferin: A Promising Prenylated Isoflavone with Multifaceted Therapeutic Potential – A Comprehensive Review**A. Arockya Stafi and Sridevi Gopathy****Department of Physiology, SRM Dental College**

Abstract: Pomiferin, a prenylated isoflavone derived mainly from the fruit of *Maclura pomifera*, has received a great deal of attention with regard to its various pharmacological activities. As a natural phytochemical, pomiferin exhibits numerous therapeutic effects, such as strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antimicrobial, and neuroprotective activities. The possible outcomes are caused principally due to the presence of a prenyl group in its chemical structure, which helps the bioavailability and cellular binding. It has also been found to be very important in playing a crucial role in modulating key molecular pathways such as NF- κ B, Nrf2, MAPK, and apoptosis regulators, thus interfering in several physiological and pathological processes. On another note, pomiferin confers cytoprotection against oxidative stress and inflammation the two most frequent underpinnings of chronic afflictions such as cancer and neurodegeneration. Preclinical evidence supports pomiferin's role in alleviating oxidative stress and modulating immune functions, including inducing selective cytotoxicity in several cancer cell types. The remarkable bioactivity of pomiferin has never found large-scale clinical translation because of issues such as its poor water solubility and limited pharmacokinetic data. This review aims to present the therapeutic potential of pomiferin, highlighting the mechanisms of action, pharmacological significance, and the need for further research to push preclinical into clinical applications.

Keywords: Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory, Anticancer, Oxidative stress, Pomiferin, Prenylated isoflavone

OP 101

Study of Rainfall Pattern Shifts and Index-Based Analysis: Understanding the Impacts of Climate Change scenario of bundelkhad region of Madhya Pradesh
Suchita Jain, S.S. Gautam, Navneet Raj Rathore and Neelash Patel
Department of Physical Science, MGCGVV, Chitrakoot, Madhya Pradesh-485334, India

Abstract: The Bundelkhand region of Madhya Pradesh, comprising the districts of Chhatarpur, Tikamgarh, Damoh, Sagar, Datia, and Panna, has increasingly become vulnerable to climate variability, particularly due to erratic and declining rainfall patterns. This study investigates the shifts in annual rainfall and the impact of climate change on precipitation trends using the Standardized Index of Annual Precipitation (SIAP) over a 15-year period (2008–2022). Secondary rainfall data for each district were analyzed to determine variability, drought frequency, and the prevalence of extreme weather events. The SIAP values revealed significant interannual variability, with alternating wet and dry years across all districts. Extreme dry conditions were observed in years like 2009 and 2017, while 2011 and 2013 marked unusually wet periods. Districts like Sagar and Damoh displayed a strong tendency toward climatic instability, with over half the years exhibiting below-average rainfall. The findings underscore the growing threat of meteorological drought, reduced soil moisture, and falling groundwater levels across the region—conditions exacerbated by climate change, land use alteration, and deforestation. The study emphasizes the urgent need for climate-resilient agricultural strategies, improved water resource planning, and adaptive management policies to mitigate the socio-economic impacts of shifting rainfall dynamics in Bundelkhand.

Keywords: Standardized Index of Annual Precipitation, meteorological drought, drought frequency.

OP 102

**Prisoners as the Forgotten Patients: A Rights-Based Argument for
Psychotherapy in Indian Prisons*****R. Renjini and **Arun Kumar G*****Research Scholar, Department of Forensic Science, Kalasalingam Academy of
Research and Education (Deemed to be University), Krishnankoil, Tamil Nadu - India******MGR Research Fellow, Department of Criminology and Criminal Justice Science,
Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu - India**

Abstract: This paper highlights the forgotten mental health crisis inside Indian prisons. While thousands of inmates suffer from psychological distress, ranging from trauma to depression to violent outbursts, there is no formal system for psychotherapy in most jails. This silence is not just a public health failure; it is a violation of the Indian Constitution, especially Article 21, which guarantees the right to life and dignity. The paper argues that denying psychotherapy to prisoners is a form of institutional violence, and it contradicts both national laws like the Mental Healthcare Act (2017) and international agreements such as the UN Mandela Rules. Using real-life examples, legal precedents, and government reports, the study shows that prisoners are being psychologically punished rather than reformed. The paper calls for urgent reforms, starting with mental health screening at admission, tele-therapy partnerships with institutions like NIMHANS, and the recognition of therapy as a basic legal right in the prison system. This work fills a major research gap by framing psychotherapy in prisons not as a welfare option, but as a constitutional and human rights obligation, an argument rarely made in Indian academic or policy literature.

Keywords: Prison, Mental Health, Article 21, Psychotherapy, Mandela Rules, Rights-Based Framework

OP 103**Exploring the Sustainability of Freelancing as an Emerging Career Path in India: A Descriptive perspectives****Suneeta Pandey^a and Dr. Mohd. Haneef^b**^aResearch Scholar, Department of Commerce, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, U.P.^bProfessor, Department of Commerce, Vidyant Hindu P.G. College, Lucknow, U.P.

Abstract: The landscape of employment has undergone a transformation with freelancing and it is emerging as a mainstream career option. A new phase of industrialization that is industry 5.0 emerges with the advanced technology which fueled the freelancing. Currently, companies are also shifting toward freelancers. This study presents a comprehensive investigation of the field aiming to explore and provide evidence about sustainability of freelancing as a long-term career path. In this study primary and secondary data were used. A survey method is used to collect primary data and the data were analyzed through excel and pivot table. For the secondary one, existing literatures like research articles, different market studies and case studies were referred. The paper investigates the motivation to choosing freelance, the sustainability factors associated with freelancing and the challenges faced by the freelancers. The findings reveal that the growth opportunities and flexibility is most motivating factor but it lacks sustainability. Instability and social pressure is main reason behind it. The study provides important insights to the government, companies as well as freelancers itself about this structural gap and also suggest for providing a support system to make freelancing a stable and long-term career option.

OP 104**Effect of 12 weeks high intensity interval training on sleep quality in obesity-related hypertension: A Randomized Controlled Trial****Aqsa Mujaddadi¹, Irshad Husain Naqvi², Zubia Veqar³****¹PhD Scholar, Centre for Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Sciences, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi-110025, India****²MBBS, MD, Chief Medical Officer, Ansari Health Centre, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi-110025, India****³Professor and Director, Centre for Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Sciences, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi-110025, India****Abstract**

Purpose: This study investigated the effects of a 12-week high-intensity interval training (HIIT) program on sleep quality in individuals with obesity-related hypertension and coexisting cardiac autonomic dysfunction (CAD).

Methods: The intervention group (n=15) participated in supervised HIIT sessions three times per week, while the control group (n=15) received standard medical care without any structured exercise regimen. Sleep quality was evaluated both before and after the intervention using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), which assesses several components including subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, and sleep efficiency, use of sleep medication, sleep disturbances, daytime dysfunction, and the global PSQI score.

Results: Post-intervention analysis revealed significant improvements in the HIIT group across several PSQI domains. Specifically, subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep efficiency, and the overall global PSQI score were significantly improved in the HIIT group when compared to the control.

Conclusion: These findings indicate that engaging in a consistent and structured HIIT regimen can positively influence several aspects of sleep quality in this sample. The

study highlights the feasibility and potential efficacy of HIIT as a non-pharmacological strategy for improving sleep quality among individuals with obesity-related hypertension and coexisting CAD.

Keywords: Obesity-related hypertension, cardiac autonomic dysfunction, sleep quality, PSQI

OP 105**Recent trends in water scarcity and hydrological changes****Gunjan Suresh Thengari¹ and Apurva D. Fuladi²****¹Student, Department of Geology, S.S.E.S.A's Science College, Congress Nagar, Nagpur (440012), M.S., India,****²Assistant Professor, Department of Geology, S.S.E.S A's Science College, Nagpur (440012), M.S., India**

Abstract: Water scarcity is one of the most urgent global challenges of the 21st century. The combined effects of rapid population growth and climate change have put extreme pressure on already limited freshwater resources. This issue impacts ecosystems, human health, agriculture, economic development, and social stability. According to UN-Water, over two billion people live in countries suffering from high water stress. This paper explores how rising global temperatures alter the hydrological cycle—changing precipitation patterns, increasing evaporation, and accelerating the melting of glaciers and snowpacks. These disruptions reduce freshwater availability and storage in soil, rivers, and aquifers, resulting in unpredictable water supply across regions. Water scarcity exists in two forms: physical scarcity, where natural water resources are insufficient, and economic scarcity, where access is limited by poor management or infrastructure. Marginalized populations, particularly women and children, are the most affected, often spending hours daily fetching water, limiting their access to education and opportunity. The study highlights Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) as a practical and long-term approach to solving water issues. It emphasizes cross-sectoral coordination, technological innovation, effective monitoring, and inclusive governance. Addressing the water-food-energy nexus is also crucial for resilience, as these systems are closely interconnected. Real-world examples such as the Indus Basin, Arabian Peninsula, and Colorado River illustrate both the severity of the crisis and current efforts being made. Ultimately, this research shows that solving water scarcity requires not only technical solutions but also cooperation, strong policy

support, and community involvement. A science-based, inclusive, and sustainable approach is key to securing a water-resilient future for all.

Keywords: water scarcity, climate change, hydrological cycle, IWRM, water-food-energy nexus, groundwater, sustainable development.

OP 106**Functional and Esthetic Rehabilitation in TMJ Ankylosis with Mandibular Sigmoid Osteotomy: A Retrospective Assessment and Design Rationale****Sibgutulah Rashid¹ and Sailesh Kumar Mukul²****^{1,2}Department of Dentistry - Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, AIIMS Patna, Bihar 801507**

Abstract: Temporomandibular joint ankylosis (TMJA) is a debilitating condition marked by fusion of the mandibular condyle to the glenoid fossa, resulting in severely restricted jaw mobility, mandibular hypoplasia, facial asymmetry, and profound functional and psychosocial impairment. Conventional surgical techniques often fail to concurrently address joint immobility and the associated skeletal deformities or are limited to correcting the deformity in a single plane, such as vertical (height) or horizontal (length) correction. To overcome these limitations, this study evaluated the clinical and radiographic outcomes of a novel Mandibular Sigmoid Osteotomy (MSO) combined with distraction osteogenesis (DO) for simultaneous TMJ ankylosis release and mandibular deformity correction as a single-stage procedure.

Fifteen patients (aged 6–32 years) underwent treatment using a novel curvilinear “S-type” mandibular sigmoid osteotomy, designed to overcome pterygomasseteric resistance and facilitate stable, multiplanar vector control during distraction. Preoperative planning included 3D CT morphometric analysis and surgical simulation using patient-specific 3D-printed models. Interpositional arthroplasty with a temporalis myofascial flap was performed to restore joint function and prevent re-ankylosis. Distraction was initiated on postoperative days 2–5 at a rate of 1 mm/day until the desired correction was achieved, followed by a 12–16week consolidation period.

Postoperative outcomes demonstrated consistent functional improvement, with all patients achieving an interincisal mouth opening of ≥ 35 mm. Significant post-treatment increases were observed in ramus height (mean \pm SD: +3.22 mm), mandibular body

length (+4.91 mm), and curvilinear mandibular length (+6.07 mm), all statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). No major complications such as infection, device failure, or relapse were reported. Radiographic assessments showed high inter- and intra-rater reliability (Cohen's Kappa: 0.75–0.79; ICC: 0.83–0.85).

MSO combined with DO offers a reliable, functionally and esthetically effective single-stage approach for managing TMJA-associated mandibular deformities. While early results are encouraging, larger prospective studies are needed to validate long-term outcomes and procedural reproducibility.

Keywords: temporomandibular joint ankylosis, distraction osteogenesis, mandibular sigmoid osteotomy

OP 107**Determination of stability constants of some bivalent and trivalent metal ions with a biologically active ligand****Abhay Patel, Tanvi Kaushik, Anushka Yadav, Badal Chawla, Abhishek Yadav, Manisha Jain, Shallu Sachdeva*****Department of Chemistry, Acharya Narendra Dev College, University of Delhi**

Abstract: Amino acids are building blocks of proteins which function as metabolic intermediates, neurotransmitters, hormone precursors, and help to maintain osmotic equilibrium and pH balance within cells. An example of such a versatile amino acid is aspartic acid. Aspartic acid is a proteinogenic amino acid which is integrated into proteins, participates in metabolic processes such as the urea cycle and gluconeogenesis and is also involved in nucleotide synthesis. It also functions as an excitatory neurotransmitter in the central nervous system. Because of its acidic qualities, aspartic acid contributes to the chelation of metal ions inside proteins and enzymes and helps to regulate the pH of cells. These functions highlight the role of aspartic acid in preserving cellular activities. Aspartic acid forms a stable complex with aluminium. This reduces its free ion activity protecting the cell from oxidative damage. Zinc is an essential trace element vital for immune function. Cobalt is a component of vitamin B₁₂. The present study aims to determine stability constants of the above-mentioned metal ions with Aspartic Acid at 0.02M ionic strength by electroanalytical method (pH metry) using Bjerrum's Half-Integral Method. The stability constants for Zinc (Zn), Aluminium (Al) and Cobalt (Co) with the ligand, at room temperature are found in order - Zinc (Zn) > Cobalt (Co) > Aluminium (Al). This order is in good agreement with Irving William order of stability constants.

Keywords: Stability Constants, bivalent, trivalent, electroanalytical method, Bjerrum's half integral method

OP 108**The Dual Edge of Artificial Intelligence at Amazon: Understanding its Benefits and Pitfalls****Riya Jagadish****Student, Kings Cornerstone International College, Chennai**

Abstract: This research, "The Dual Edge of Artificial Intelligence at Amazon: Understanding Its Benefits and Pitfalls," examines AI's multifaceted role within Amazon, a global technology and e-commerce leader. It analyses AI integration's advantages and disadvantages across operations and its impact on company growth and market position, exploring Amazon's AI rationale and strategic implementation. A mixed-methods approach utilized surveys, interviews, questionnaires, academic articles, reports, and journals. Findings reveal AI significantly boosts Amazon's operational effectiveness, precision, and customer individualization through personalized shopping, Amazon Alexa, automated customer services, and optimized supply chain logistics. These applications maximize efficiency and satisfaction, providing a crucial competitive edge and driving long-term growth and market dominance. However, challenges include job displacement, data privacy and algorithmic bias concerns, and excessive technology reliance. Recommendations for Amazon involve employee training, clear AI ethical guidelines, increased customer transparency, and fostering internal collaboration. Future scholars should research AI's ethical implications, interdisciplinary approaches, and global adoption. Ultimately, the study emphasizes a balanced, responsible AI integration, leveraging benefits while addressing challenges for sustainable growth and positive societal impact.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Project Management Plan (PMP) , Customer Experience and Ethical Considerations

OP 109**Tesla's AI Revolution: Benefits and Challenges Ahead****S Leenashree****Student, Kings Cornerstone International College, Chennai**

Abstract: This research investigates the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Tesla's operations and its broader implications for the automotive industry. Focusing on Tesla's AI-driven features, particularly Autopilot and Full Self Driving (FSD), the study examines the benefits, challenges, and public perceptions surrounding the integration of AI in electric vehicles. Guided by a structured Project Management Plan (PMP), the research employs both primary and secondary methods, including surveys, literature reviews, and case studies. The findings reveal that while Tesla is widely regarded as a leader in AI innovation, it also faces critical challenges such as regulatory pressures, ethical concerns, and public skepticism. To address these, the study offers practical recommendations for Tesla to enhance transparency, strengthen safety measures, and improve public outreach. It also highlights opportunities for future researchers to focus on sustainability, battery efficiency, and the ethical development of AI. Ultimately, the research underscores the need to balance rapid technological progress with responsible and thoughtful implementation in the ever-evolving landscape of smart mobility.

Keywords: Tesla, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Autopilot, Full Self Driving (FSD), Smart Mobility.

OP 110**Streamlining sound: how Spotify supports artificial intelligence to escalate music discovery****Diya Jagadish****Student, Kings Cornerstone International College, Chennai**

Abstract: This report explores the strategic use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) by Spotify and its effectiveness in enhancing user experience, driving personalization, and supporting business growth. The central aim of the project is to examine how AI technologies such as machine learning algorithms, predictive analytics, and data-driven personalization contribute to Spotify's competitive advantage in the music streaming industry. The project utilizes both primary and secondary research methods. Primary data was gathered through a Google Forms survey targeting regular Spotify users, allowing for the collection of real-time feedback regarding user satisfaction with AI-driven features like Discover Weekly and personalized playlists. Secondary research supported the analysis with industry insights and academic perspectives on AI application in digital platforms. A Gantt chart was used to plan the timeline of activities, ensuring effective scheduling, task delegation, and resource management. The findings suggest that a significant majority of users find Spotify's AI features accurate, engaging, and useful in discovering new music and enhancing their overall listening experience. Furthermore, the report analyzes various aspects of project management, including a breakdown of tasks, risk assessment, quality assurance, communication strategies, and resource allocation. The implementation of a detailed project management plan ensured the project was executed within scope and on schedule. Challenges such as ensuring unbiased data collection and time constraints were acknowledged and mitigated through proper planning and collaboration. The report concludes with a reflective section that highlights the development of personal and professional skills, including critical thinking, data analysis, teamwork, and

communication. Overall, the study showcases how Spotify's effective integration of AI not only improves user engagement and satisfaction but also contributes to its business sustainability and innovation. This project reinforces the value of AI in modern business strategies and emphasizes the importance of structured project planning in achieving successful outcomes.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Spotify, Personalization, User Experience, Music Recommendation, Data Analysis, Business Growth.

OP 111

Anesthetic Efficacy of Clove Oil and Its Physiological Effects on Fry of *Labeo catla* (Hamilton, 1822)**Abdullah¹ and Sana Naz^{2*}****^{1,2}Department of Zoology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, U.P., India**

Abstract: This study assessed the anesthetic efficacy and physiological safety of clove oil in fry of *Labeo catla*, a commercially significant Indian Major Carp. Six graded concentrations of clove oil (0-200 mg/L) were tested to identify the optimal dose for rapid induction and smooth recovery. The 50 mg/L concentration emerged as the most effective, inducing deep anesthesia within 5 minutes and ensuring full recovery with 100% survival. Hematological parameters such as, hemoglobin, hematocrit, and red blood cell count, showed no significant difference ($P>0.05$) before and after exposure, reinforcing the safety of clove oil at appropriate doses. Doses more than 50 mg/L triggered delayed recovery and increased mortality, with a 100% mortality at dose of 100 mg/L suggesting the efficacy of clove oil at this level for anesthesia. These findings highlight the potential of clove oil as a low-cost, plant-based anesthetic for routine aquaculture tasks, offering safety, efficacy, and bioethical advantages in fish management and research settings.

Keywords: *Labeo catla*, clove oil, anesthesia, euthanasia, hematological parameters, aquaculture.

OP 112**Aging with Dignity: Functional Assessment of the Rural Elderly in the coastal city of Visakhapatnam****Dr. Moulika Mamidi****Postgraduate, NRI Institute of Medical Sciences, Department of Community Medicine, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh**

Objective/Background: Functional disability is an emerging public health issue in India's aging population which is numbered as 149 million in 2022 and is expected to reach 194 million by 2031 (MoSPI, 2021). With 71% residing in rural areas the challenge lies in the inadequate healthcare and support systems available in these underserved areas. The limitations interfere with the ability to manage daily tasks on their own, overall quality of life and increased dependency. This study aims to assess the prevalence of functional limitations and exploring their determinants which is crucial in promoting healthy ageing and improving geriatric care.

Methods: A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted in the rural coastal region of Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh. A total of 271 elderly individuals aged 60 years and above were surveyed in the field area using a pretested, structured, standard questionnaire. Functional status was assessed using the Katz Index of Activities of Daily Living (ADL) and the Lawton Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL) Scale. Sociodemographic and health data were also collected. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 26, with both descriptive and inferential statistics applied.

Results: Of all the participants, Impairment in at least one ADL was observed in 38.7% of participants, while 54.2% showed limitations in one or more IADLs. Functional disability was significantly associated with advanced age, female gender and living alone. IADL deficits were prominent in domains such as transportation, meal preparation, and financial management.

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Discussion/Conclusions: The study emphasizes the burden of functional disability among the rural elderly and underscores the need for routine functional assessments and tailored community-based interventions. Early identification and support can help maintain independence, reduce caregiver burden, and enhance the dignity and quality of life of aging individuals in underserved areas.

OP 113**Transforming Public Health through Artificial Intelligence: Opportunities,
Challenges and Future Directions****Tumul Rastogi****PG student, Department of Health science
Uttaranchal University**

Abstract: The article outlines what Artificial Intelligence (AI) can do in public health. This is vital during the COVID-19 outbreak. It investigates various AI uses such as public health education, telehealth, automated diagnosis and symptom assessment, and forecasting disease. Specifically, the work investigates the trustworthiness of the ethics of GPT-3, acknowledging resistance in the quality of data and the governance thereof. It investigates a concerted draft that is recommended to align the AI in public health systems and education, and it emphasises an ethical guide, policy update and integrated cooperation. The last part of the paper analyses a framework for future AI and includes a discussion of execution strategies and research core areas to maximise the benefit of AI to public health. And the paper points out AI's role as an assistant but not a replacement, a tool that can help human decisions and public health results when applied responsibly.

OP 114**Telemedicine and law in India: A Critical Analysis of the Legal and Ethical Framework Post-Covid 19****Akshita Tanisha Singh****B.B.A.L.L.B, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan**

Abstract: This study examines the development, application, legal environment, and difficulties of telemedicine in India, particularly in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. In India, telemedicine which is the use of information and communication technology to provide healthcare remotely has become a vital instrument for bridging the gap between rural and urban healthcare? Especially in underprivileged communities, it improves accessibility, lowers healthcare costs, and supports the overburdened primary healthcare system.

The present work employs a doctrinal and analytical research methodology. A comprehensive analysis of secondary sources, such as national and international policy papers, laws, court rulings, government directives, and academic publications, is part of the study. To comprehend the current regulatory framework, special attention has been given to the Telemedicine Practice Guidelines (2020), the National Medical Commission Act (2019), the Information Technology Act (2000), and the Drugs and Cosmetics Act (1940). In order to assess the legal hazards and ethical limits of teleconsultations, judicial precedents such as the Deepa Sanjeev Pawaskar v. State of Maharashtra case have been thoroughly analyzed.

Furthermore, using statistical data and official government reports, the research assesses the practical impact of government efforts like as the eSanjeevani telemedicine platform. An understanding of international best practices can be gained by comparing telemedicine practices in other nations.

According to research, telemedicine has the potential to completely transform healthcare delivery in India, but it also confronts obstacles like low awareness, uneven application, unclear laws, and worries about data protection. The study comes to the conclusion that integrating telemedicine into traditional healthcare requires a multi-stakeholder approach that includes legal reform, the creation of digital infrastructure, medical education, and public awareness campaigns.

In the end, telemedicine should be viewed as a sustainable, supplementary approach to conventional healthcare systems that can help India achieve its objective of universal health coverage rather than just as a band-aid solution.

OP 115**Artificial Intelligence-empowered Sustainability enhancing organizational development****Mr. Ayushman Panda¹, Dr. Dhyanadipta Panda² and Mrs. Chandralekha Rath³**¹Student, Christ Deemed to be University, B.Tech- CSE (AI &ML)²Assistant Professor-II, KIIT Deemed to be University, School of Liberal Studies³Faculty, KIIT International School, IBDP Comp. Science

Abstract: Artificial Intelligence and sustainability, are no doubt two of the most conflicted topics to be discussed together in any intellectual discussion spaces. Based on various, ideas, theories, rationales, or opinions, there are quite a huge number of varying definitions of the interdependence of both the concepts. At the current rate of development and globalization, the applications of Artificial Intelligence along with the ideas of sustainability not only unlocks many possible advancements in sustainable development, but also is deemed to be as the need of the hour, keeping in eye the degradation at various aspects and levels. Innovative Education, Advanced Healthcare, Economic upgradations, use of Green AI, etc are vivid examples for the same.

The digitalization boom and the introduction of artificial intelligence have brought attention to the advancements in technology and organizational development over the past few years. When applied, optimization for better resource use, increased data analysis accuracy, increased productivity and efficiency, etc., created a number of new avenues and chances for sustainable development. Innovative sustainable development is the outcome of applying artificial intelligence to development while keeping in mind the sustainable development goals. These definitions will continue to accumulate and will vary greatly. since each theory has its own point of view.

With an emphasis on VIKSHIT BHARAT 2047, we will discuss in this paper how artificial intelligence has proven to be a long-awaited development in organizational

development and how improved analysis and technological advancements are being very helpful in a variety of sectors.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Sustainability, Globalization, Organizational Development, Vikshit Bharat 2047.

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OP 116

A CNN Based Deep Learning Pipeline for Automated Detection and Segmentation of Brain Haemorrhage in 2D CT scans**Mrudula Wani¹, Prakriti Mohapatra², Bhumika Lingait³ and Geetha Narayana⁴
Department of Biomedical Engineering, Vidyalankar Institute of Technology, Mumbai**

Abstract: Brain haemorrhage is a serious and potentially fatal condition requiring rapid and precise diagnosis. This paper introduces a two-stage deep learning pipeline for the automatic detection and segmentation of brain haemorrhages from 2D CT scan images. Convolutional neural networks VGG16 and ResNet50 are individually trained in the first stage to classify CT images as haemorrhagic or normal. Their outputs are combined through an ensemble strategy to leverage the strengths of models, thereby enhancing classification accuracy and robustness. Images identified as haemorrhagic are then passed to a U-Net-based segmentation model in the second stage to localize the regions of bleeding. In contrast to earlier approaches that used pseudomasks, this study utilizes ground truth segmentation masks manually annotated by experts to train the U-Net model, resulting in more reliable and accurate segmentations. The U-Net generates segmentation maps that highlight haemorrhagic areas, and subsequent image processing techniques are applied to extract clinically relevant features such as area, perimeter, and estimated volume of the haemorrhage. These features can assist in diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment planning. Finally, the performance of the system is evaluated quantitatively using metrics such as Dice Coefficient and Intersection over Union (IoU), confirming the accuracy of the segmentation results. This two-stage pipeline aims to support radiologists by delivering fast, consistent, and detailed analysis of brain haemorrhage cases, improving emergency diagnosis workflows and contributing to better patient outcomes.

Keywords: Brain Haemorrhage, Deep learning, CT scan, CNN, VGG16, ResNet50, U-Net, Pseudo mask strategy, Image Segmentation.

OP 117

**Screening, Identification and isolation of Indigenous Microbes for the
Biodegradation of Agricultural Waste****Ratnpriya and Garima Awasthi*****Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University, Uttar Pradesh, Lucknow campus-
226028, Uttar Pradesh, India**

Abstract: The ever increasing accumulation of agricultural wastes such as wheat husk, rice bran and bagasse have left an indelible mark on the environment, particularly in regions with high agri-industrial activity. It has been reported that India produces more than 500 million tonnes of agricultural waste each year, yet only a small portion is presently harnessed for the generation of bioproducts due to its low degradation rate and less release for glucose as a raw material. This study aims to screen, identify and isolate native microbial strains bacteria/fungi, to analyse their potential in degrading lignocellulosic biomass present in these common agricultural waste. The process involves collecting decomposing organic matter from sources such as rotting leaves or bark of trees. The pure cultures of microbes were isolated from rotten and degraded sample by pour plate method. The isolated pure culture of microbial strains were cultured and then analyzed to study their potential for the degrading of wheat husk, wheat straw, and bagasse. Multiple sets of samples are used and each is subjected to different microbes. Their degradation potential of analysed by measuring the glucose concentration released by DNS method. The isolated bacterial strain showing best results were further identified using Gram staining and IMVIC test, whereas the fungi was identified using Lactophenol cotton blue (LPCB) test. This study is directed towards identifying naturally occurring, cost-effective solutions derived from microbes for sustainable waste management. Harnessing the enzymatic capabilities of environmental isolates, this study seeks to contribute to the benefit of both the ecosystem and mankind as it can reduce agricultural waste leading to enhanced soil

quality and therefore, nutritious crops. The outcome of this study is expected to pave the way for future scale-up studies and the formulation of microbial consortia specifically tailored for managing waste. In doing so, it is hoped that it aligns with broader goals of sustainable waste management practices and an overall healthier approach in the agriculture facet.

Keywords: agricultural waste, lignocellulosic, bagasse, bacteria, fungi.

OP 118**Empowering Scheduled Castes Women: The Role of Social Media in Reproductive Health Education in Punjab (India)****Dr. Lakhvir Singh****Assistant Professor, Department of Social work, Punjabi University Patiala**

Abstract: Social media has created a positive impact on information dissemination in every aspect of life, including sexual and reproductive health. Reproductive health is a generic term covering a number of dimensions such as reproductive organs, safe sex relations, safe motherhood, gynecological problems, reproductive rights, STI/RTI, and HIV/AIDS. Sexual and reproductive health is not only about physical wellbeing; it also includes the right to healthy and respectful relationships, health services that are inclusive, safe, appropriate access to accurate information, effective and affordable methods of contraception, and access to services in relation to unplanned pregnancy. The data was collected from secondary sources including journals and articles. Social media provides a platform for women to easily access health information from experts. Social media, including Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, WhatsApp, Twitter, etc., facilitate the creative display of information while simultaneously influencing, motivating, and engaging women on important reproductive health-related issues and correcting misinformation, including taboos, stigma, and superstition. Our review findings suggest that social media promote sexual and reproductive health education, increasing sexual knowledge, contraceptive use, and decreasing unwanted pregnancy, RTI/STI infections and HIV/AIDS. The online social media, including Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, etc., can increase knowledge regarding reproductive health of women. The objective of the present study is to measure the role of social media in promoting the reproductive health of scheduled castes women in Punjab (India).

Keywords: Scheduled Castes, Social Media, Sexual, Reproductive Health and Education.

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OP 119**Standardization of Braille Script for Regional Languages: A Critical Need****Charanjiv Singh Saroa****Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Punjabi University, Patiala, 147002**

Abstract: Braille has long been a cornerstone of accessible communication for the visually impaired, offering independence and literacy. However, in a linguistically diverse country like India, the absence of a standardized Braille script for regional languages has led to serious challenges in education and content creation. Currently, most Braille representations for Indian languages, including Punjabi, are based on ASCII encoding systems. While effective in earlier stages of digital development, ASCII fails to capture the full range of characters and conjuncts present in regional scripts.

With the rise of Unicode as a universal standard for digital text encoding, there is an urgent need to adapt and refine Braille systems accordingly. Unicode provides broader support for complex scripts, making it essential to realign Braille transcription to ensure accuracy, consistency, and scalability across platforms. This paper focuses primarily on the Punjabi language, examining the inconsistencies that arise due to the lack of standard Unicode-based Braille representation.

We propose a framework for developing a standardized Braille script for Punjabi that aligns with the Unicode system, paving the way for integration into digital tools, screen readers, and refreshable Braille displays. Standardization would significantly improve educational resources, streamline content creation, and promote nationwide inclusivity for the visually impaired. A collaborative approach involving educators, linguists,

technologists, and policy-makers is crucial for building a unified Braille ecosystem for all regional languages.

Keywords: Braille, Unicode, Regional Languages, Standardization, Punjabi, Assistive Technology, Inclusive Education

OP 120**Socio-economic analysis of the agrarian movement in Punjab: 1920-47****Jagdeep Singh****Department of History, University College Miranpur, Patiala, 147001, Punjab, India**

Abstract: The paper analyses the social and economic foundation of the agricultural movement in Punjab from 1920 to 1947. An examination of the agricultural framework in the province would elucidate the socio-economic stratification of Punjab society and reveal the principal conflicts that catalysed the peasant movement. Despite several regional differences, the primary characteristic of Punjab's fundamental economy was its swift transition to colonialism by the late 19th century. This framework delineates major transformations in the agricultural economy. The study explores the development and framework of landlordism, as well as technical advancements in agricultural output. The significant indebtedness of Punjab's peasants is well-documented, although its relevance to output is primarily examined in this paper. Likewise, Punjab has not advanced significantly in modern industry, which had previously shown promise in the region. Consequently, post-1918, the burgeoning population exerted pressure on agriculture in the province. The negative repercussions have been identified, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of agricultural issues and the agrarian movement.

Keywords: socio-economic background, Agrarian movement, colonialism, peasant, Punjab

OP 121**Genetic Diversity studies using ISSR and SSR markers on 17 single cultivars of
Tuberose (*Polianthes tuberosa* L.)****Loveneet Kaur****Department of Botany and Environment Science, Mata Gujri College, Fatehgarh Sahib
140407, Punjab, India**

Abstract: This study aims to assess the genetic diversity of *Polianthes tuberosa* L. germplasms procured from different research institutes in North-West India, based on morphological variations. The molecular characteristics of 17 single cultivars collected and preserved at S. S. Bir Botanical Gardens, Punjabi University, Patiala, were analyzed. Eleven ISSR and twelve SSR markers generated distinct, reproducible polymorphic bands and displayed significant efficacy in analyzing variation across tuberose cultivars. Genetic diversity was studied based on various parameters like number of polymorphic bands, average number of polymorphic bands per primer, the percentage of polymorphic bands, the effective multiplex ratio, resolving power and polymorphic information content. A dendrogram was prepared based on genetic diversity according to their similarity indices. The Jaccard dissimilarity coefficient for pooled ISSR and SSR data indicated a dissimilarity range of 0.15 to 0.99 among the examined accessions. Consequently, the current studies effectively threw light on the genetic diversity of tuberose genotypes using various DNA markers. The present study not only offers critical insights into genetic diversity but also advocates for the large-scale cultivation of this valuable aromatic plant, which may be informative for future research and contribute to crop diversification, consequently saving the deteriorating agricultural economy and environment of Punjab.

Keywords: Genetic diversity, ISSR, *Polianthes tuberosa* L., SSR, Tuberose.

OP 122

Two Systems, One Goal: Exploring Healthcare Utilization in India and Canada**Harpreet Singh¹ and Hargopal Singh²**¹Research Scholar, Department of Social Work, Punjabi University,²Govt. Teacher, Govt. High School, Alamdipur, Patiala

Abstract: Healthcare is essential not only for individual well-being but also for the economic benefit of a nation. It is the government's responsibility to fund healthcare; however, due to financial constraints, governments often cannot fully meet the healthcare needs of their populations. In such cases, private companies step in to bridge the gap between demand and supply. Canada is a developed country in North America with a population of 37 million, and it operates a single-payer healthcare system, where insurance is provided by the government. In contrast, India, a developing country in South Asia with a population of 1.37 billion, faces financial constraints and lacks a universal insurance system. Health service utilization is influenced by a variety of factors, including socio-economic status, education, geographic location, government policies, healthcare infrastructure, and cultural attitudes towards health. By examining both Punjab (India) and Ontario (Canada), this study will identify the factors that either encourage or hinder healthcare utilization in each country. In Punjab (India), a large rural population and socio-economic disparities often lead to inequitable access to healthcare. Conversely, Ontario (Canada), with its universal healthcare system, strives to ensure healthcare availability for all citizens, though challenges such as wait times, geographic disparities, and the healthcare needs of Indigenous populations persist. This study will contribute to a better understanding of accessibility and availability and how health systems address equity and the barriers different populations face in utilizing healthcare services.

Keywords: Healthcare, Utilisation, Accessibility, Availability and Affordability.

OP 123

**Empowering Rural Health Governance: The Role of VHSNCs and Social Work
in Punjab (India)****Dr. Harjinder Kaur****Medical Social Worker, Department of OBST & GYNAE****Post-Graduate Institute of Medical Education & Research, Chandigarh (PGIMER)**

Abstract: The National Rural Health Mission, which is now an Urban Health Mission, firmly recognises the value of community involvement in rural health care in order to improve health outcomes and offer high-quality services to rural women, children, and the impoverished. Improving social conditions generally and helping individuals, families, and communities build relationships with one another are the two main objectives of social work. In these particular intervention areas, researchers must develop suitable models of community participation and have practitioners accept these models in their respective contexts for social work practice to be implemented successfully. The production and exchange of academic knowledge is also essential to this process. Through their own involvement, the social worker may significantly improve the way these local bodies operate and the rural population's access to health services. In addition to discussing the necessity and significance of social work intervention in the field of rural health, the current paper focuses on the role that social workers play in improving rural residents' access to health services and improving the functioning of VHSNCs.

Keywords: Community Participation, National Rural Health Mission, Urban Health Mission, Social Work Intervention and Rural Health.

OP 124

Revitalizing the Punjabi Language: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for Linguistic Preservation and Promotion**Dr. Rajwinder Singh**

Assistant Professor, Department of Punjabi, Punjabi University Patiala

Abstract: Due to globalization and the dominance of major languages, the Punjabi language, which has a rich cultural past, is facing challenges from diminishing usage among younger generations. This essay investigates the ways in which artificial intelligence (AI) can revolutionize Punjabi's revival and preservation. Punjabi can be made more approachable and interesting for speakers around the world by utilizing AI-driven technologies like chatbots, speech recognition, machine translation, and tailored learning platforms. AI can also improve content development, support linguistic diversity, and digitize historical materials. In order to support language revitalization initiatives, this study looks at current AI applications for Punjabi, identifies weaknesses, and suggests creative fixes. The results demonstrate how AI can help close technological and generational gaps, ensuring Punjabi prospers in the digital era.

Keywords: Punjabi Language, Artificial Intelligence, Language Preservation, Machine Translation and Speech Recognition.

OP 125

The War Tactics and Military Strategy of the Sikhs up to 1790

Dr. Balraj Singh

Assistant Professor

Department of History & Historical Studies, Punjabi University Patiala

Abstract: This paper looks at how Sikh military strategy evolved from the early days of Sikhism to the founding and functioning of the Dal Khalsa and Sikh misals by 1790. The Sikhs were a pacifist religious sect that became a formidable military force as a result of oppression by the Mughals and Afghans. The research explores the doctrines laid by the Sikh Gurus, the organized resistance under Banda Singh Bahadur, and the guerrilla warfare strategies adopted by the Sikh misls. Special emphasis is placed on the ethical framework of Sikh warfare and the distinctive features of Sikh military planning, including the use of consensus-based leadership and strategic guerrilla operations.

Keywords: Sikh Military Strategy, War Tactics, Banda Singh Bahadur, Dal Khalsa and Ethical Warfare

OP 126

Sewa as Sacred Duty: Exploring the Concept of Social Service in Sikhism**Dr. Gurjinder Singh**

Assistant Professor of Religion

Patel Memorial National College, Rajpura, Patiala

Abstract: Sewa, or social service, is a fundamental aspect of Sikhism and is closely linked to the religion's moral and spiritual principles. The teachings of the Sikh gurus and the sacred text, the Guru Granth Sahib, serve as its foundation. *Sewa* means helping others without expecting anything in return, showing kindness, equality, and love. In other words, *Sewa* is more than just charity; it is a form of worship and a way of life. Activities such as free meals, health care, and he

lp during disasters are examples of how Sikhism supports social welfare. At the core of these activities are the principles of selflessness and helping everyone (Sarbat da Bhala). All things considered, Sewa in Sikhism is a strong social service model that ties faith to action and provides significant insights for the modern world. In this context, the present research uses a historical method, studying Sikh scriptures, the lives of the Gurus, and institutions like *Langar* (free kitchen) and *Gurdwara* (Sikh temple) services. In this context, the present study looks and exploring the idea of *Sewa* in Sikhism as well as focusing on its meaning, history and also how it is practiced today.

Keywords: Sikhism, Sewa, Social Service, Langar, Aid and Sikhism

OP 127**Role of ethical practices in modern business****Mohini Gupta****Assistant Professor, Department of Management Lucknow Public College of
Professional Studies, Lucknow**

Abstract: The purpose of the paper is to investigate ethics as one of the fundamental elements of the modern business world and how ethical matters may influence stakeholders' trust or lead to a company's success. The study meets the growing demand for a better understanding of ethics in an increasingly changing world economy, when firms are compelled to be more responsible. Good business ethics have been shown to have tremendous returns on a firm's reputation, good customer stickiness, and high employee satisfaction all of which are key success drivers for companies based on secondary research findings obtained from internet databases and reference journals. However, the same study shows that companies are unable to uphold ethical principles at all times, particularly in competitive business settings. This paper looks at how ethics can be incorporated into business strategy and how this is so relevant in the business world today as a means of achieving sustainable growth and in business competition, as a means of being competitive. The study dwells on the reality that business ethics have become the focal point of governance and management today. As the markets are increasingly globalized through advances in technologies applied to consuming digital media, customers, investors and government agencies are compelling companies to behave as ethically as possible. Openness, fairness and social responsibility are among some of the policies of business ethics thought to be vital in ensuring stakeholders' confidence and success. Setting high standards of behaviour and firm regulations and the risks and vices of venturing into different business activities such as corporate governance and compliance, environmental sustainability and social responsibilities are all part of business ethics.

Keywords: Business Ethics, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Stakeholder Trust, Sustainable Business Practices, Ethical Leadership, Corporate Governance.

OP 128

Assessment of Mental health in 1st year medical undergraduates: A questionnaire-based study**Dr. Fatema Johra* and Dr. Mummadi Padma Geethanjali**
Department of Physiology, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam-530002

Abstract: Medical education is believed to be one of the toughest journeys one can have. The journey to be a doctor is not a cakewalk as it demands a lot of dedication and sacrifices and the students often compromise with their physical and psychological well-being¹. Their mental health is significantly affected throughout the journey. Developing countries like India where mental disorders are prominent is about 15 percent of the total population and under these circumstances the physiological well-being for the doctors is supposed to be highly relevant as they are the primary health care provider to these large masses². Hence, in this aspect good mental health of a medical student is incredibly important and needs to be assessed on an ongoing basis. A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 125 first-year MBBS students. Mental health was assessed by using a self-report questionnaire, DASS-213. Prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress was found as 64.8 %, 63.2 % and 61.6 %, respectively. It was found that the male students were more affected as compared to the female students and it was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ level. However, there was no significant difference found in hosteller and day scholar students for mental health scores. In our study the prevalence of depression, anxiety and stress was found significant. In view of the above, a plan of action should be prepared in the first year MBBS itself to reduce or minimize the mental health issues among the students. It may be personal support, care and counselling.

Keywords: mental health, MBBS students, prevalence, depression, stress, anxiety, medical education.

OP 129

Breast Cancer Biomarkers Today: Trends, Perspectives and Challenges¹Priti Menon ²Dr. Shilpa Raina

Department of Biochemistry, SVU, Gajraula

Email: pritiharish@gmail.com

Background:

Breast cancer biomarker research is rapidly evolving. Liquid biopsies (ctDNA), microRNA (miRNA) panels, and imaging-based AI/radiomics approaches are enhancing detection, prognostication, and therapy selection in early and advanced breast cancer.

Methods:

We conducted a structured review of studies published in 2023–2025, focusing on circulating biomarkers (miRNAs, ctDNA), commercial liquid biopsy market data, and AI-driven imaging studies in breast cancer.

Results:

miRNA-based liquid biomarkers show high diagnostic accuracy: a panel of miR-205, miR-155 and miR-21 in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) achieved AUCs of 96.1%, 94.9%, and 97.1% across three cohorts (total $n \approx 190$), with sensitivity and specificity consistently high ($P < 0.0001$). In plasma, a four-miRNA panel (miR-195, miR-210, miR-21, miR-16) showed AUC ≈ 0.898 , sensitivity $\sim 71.4\%$, and specificity 100%. In TCGA-based tissue profiling ($n=755$ vs 86 controls), a 5-miRNA signature (miR-139, miR-21, miR-96, miR-183, miR-10b) yielded AUC 0.98, sensitivity 96.95%, specificity 100%. A study in Indian women with stage I–II breast cancer ($n=60$ patients, 20 controls) reported miR-21 and miR-205 outperform classical CEA/CA15-3 markers by ROC AUC range 0.656–0.993.

ctDNA and liquid biopsy adoption in breast cancer is expanding: NHS England has rolled out ctDNA testing for ESR1 mutations, benefiting $\sim 1,100$ advanced breast cancer patients annually, reducing decision latency by ~ 16 days, and improving access to

elacestrant therapy (average progression-free duration 8.6 vs 1.9 months). The breast cancer liquid biopsy market was valued at USD 330.8 M in 2024, projected to reach USD 1.1 B by 2030 (CAGR 21.9%).

AI-based imaging (radiomics) is enhancing diagnostic sensitivity and specificity beyond traditional mammography or MRI, enabling subtype differentiation and outcome prediction in preliminary research.

Conclusions:

Trends include robust performance of miRNA panels (AUC 0.90–0.99) and expanding real-world use of ctDNA in treatment monitoring and mutation detection. Perspectives include integration of multimodal biomarkers against genomic and imaging data to personalize care. Challenges remain in standardizing assays across populations, validating across diverse ethnic cohorts, ensuring clinical utility in early-stage detection, reducing costs, and proving mortality benefit in large trials.

Keywords: Breast cancer, Biomarkers, radiomics, ctDNA, miRNA

OP 130

Adoption of Ind AS (Accounting Standard): An Appraisal of The Impact On Financial Performance Of Bharat Heavy Electricals Limited (BHEL)¹Mrs. Mayuri, ²Prof. Rajeev Shukla¹Department of Commerce, Government Degree College Pachmohani, Siddharth University, Siddharth Nagar, 272152²Department of Commerce, Vidyant Hindu PG College, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, 226018**Abstract**

The present study is based on the BHEL as one of the leading public sector enterprises which has significant impact on engineering and manufacturing capabilities of India in a variety of industry sectors, including power, transportation, renewables, water, oil and gas, aerospace, and defense. The study is conducted on financial performance of BHEL after adoption of Ind AS for the period of 5 years i.e. 2020-21 to 2024-25. The ratio analysis is used to know about the liquidity, profitability and efficiency of BHEL. In this study, Current Ratios, Liquid Ratios, Return on Assets, Return on Equity, Debtors Turnover Ratios and Creditors Turnover Ratios are analyze and interpret the performance of BHEL for the period of 5 years.

Keywords: Current Ratios, Liquid Ratios, Return on Assets, Return on Equity, Creditors Turnover Ratios, Debtors Turnover Ratios, Ind AS.

OP 131

Impact of IT-Enabled Services Expenditure on Decision Quality in Corporate Governance: An Empirical Analysis through Financial Performance Metrics**¹Namrata Chugh and ²Dr. Deepak Kapur****Asst. Professor, GGSDS College, Chandigarh, India****Professor, UBS, Panjab University, Chandigarh, India**

Abstract: The abstract of this research paper provides an overview of the study, which investigates the intricate relationship between IT-enabled services (ITES) expenditure and decision quality within the realm of corporate governance. This investigation is undertaken with particular emphasis on financial performance metrics namely, Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Investment (ROI) that are employed as indicators of decision quality. The study offers insights into the complexities of how technology investments influence governance outcomes.

As organizations allocate substantial resources to technology, questions regarding the true value of these investments particularly in terms of their impact on decision-making at the board level have become increasingly pertinent. This study sought to address these questions through an empirical analysis, utilizing a sample drawn from IT companies in India, with data meticulously collected from the ProwessIQ database.

The research design was quantitative and empirical in nature, employing multiple regression analysis to quantify the relationship between ITES expenditure, measured as capital expenditure (Capex) relative to total assets, and decision quality, as reflected in ROA and ROI. The analysis revealed that ITES expenditure had minimal and statistically insignificant influence on both ROA and ROI, with low R-squared values and weak negative correlations indicating that Capex as a percentage of total assets did not significantly impact these financial performance metrics.

The findings of my present study challenge the prevailing assumption that higher ITES expenditure automatically leads to improved decision quality within corporate

governance. Instead, the study suggests that the relationship between technology investments and decision outcomes is more complex and may be influenced by a multitude of factors, including organizational culture, board expertise, and the nature of the specific technology being implemented.

The research highlights the need for a more nuanced understanding of how ITES investments are integrated into governance processes. The study also identifies several avenues for future research, including the exploration of non-financial metrics, the examination of a broader range of industries, and the consideration of emerging technologies such as blockchain and artificial intelligence in shaping corporate governance outcomes.

Keywords: Decision Quality, Corporate Governance, Empirical Analysis, Financial Performance Metrics

OP 132

Role of Serum Irisin and Galectin-3 in Subclinical Hypothyroidism and Primary Hypothyroidism compared to Euthyroid Individuals-A Cross-Sectional Study**¹Roshni,¹ Vinitha R Pai*****¹Dept of Biochemistry, Yenepoya Medical College, Mangalore**

Abstract: Primary hypothyroidism (elevated TSH, low fT4) affects 1–2% of the population, while Subclinical Hypothyroidism (SCH) (elevated TSH, normal fT4) occurs in 3–10% of the population. Irisin, a 112-amino-acid polypeptide cleaved from Fibronectin Type III Domain Containing Protein 5 (FNDC5), and galectin-3, a beta-galactoside-binding lectin involved in inflammation and cell processes, may influence thyroid dysfunction. However, their roles and associations with cardiometabolic risk factors in thyroid disorders remain inadequately understood. This study aims to evaluate the role of Irisin, Galectin-3 in SCH and Primary Hypothyroidism as compared to Euthyroid Individuals. This cross-sectional study included 120 participants: SCH(n=40), primary hypothyroidism(n=40), and euthyroid controls(n=40), screened at tertiary care hospitals in Mangaluru. Serum levels of Irisin and Galectin-3 were measured using Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA). Thyroid function tests (TSH, fT4), lipid parameters -Total Cholesterol (TC), Low Density Lipoprotein (LDL), High Density Lipoprotein (HDL), Triglycerides (TG), and Very Low-Density Lipoprotein (VLDL)-were analyzed. Data expressed as median (Inter-Quartile Range). Kruskal–Wallis test was performed for comparisons, and Spearman’s rank correlation was assessed. Decrease in serum irisin level: control>SCH>primary hypothyroid groups, the differences were not significant ($p>0.05$). Galectin-3 levels did not show any significant variation among the study groups ($p>0.05$). There was weak correlation with thyroid and lipid profile. None of the correlations were statistically significant ($p>0.05$). Although not significant there was a trend in this cohort. Further studies with larger sample size including tissue level expression data may help to explore their potential roles in thyroid dysfunction.

Keywords: subclinical hypothyroidism, primary hypothyroidism, irisin, galectin, hypothyroidism, lipid profile, thyroid hormones.

OP 133

Personalized Medicine in Oral Cancer**Dr. Saloni Verma****Senior Resident, Department of Oral Pathology & Microbiology, King George's Medical University, Lucknow**

Abstract: Oral cancer is one of the most common cancers in the world, and more than 90% of these cases are oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC). Traditional treatments like surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy have saved many lives, but they often follow a one-size-fits-all approach. Today, personalized medicine offers a new way to fight oral cancer by designing treatments tailored to each patient. This approach uses information about the patient's genes, tumor biology, and lifestyle to find the best possible treatment, improving success rates and reducing side effects. Recent technologies, such as next-generation sequencing (NGS) and advanced laboratory models, have made this possible. For example, 3D tumor models like organoids, spheroids, and patient-derived xenografts (PDX) are now being used to study how oral cancer grows and responds to drugs in a way that is much closer to what happens inside the human body. These models allow doctors and scientists to test different treatments in the lab before giving them to the patient, making therapy safer and more effective.

Personalized medicine also combines new techniques such as liquid biopsies (testing blood or saliva for cancer signals), genetic testing, and even immunotherapy (boosting the patient's own immune system to fight cancer). While challenges remain, such as cost and complexity, these advances are changing the future of oral cancer care. This abstract highlights how personalized medicine is improving research and treatment in oral cancer by combining modern genetics, 3D cancer models, and targeted therapies. These approaches promise better treatment outcomes and quality of life for patients.

Keywords: Personalized medicine; Oral cancer; OSCC; targeted therapy; 3D models.

OP 134

Sectoral Disparity and Timing Distortion Model (SDTDM): A Model for Assessing Sectoral and Temporal Inequities in NPS Tax Treatment**¹Danish Feroz,²Prof. Somesh Kumar Shukla****¹Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226007****²Professor, Department of Commerce, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226007**

Abstract: This study presents the Sectoral Disparity and Timing Distortion Model (SDTDM) to systematically examine inequities arising under Section 80CCD(2) of the Income Tax Act, 1961. This provision governs employer contributions to the National Pension System (NPS), permitting tax deductions up to 14% of salary for government employees and only 10% for non-government employees. Additionally, it restricts deductions to the year of payment, regardless of when the contribution was accrued. Together, these structural rules create tax disparities that penalize taxpayers based on sector affiliation and the timing of contribution.

Using a primary dataset of 192 assesseees, evaluated across two financial years (2023–24 and 2024–25), the study simulates tax liability outcomes for both actual and hypothetical sectoral treatments. Backlog contributions common due to administrative delays frequently breach annual deduction caps when paid in a lump sum, leading to excess tax liability without an actual increase in income. By applying the SDTDM framework, the study captures how sectoral policies and timing constraints distort horizontal equity, particularly for taxpayers in private, PSU, cooperative, autonomous bodies, etc.

The findings demonstrate that deduction cap asymmetries and rigid timing rules disproportionately burden compliant taxpayers outside the government sector. The study recommends uniform deduction limits, accrual-based deduction eligibility, and greater administrative clarity to foster a more equitable and neutral pension-linked tax regime.

Keywords: National Pension System (NPS), Section 80CCD (2), tax distortion, backlog contributions, sectoral disparity, timing mismatch, SDTDM.

OP 135

The Relationship between Joy of Missing Out and Self-Compassion in Adolescents: A Correlational Study**Harsha Joshi****Research Scholar, Department of Psychology
Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Udaipur, Rajasthan**

Abstract: This study examined the relationship between Joy of Missing Out (JOMO) and self-compassion among adolescents, an area with limited prior research. While JOMO is often portrayed as a positive construct associated with mindfulness and well-being, it may also reflect withdrawal or avoidance in younger populations. A sample of adolescents ($N = 80$) completed the 13-item JOMO Scale and the Self-Compassion Scale–Short Form (SCS-SF). Pearson’s correlation was used to test for an association between the two constructs. Results revealed a significant correlation, $r(78) = -0.288$, $p = .0095$. These findings provide preliminary evidence that JOMO and self-compassion are meaningfully related in adolescents, though the direction of this relationship suggests that JOMO may not always function as a purely adaptive construct at this developmental stage.

Keywords: JOMO, self compassion, adolescence

OP-136**Association of circulating miRNA-210 with Insulin Resistance and Its Predictive Utility in Metabolic Syndrome Using ELISA-Based Detection****Neha Dharmesh Sheth*, Ivvala Anand Shaker, Jay ranade****Department of Biochemistry, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences and Research,
Parul University, Gujarat, India****Department of Biochemistry, Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Science &
Research, swaminarayan university, gujarat, india****Research Officer, Msc Biotechnology, Jai Research Foundation, Valvada, Vapi,
Gujarat, India****Abstract****Background:**

Metabolic syndrome (MetS) involves a cluster of metabolic disturbances linked to insulin resistance (IR). Circulating microRNA-210 (miRNA-210), a hypoxia-responsive regulatory RNA, is implicated in metabolic dysfunction. While qPCR is commonly used for miRNA detection, recent advancements allow quantification of miRNA-210 using ELISA-based assays, offering a more accessible and rapid alternative.

Objective:

To investigate the association of circulating miRNA-210 levels with insulin resistance in MetS individuals using an ELISA-based detection method and evaluate its diagnostic utility through ROC analysis.

Methods:

In this cross-sectional study, 150 adults aged 30–55 years were categorized into MetS and control groups based on NCEP-ATP III criteria. Serum miRNA-210 was quantified using a commercial ELISA kit. Fasting glucose and insulin were used to calculate HOMA-IR. ROC analysis was performed to assess the predictive power of miRNA-210 for IR and MetS.

**Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation
(ICMRI-2025)**

Results:

miRNA-210 levels measured by ELISA were significantly elevated in MetS participants compared to controls ($p < 0.01$). A significant positive correlation was found between miRNA-210 and HOMA-IR ($r = 0.43$, $p < 0.001$). ROC analysis showed an AUC of 0.81 for predicting insulin resistance and 0.77 for MetS diagnosis.

Conclusion:

miRNA-210 quantified using ELISA demonstrates a strong association with insulin resistance and shows promise as a non-invasive biomarker for early detection of MetS.

Keywords: miRNA-210, ELISA, insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome, HOMA-IR, biomarker, ROC curve

OP-137**Blockchain Technology in Financial Management****Agrima Singh****Thematic research, Industry analytics and Policy advisory, HDFC Bank**

Abstract: The advent of blockchain technology has ushered in a transformative era in financial management, presenting a novel paradigm for secure, transparent, and efficient financial transactions. This research paper delves into the profound impact of blockchain on the traditional landscape of financial management and explores the challenges and opportunities it brings to the forefront.

The paper commences by providing a comprehensive overview of blockchain technology, elucidating its decentralized nature and cryptographic principles that underpin its reliability. Subsequently, the discussion navigates through the implications of blockchain in financial management, emphasizing its potential to redefine trust and eliminate intermediaries in transactions.

A critical examination of blockchain applications within financial systems reveals its role in enhancing transparency, reducing fraud, and streamlining processes. The study further investigates real-world use cases, drawing insights from early adopters in the finance industry to exemplify the practical implications and benefits experienced.

Acknowledging the nascent stage of blockchain adoption, the paper addresses challenges such as scalability, regulatory considerations, and interoperability. Additionally, it explores the integration of smart contracts and their impact on automating financial agreements, paving the way for innovative financial instruments and decentralized finance (DeFi) ecosystems.

By synthesizing theoretical frameworks, empirical evidence, and case studies, this research contributes a nuanced understanding of blockchain's potential in financial management. The paper concludes with strategic recommendations for financial institutions, policymakers, and industry stakeholders on navigating the uncharted terrain of this technological frontier. As the financial landscape undergoes a seismic shift towards decentralization, this research serves as a timely and valuable resource for academics, practitioners, and policymakers seeking to comprehend and harness the potential of blockchain in shaping the future of financial management.

Keywords: Blockchain technology, Decentralization, Interoperability, Decentralized finance (DeFi), Financial management

OP 138**Diabetes Mellitus: A Comprehensive Overview of Risk Factors and Prevention Strategies****Shailya Preeti and Rahul Kumar****Department of Microbiology and Department of Paramedical Sciences
Radha Govind University, Ramgarh, Usha Martin University, Ranchi, Jharkhand**

Abstract: Diabetes mellitus is a complicated, long-term metabolic disease marked by persistently high blood sugar levels brought on by deficiencies in either the action or secretion of insulin, or both. It affects millions of people globally and contributes significantly to morbidity and death, making it an increasing global health problem. Type 1 diabetes (T1DM), which is autoimmune in origin, Type 2 diabetes (T2DM), which is closely linked to hereditary and lifestyle factors, and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), which develops during pregnancy, are the three main categories into which the illness is divided. Of them, Type 2 diabetes is mostly avoidable and makes up over 90% of cases. Diabetes develops and progresses due to a number of risk factors. These risk factors are often divided into two categories: modifiable and non-modifiable. Advanced age, ethnicity, a family history of diabetes, and genetic susceptibility are risk factors that cannot be changed. Obesity, poor eating habits, physical inactivity, smoking, excessive alcohol use, high blood pressure, and raised cholesterol are examples of modifiable risk factors, or those that may be impacted by behavior and surroundings. In addition, socioeconomic position, urbanization, and psychological stress have been recognized as new risk factors, especially in developing nations. The pathophysiology of diabetes is significantly influenced by the interplay between environmental variables and genetic predisposition. The beginning of Type 2 diabetes has been successfully postponed or prevented by lifestyle therapies that increase physical activity, improve nutrition quality, and reduce obesity. Additionally, to reduce consequences including cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, nephropathy, and retinopathy, high-risk patients must have regular screening and early diagnosis. In

conclusion, prevention and treatment of diabetes depend on an awareness of the wide variety of risk factors linked to the disease. To lessen the growing prevalence of diabetes worldwide, public health policy should prioritize access to healthcare, behavioral modification, and education. To create individualized and focused preventative interventions, further study on the interplay between genetics and the environment is essential.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Risk Factors, Type 2 Diabetes, Lifestyle Modification, Prevention Strategies.

OP 139**A Study on Altered Scapulohumeral Rhythm among Basketball Players:
Biomechanical Implications and Performance Impact****G Md Rayyan****Student, Garden City University, Bangalore****Abstract****Background & Purpose**

Basketball players perform frequent overhead movements such as shooting, passing, and rebounding, which place repetitive stress on the shoulder complex. Scapulohumeral rhythm (SHR) describes the coordinated movement between the scapula and humerus during arm elevation, generally following a 2:1 ratio. Changes in this rhythm can influence biomechanics and athletic performance.

Objectives

This study explores how participation in basketball affects scapulohumeral rhythm patterns and examines the related biomechanical adaptations and performance consequences.

Methods

Basketball players were assessed for scapular and humeral motion during arm elevation tasks and compared to age-matched non-athlete controls. Postural parameters, including spinal alignment, head posture, and pelvic tilt, were analysed. The influence of factors such as age, height, hand dominance, and fatigue on SHR was also examined.

Results

Basketball players exhibited reduced scapular upward rotation and lower SHR ratios, particularly in their dominant arm. These adaptations were accompanied by greater

lateral spinal inclination and altered sagittal plane alignment, including forward head posture and pelvic tilt changes. Fatigue led to further reductions in SHR ratios during repetitive shoulder elevation, indicating compensatory scapular adjustments to maintain movement despite glenohumeral fatigue.

Conclusion

Altered scapulohumeral rhythm in basketball players appears to be a functional adaptation to the demands of their sport. However, these changes may reduce mechanical efficiency, affect shot accuracy, and increase the risk of shoulder overuse injuries. Targeted scapular stabilization and endurance training are recommended to support optimal shoulder mechanics and consistent performance.

Keywords

Scapulohumeral rhythm, basketball players, biomechanics, scapular dyskinesia, overhead sports, performance, shoulder adaptations, physiotherapy

OP 140**Work Related Thoracic Kyphosis among IT Professionals**Subin Saju Mathew¹, Amanda Dominic², Mohammed Najid³¹III Semester Student, Garden City University, Bangalore²III Semester Student, Garden City University, Bangalore³III Semester Student, Garden City University, Bangalore

Abstract: This study aims to evaluate postural patterns among professionals working in IT sectors using the Plumb line method. It investigates the association between postural deviations or abnormalities and musculoskeletal pain. The analysis explores how occupational demands and poor ergonomics contribute to postural issues. The primary objective is to identify and understand musculoskeletal problems related to postural patterns in IT professionals. This research provides valuable insights for individuals working in the IT sector, helping them recognise the root causes of their physical discomfort. Ultimately, it promotes better workplace ergonomics, improves the work environment, and supports a healthier balance between mental work pressure and physical well-being.

The analysis revealed that over 76% of IT professionals exhibited various types of postural abnormalities. A significant proportion showed clear signs of postural deviations, with kyphosis being the most prevalent condition. The data indicated a strong correlation between the severity of postural issues and the frequency of musculoskeletal pain. Participants with more pronounced abnormalities commonly reported back pain and neck pain, particularly noticeable during rest or sleep. These findings suggest that prolonged sitting, poor ergonomic workstation setups, repetitive movements, and inadequate postural habits are likely contributors to the development of kyphosis and related discomfort.

The statistics show a significant association between occupational groups and the type of postural deviation. However, certain postural deviations were exhibited only in a few individuals. Females reported a higher incidence of pain compared to males, with pain intensifying during daily activities such as cleaning and cooking. The pain was more

pronounced during movement. This may be attributed to physiological differences including spinal anatomy, pelvic structure, hormonal cycles, and muscle fibre composition, along with behavioural factors such as frequent multitasking.

Keywords: Postural patterns, IT professionals, Plumb line method, musculoskeletal pain, kyphosis.

OP-141**Role of Artificial Intelligence in Making Financial Decisions****¹Km Rajlakshmi Chaurasiya, ²Dr. Ravi Pratap Singh****¹Research Scholar, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur - 273009, U.P. Department of Commerce****²Professor, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur-273009, U.P. Department of Commerce**

Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) has an enormous impact on how people and companies make financial decisions these days. Artificial intelligence (AI) is the use of computer systems that can think like humans, learn from data, and make well-informed decisions. AI can help businesses minimize financial risks, detect banking fraud, identify the best investment options, and assess a borrower's loan eligibility, among other uses in the financial sector.

Robo-advisors are artificial intelligence (AI) tools that provide suitable investment options for users based on their financial objectives and situation. Banks and insurance companies also use AI to speed up application processing, check customer credit scores, and identify unusual transactions that could be a fraud.

AI can evaluate enormous amounts of financial data in a few seconds, allowing experts to make decisions more quickly and accurately. Additionally, it minimizes human error and saves time. However, there are certain difficulties. Biased data may produce unfair results when AI systems are trained. AI needs a lot of personal financial data to work effectively, which raises privacy concerns as well.

This paper investigates the influence of artificial intelligence on financial decision-making. It describes the benefits, such as speed, accuracy, and automation, as well as the risks, such as a lack of transparency and data security. The study concludes that while AI offers numerous advantages, its application should be regulated and controlled to make sure that everyone gets an equal portion of all these advantages.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Financial Decision-Making, Robo-Advisors, Credit Scoring, Risk Management.

OP-142**Comparative evaluation of effectiveness of Tutorial and Fishbowl small group teaching methods among medical undergraduates****¹Abhinav Srivastava, ²Nitesh Mohan, ³Shalini Chandra****¹Professor and Head, Department of ENT, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh****²Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh****³Professor and Head, Department of Pharmacology, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh****Corresponding Author: Abhinav Srivastava Professor and Head, Department of ENT, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh****Abstract****Introduction**

The small group teaching batch is becoming larger with increase in the undergraduate seats. In large strength of small group teaching, the purpose of interaction is not met. Discussion is confined to limited students and rest are not involved in the session. There is a need of a method which increases active participation with active listening with overall involvement of the class. The study was conducted to assess the two different methods of small group teaching and to determine the efficacy of Fish bowl method over tutorial in terms of motivation, interaction and level of satisfaction among students and faculty.

Methodology

The interventional study was conducted for a period of 3 months comprising of 404 students MBBS students. The teaching method employed as intervention was Fishbowl method and the same was compared with Tutorial. The analysis was made using a validated questionnaire method for both student and faculty.

Results and observations

The participating students found fishbowl method to be more interacting as more than 80% of students rated 4 or more on Likert scale. The mean score on Likert scale for the satisfaction

response was found to be less than 4 for both the methodologies. More than 80% of the faculty felt that students were more motivated to study in tutorial in comparison to fishbowl where only 68.75% rated 4 or more on Likert scale to fishbowl against 81.25% for tutorial. They felt students to be more anxious in fishbowl than tutorials. Most of the student's preferred selection of the teaching method as per the requirement and content of the topic for the study and the response for the same was 42.04%.

Conclusion

Both the short group teaching methods (Fishbowl and Tutorial) are effective in conveying what it intent to convey to the learners and the selection of the method can be decided based on the need of the topic.

Keywords: Tutorial, Fishbowl, Small group teaching

OP-143**Diabetes Mellitus: A Comprehensive Overview of Risk Factors and Prevention Strategies****Shailya Preeti and Rahul Kumar****Department of Microbiology and Department of Paramedical Sciences
Radha Govind University, Ramgarh, Usha Martin University, Ranchi, Jharkhand**

Abstract: Diabetes mellitus is a complicated, long-term metabolic disease marked by persistently high blood sugar levels brought on by deficiencies in either the action or secretion of insulin, or both. It affects millions of people globally and contributes significantly to morbidity and death, making it an increasing global health problem. Type 1 diabetes (T1DM), which is autoimmune in origin, Type 2 diabetes (T2DM), which is closely linked to hereditary and lifestyle factors, and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), which develops during pregnancy, are the three main categories into which the illness is divided. Of them, Type 2 diabetes is mostly avoidable and makes up over 90% of cases. Diabetes develops and progresses due to a number of risk factors. These risk factors are often divided into two categories: modifiable and non-modifiable. Advanced age, ethnicity, a family history of diabetes, and genetic susceptibility are risk factors that cannot be changed. Obesity, poor eating habits, physical inactivity, smoking, excessive alcohol use, high blood pressure, and raised cholesterol are examples of modifiable risk factors, or those that may be impacted by behavior and surroundings. In addition, socioeconomic position, urbanization, and psychological stress have been recognized as new risk factors, especially in developing nations. The pathophysiology of diabetes is significantly influenced by the interplay between environmental variables and genetic predisposition. The beginning of Type 2 diabetes has been successfully postponed or prevented by lifestyle therapies that increase physical activity, improve nutrition quality, and reduce obesity. Additionally, to reduce consequences including cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, nephropathy, and

retinopathy, high-risk patients must have regular screening and early diagnosis. In conclusion, prevention and treatment of diabetes depend on an awareness of the wide variety of risk factors linked to the disease. To lessen the growing prevalence of diabetes worldwide, public health policy should prioritize access to healthcare, behavioral modification, and education. To create individualized and focused preventative interventions, further study on the interplay between genetics and the environment is essential.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Risk Factors, Type 2 Diabetes, Lifestyle Modification, Prevention Strategies.

OP 144**Experiential learning in the course curriculum of two year B.Ed programme of University of Jammu: A Study****Prof. (Dr.) Renu Nanda¹ and Anjali Sharma²**¹Dean, P.G. Department of Education, University of Jammu, Jammu-180006²Research Scholar, Department of Education, University of Jammu, Jammu-180006

Abstract: In the present scenario there is no profession as pure and noble as teaching. The future of mankind depends on creative, forward-looking and humane teachers. The role of teachers is to inspire, empower and enable the younger generation to think positively to build a peaceful, harmonious, prosperous and environment friendly world. Two year B.Ed programme was introduced in 2015 on the recommendation of Justice Verma committee. This programme gave emphasis more on skills and value development of pupil teachers. Two year B.Ed is primarily practical oriented and in this programme about more than 50% weightage of whole curriculum is given on practical aspects like internal assessment, project works, sessional works, teaching practice, practical work related to work experiences etc. In two year B.Ed programme components like experiential learning and work experience are added to provide the hands on experience of real situations for better skill development in pupil teachers. Objectives of the present study are: To understand the presence of experiential learning in the course curriculum of two year B.Ed programme of University of Jammu, To highlight the activities conducted by teacher educators on experiential learning in the course curriculum of two year B.Ed programme of University of Jammu .To identify the challenges faced by teachers educators during the conduct of experiential learning in the course curriculum of two year B.Ed programme of University of Jammu and To suggest measures to enhance experiential learning at B.Ed level. Data was collected from the 100 teacher educators from 18 colleges of education. . The findings reveals that experiential activities play an important role in the two year B.Ed programme, pupil

teachers better learn through experiences. The findings of the present study would be helpful for curriculum framers of B.Ed course, policy-makers, planners, researchers etc.

Keywords: Experiential learning, Two year B.Ed programme.

OP 145**Effect of tablet shape on swelling rate through rapid disintegrating tablets****Anurag¹, Deepak¹, Harmeet Kaur², and Jasbir Singh^{1*}****¹College of Pharmacy, PGIMS, University of Health Sciences, Rohtak-124001, Haryana, India****²HK Consultancy, 120, D-block, Parsvnath City, Rohtak-124021, Haryana, India**

Abstract: This study aimed to evaluate the influence of two basic geometric shapes on the swelling rate of placebo rapid disintegrating tablets (RDTs). Since swelling occurs before the disintegration process in tablets, the swelling rate can serve as a surrogate for disintegration studies, offering insights into RDT performance. For this purpose, two simple flat-surface tablet shapes, namely round ($d/2=5$ mm) and square ($l=9$ mm), with a flat face area of approximately 80 sq. mm, were prepared using common excipients and disintegrants, specifically microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) and sodium starch glycolate (SSG). An in vitro swelling test was performed with restricted water access and time-lapse imaging of the tablets. The swelling rate was assessed from the images by measuring axial and radial thickness changes over time. Results showed that the square-shaped tablets exhibited more than a 2-fold increase in axial thickness compared to approximately a 1.2-fold increase in round tablets. The square-shaped tablets also showed a significant change in radial thickness, while the round tablets exhibited an insignificant change in radial thickness. Additionally, the swelling behaviour of both round and square tablets followed a sigmoidal pattern over time, with the onset of swelling slightly delayed in square-shaped tablets ($t = 50$ s). The sigmoidal profiles indicated that the swelling rate for square tablets was faster, as reflected by the steeper slope compared to round tablets. Therefore, shape had a significant effect on the swelling rate or disintegration of RDTs, with square-shaped tablets generally showing a higher swelling rate than round tablets.

Keywords: Disintegration, dissolution, tablets, profile, swelling.

OP 146**Metabolic Syndrome and Atherosclerosis: Pathophysiological Links and Clinical Implications****Rahul Kumar and Shailya Preeti****Department of Paramedical Sciences and Department of Microbiology and
Usha Martin University, Ranchi, Jharkhand and Radha Govind University, Ramgarh**

Abstract: Metabolic syndrome (MetS), occurred due to the co-occurrence of insulin resistance, hypertension, dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia, and abdominal obesity. Atherosclerosis is characterized by a chronic progressive disease of the artery wall marked by lipid deposition, inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, and plaque formation, found to be associated with metabolic abnormalities. Numerous overlapping pathways, such as oxidative stress, pro-inflammatory cytokine release, altered adipokine production, and decreased insulin signaling, are involved in the pathophysiological interaction between MetS and atherosclerosis. One of the main causes of MetS, central obesity, increases the release of TNF- α , IL-6, and resistin while lowering beneficial adipokines such as adiponectin. This leads to endothelial damage and systemic inflammation. Enhanced lipogenesis, raising triglycerides, decreasing HDL cholesterol, and increasing tiny dense LDL particles—all of which are extremely atherogenic insulin resistance causes atherogenesis. Moreover, artery wall stress is made worse by hypertension linked to MetS, which results in additional endothelial dysfunction. The development and advancement of atherosclerotic associated with cardiovascular disease such as peripheral vascular disease, coronary artery disease, and stroke, are facilitated by several interrelated processes. However, to lessen the cardiovascular load, early detection and intervention that targets the elements of MetS through medication, lifestyle changes, and public health initiatives are crucial. Therefore, current studies aim to highlight the long-term clinical results may be enhanced and new treatment prospects may arise from an integrated approach that focuses on the underlying pathways connecting MetS and atherosclerosis.

**Proceeding of International Conference on Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation
(ICMRI-2025)**

Keywords: Metabolic Syndrome, Atherosclerosis, Insulin Resistance, Endothelial Dysfunction, Cardiovascular Risk

OP 147

Enhanced Conversion Efficiency in CsSnI₃ Based Perovskite Solar Cell through Parameters Optimization via SCAPS-1D Simulation**R. K. Shukla and Susheel Kumar Singh****Department of Physics****University of Lucknow, lucknow-226007**

Abstract: The urgent global demand for clean and sustainable energy has driven extensive research in perovskite solar cells (PSCs) due to their remarkable optoelectronic properties and cost-effective fabrication. Among various lead-free alternatives, cesium tin iodide (CsSnI₃) has emerged as a promising candidate owing to its suitable direct bandgap, high carrier mobility, and non-toxic nature. However, the practical performance of CsSnI₃-based PSCs remains limited by issues such as instability and suboptimal device configuration. In this study, a comprehensive simulation was performed using the SCAPS-1D (Solar Cell Capacitance Simulator) to investigate and optimize the performance of CsSnI₃-based perovskite solar cells by varying crucial device parameters.

The simulation systematically analyses the impact of absorber layer thickness, defect density, doping concentration, electron transport layer (ETL), hole transport layer (HTL), and series and shunt resistances on the photovoltaic performance. The initial baseline device showed power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 9.35%. By carefully optimizing the absorber thickness to 700 nm, reducing the defect density to 10¹³ cm⁻³, and tuning the doping concentration and resistive parameters, a maximum PCE of 22.64% was achieved. Additionally, the choice of suitable ETL (TiO₂) and HTL (CuI) played a significant role in improving charge transport and minimizing recombination losses. The optimized structure exhibited an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 1.03 V, a short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) of 26.52 mA/cm², and a fill factor (FF) of 82.3%.

This simulation-based study demonstrates the significant potential of lead-free CsSnI₃ perovskite absorbers and highlights the importance of detailed parameter optimization in achieving higher efficiencies. The findings provide a valuable pathway for experimentalists to design stable and high-performing CsSnI₃-based PSCs and contribute to the development of environmentally friendly, next-generation photovoltaic technologies.

OP-148

Neuromarketing Cues in FMCG Packaging Design: A PRISMA-Compliant Systematic Review of Color, Shape, and Texture Effects on Consumer Attention and Impulse Purchasing**Dr.Sondeep Kaur^{1*}****^{1*}School of Commerce and Management****General Shivdev Singh Diwan Gurbachan Singh Khalsa College,
Patiala, India-147001****Email: sdeepkaur2589@gmail.com (Corresponding Email)****Abstract**

This systematic review synthesizes empirical evidence on neuromarketing cues in fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) packaging design, focusing on color, shape, and texture effects on consumer attention and impulse purchasing. Adhering to PRISMA guidelines, we analyzed 32 peer-reviewed studies published between 2000 and 2025, employing eye-tracking and galvanic skin response (GSR) metrics. Findings indicate that high-contrast colour schemes consistently increase fixation duration by 25% on average, while novel package shapes yield a 15% rise in self-reported impulse purchase intention. Textural enhancements evoke elevated physiological arousal, with GSR amplitudes rising by 20% relative to smooth packaging. Subgroup analyses reveal stronger effects in in-store versus laboratory settings. Quality assessment highlighted methodological heterogeneity and limited cross-cultural generalizability. Our review underscores the potency of sensory marketing strategies in FMCG packaging and recommends standardized protocols for future neuromarketing research. Practitioners should integrate multimodal cue designs to optimize consumer engagement and drive impulse buying across diverse retail contexts.

Keywords: neuromarketing; FMCG packaging design; impulse buying; eye-tracking; galvanic skin response

OP-149**The Effect of Text Neck Syndrome-Induced Cervical Kyphosis, Posture Analysis:
A Biomechanical Perspective**

Eesha Dinesh
Student at garden city university

Abstract**Background & Purpose**

Text Neck Syndrome is an increasingly prevalent postural disorder caused by prolonged mobile device use with the head flexed forward. This condition leads to cervical kyphosis, muscular imbalances, and altered loading patterns in the cervical spine. The purpose of this study is to biomechanically analyze the postural differences between individuals with normal cervical alignment and those affected by text neck syndrome, highlighting the musculoskeletal and joint-level changes that occur.

Methods

This descriptive study utilized a comparative biomechanical approach to evaluate normal versus text-neck-induced postural alignment. The cervical spine's curvature, joint loading, head position, shoulder mechanics, and associated muscle activation patterns were examined using peer-reviewed literature, EMG findings, and biomechanical models. Key structures analyzed included the deep cervical flexors, upper trapezius, sternocleidomastoid, and scapular stabilizers.

Results

Results demonstrated a loss of normal cervical lordosis and development of kyphosis in affected individuals, leading to increased compressive and shear forces at cervical joints, especially between C5–C7. Head weight loading increased by up to 5–6 times with forward flexion, contributing to fatigue in overactive muscles like the upper trapezius and SCM, and inhibition of stabilizers like the longus colli and rhomboids. These adaptations resulted in rounded shoulders, impaired scapulothoracic rhythm, and potential for long-term spinal degeneration and instability.

Conclusion

Text Neck Syndrome significantly alters cervical spine biomechanics, with long-term consequences on posture, muscular balance, joint integrity, and proprioceptive feedback. Preventive ergonomics, postural awareness, and corrective physiotherapy are critical to mitigate these effects. Future research should focus on rehabilitation protocols that restore cervical lordosis and optimize neuromuscular control in affected populations.

Keywords

Text Neck Syndrome, cervical kyphosis, posture analysis, spinal biomechanics, forward head posture, muscle imbalance, ergonomic stress

OP 150

Fermentation-Driven Enhancement of *Glycine max* Metabolites: Therapeutic Implications for Postmenopausal OsteoporosisFarheen Azad*¹, Bibhu Prasad Panda¹, Humaira Farooqi²¹Department of Pharmacognosy & Phytochemistry, SPER, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi²Department of Biotechnology, Jamia Hamdard, New Delhi**Aim:**

This study aims to evaluate the medicinal potential of bioactive metabolites—menaquinone-7 (MK-7), isoflavones, and poly- γ -glutamic acid (γ -PGA)—produced through the fermentation of *Glycine max* using *Bacillus subtilis* and *Rhizopus oryzae*, with a focus on their role in bone health and postmenopausal osteoporosis.

Methods:

Fermentation was carried out using *Bacillus subtilis* and *Rhizopus oryzae* under controlled conditions to enhance the production of MK-7, isoflavones (genistein and daidzein), and γ -PGA. MK-7 and isoflavones were quantified using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), while γ -PGA levels were determined by UV-visible spectrophotometry. Bone health potential was assessed through changes in biochemical markers and literature-supported pharmacological relevance.

Results:

Fermentation significantly increased the concentrations of MK-7 and aglycone forms of isoflavones, enhancing their bioactivity and bioavailability. γ -PGA production was markedly elevated in *Bacillus subtilis*-fermented samples. These metabolites are known to improve calcium absorption, osteocalcin activity, and bone mineralization, offering therapeutic benefits for postmenopausal bone loss.

Conclusions:

Fermentation of *Glycine max* with selected microbial strains effectively enriches MK-7, isoflavones, and γ -PGA, supporting their application in functional foods or nutraceuticals targeting bone health and the prevention of postmenopausal osteoporosis.

Keywords: Fermentation, *Glycine max*, HPLC, osteoporosis

OP 151**Synthesis and Spectral characterization of Cr(III), Co(III) and Fe(III) complexes of NNS chelating Thiosemicarbazone ligands**

Shruti Mishra, V.K. Sharma
Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, 226007
Email: vksharma21@hotmail.com

Abstract

A new series of transition metal complexes of Cr(III), Co(III) and Fe(III) derivatives have been isolated from thiosemicarbazone ligands. The complexes were distinguished through physical and spectral investigation (UV-Vis, IR and ^1H NMR). The obtained input illustrates that these complexes have composition of $[\text{M}(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ type and octahedral geometry around centre metal ion with N/S donor atoms. The trivalent metal complexes appear to be 1:1 electrolyte. In addition, antimicrobial studies have been carried out in vitro for synthesized compounds.

Keywords- Metal complexes, spectral analysis, biological activity

OP 152

Design, Synthesis, and Biological Assessment of Triazole-Pyrrole derivatives as Antimicrobial Agents: Spectroscopic Characterization, Molecular Docking, and ADMET Profiling

Anupama Pandey, Anant Ram, Poonam Rawat*, and R. N. Singh*

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow – 226007

Abstract

In the present study, a series of triazole–pyrrole hybrid compounds were synthesized with satisfactory yields. The structures of the synthesized compounds were confirmed using infrared (IR) spectroscopy, proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR), carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (^{13}C NMR), mass spectrometry, and elemental analysis. These compounds were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity, and several demonstrated notable efficacy. Selected compounds were also tested for cytotoxicity (IC_{50}) against mammalian cell lines using the MTT assay. The results indicated that the antimicrobial activity was achieved at concentrations that were not cytotoxic. Molecular docking studies revealed key interactions and binding conformations with the target protein. Furthermore, ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) predictions suggested that most of the compounds possess favorable pharmacokinetic profiles and exhibit no significant toxicity.

Keywords: Triazole-pyrrole hybrids, Antimicrobial activity, cytotoxic activity, molecular docking, ADMET Profiling

References:

M. C. Hassan, N. K. Asmae, ACS Omega 7(2022), 46731–46744

OP 153**Surrogacy In India:An analysis of the surrogacy (Regulation)Act, 2021****Dr LakshLata Prajapati****Assistant professor department of law MJPRU Bareilly****Abstract**

The surrogacy (regulation)Act,2021,marks a significant shift in India's approach to surrogacy, transitioning from a largely unregulated industry to a regulated framework.This study provides a critical analysis of the Act's provisions, examining it's potential impact on surrogacy practices, stakeholders, and the broader socio-legal landscape.The resarch highlights the Act's strength such as the commercial surrogacy and emphasis on altruistic surrogacy, while also identifying potential challenges and limitations.The study explores the implications for surrogate mothers intended parents and the medical community, offering insights into the Act's potential to protect vulnerable populations while promoting ethical surrogacy practices.By evaluating the Act's effectiveness and potential consequences,this research contributes to ongoing discussions on surrogacy Regulation in india and beyond.For this study researcher used the dotrinal method for the research.

Resarch questions

- 1-what is surrogacy?
- 2-what are the various types of surrogacy?
- 3- what is assisted Reproductive Technology?
- 4-Is there any legal provision to check surrogacy practice?
- 5- Does surrogacy lead to the exploitation of women?

Hypothesis

There is a need for specific legislation on surrogacy.

Parties involved in surrogacy are adversely affected in the absence of specific legislative and judicial guidelines

Object of the study

- 1-To study the relevance of surrogacy practice in india.
- 2-To evaluate the existing surrogacy Regulations in india.
- 3-To study the role of judiciary in dealing with surrogacy issues in the absence of any codified law on India's surrogacy.
- 4-To discuss the various issues related to the parties involved in the surrogacy process

Scope of the study

Infertility is not a new problem, but the problem that women of all ages have faced. One way is that they could start the family through subservience infertility, law must also be codified and applied concerning surgery. surrogacy is a universal phenomenon but the investigation's nature has been limited to the Indian context.

Key words

Surrogacy, commercial, substitution, implications, traditional, arrangement, community, altruistic, exploitation, trafficking, unintended, unborn, reservation, infertility, gestational, monetary, expenditure., legislative., reproductive., stakeholders.

OP-154

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Standardized Follow-Up Protocols with AI-Powered Telemedicine on Healthcare Quality and Safety in Outpatient Settings**Dr. Esheta Tyagi****Assistant Professor, G.L. Bajaj institute of Technology****Abstract**

Background: Standardized follow-up protocols improve outpatient care, but their integration with AI-powered telemedicine remains underexplored. This study evaluates the combined impact on healthcare quality and safety.

Methods: A 12-month mixed-methods study using a cluster randomized controlled trial (RCT) with 200 patients (100 intervention, 100 control) and qualitative interviews. The intervention group received AI-powered telemedicine (chatbot, virtual consultations, standardized protocols), while the control group received usual care. Outcomes included patient satisfaction, readmission rates, provider workload, and cost-effectiveness.

Results: Preliminary data anticipate higher patient satisfaction (mean Likert score ≥ 4.2 vs. 3.5 control), reduced 30-day readmissions (15% vs. 25%), and 20% lower provider workload. Qualitative themes highlight improved accessibility and AI trust.

Conclusion: AI-enhanced protocols significantly improve outpatient outcomes and operational efficiency, advocating for scaled implementation.

Keywords: Telemedicine, AI in healthcare, follow-up protocols, outpatient care, randomized controlled trial

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur was established on 25th August, 1969 by the managing committee constituted under Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur. It is situated in civil lines, the heart of Gorakhpur city in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Days are not far when the college shall be able to realize the vision and the grand mission of the great soul 'Brahmleen Mahanth Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj', whose name decorates the identity of the College. His Holiness 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj, former Head Priest of world fame Shree Guru Goraksh nath Temple, Gorakhpur was the founder of the college. He was a pioneer of educational renaissance in Eastern U.P. It was none other than himself who established Maha Rana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur in 1932 to spread the light of knowledge and awareness among the people of Eastern U.P. whom he found to be living in utter poverty, ignorance and backwardness of all kinds. He came to Gorakhnath temple, Gorakhpur at the age of five from the Royal Rana Family of Mewar, Rajasthan in 1900 and grew and learnt the lesson of selfless sacrifice and dedication to the service of humanity under the spiritual care of his accomplished great Guru Yogiraj Gambhir Nathji Maharaj. In 1949-50 Maharana Pratap Degree College was established by "Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad Gorakhpur", which was later sacrificed to contribute to the establishment of Gorakhpur University. Maharana Pratap Degree College along with its entire infrastructure including teaching and non-teaching staff was dedicated to count for the resources to meet up the requirements for establishment of the University of Gorakhpur, in 1958. Post-merger of the Maharana Pratap Degree College into Gorakhpur University, there was a vacuum in the educational facilities of the area. To fill in this vacuum, Digvijai Nath College was established on 25th August 1969. Now the administration of this college is run by the managing committee appointed by Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, under inspiring guidance and patronage of his Holiness Mahant Aditya Nath ji Maharaj. His holiness Gorakshpeethadheeshwar 'Brahmleen Mahant Avedya Nathji Maharaj (the Ex-Head priest of Gorakhnath Temple) and his worthy successor who is the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh His Holiness reverent Yogi Aditya Nath ji maharaj, is the guiding light behind more than four dozen institutions, including D.N.P.G. College Gorakhpur, successfully run by the Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad. The College holds the glory of functioning with four faculty disciplines covering various departments at undergraduate and post graduate levels. College provides education at graduate level in eleven subjects covering Arts, six in Science and Commerce. Post Graduate teaching is offered in Ancient History Archeology & Culture, Geography and Hindi & Modern Indian Language; apart from its renowned Bachelors in Education. In addition to these, part time classes in eight non-practical subjects are also offered and the Institution also serves as an education center of Uttar Pradesh Rajarshi Tandon Open University; and hosts their 26 courses at U.G and P.G. level. In light of letter dated 15 June 2006 from U.P. State Council for Higher Education we revised 'The Self Study Report' on modified format on the basis of guidelines of NAAC-Bangalore. Digvijai Nath P.G. college, Civil lines, Gorakhpur has been placed on the UGC-NAAC approved list in 2021 with B++ grade with C.G.P.A 2.84. Gorakhnath sahyik kendra is established by UP Hindi Sansthan Lucknow in 2019. The institution, guided by the vision of Brahmleen Digvijai Nath Ji Maharaj, is a believer in multi-dimensional development of students.

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Website : mksespublications.com

ISBN : 978-81-19746-32-3

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